

**RESEARCH INTO THE FEASIBILITY AND VIABILITY OF
STARTING AN**

Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy – Sri Lanka

by

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STUDENT NUMBER : 2015004024

Dissertation submitted in part fulfilment of the requirements for the

Post Graduate Diploma in Business Enterprise

In the Faculty of Business

At

SOUTHERN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

INVERCARGILL, NEW ZEALAND

Supervisor : Dale Hinkley

April, 2016

Word count: 23934

Declaration

I, S.M.D.N.B. Samarakoon, declare that this dissertation is my own work and has not previously been submitted for academic examination towards any qualification. The ideas presented are own opinions and not necessarily those of the Southern Institute of Technology.

Signed:

Date :

Acknowledgement

I am using this opportunity to express my gratitude to my dissertation supervisor, Dale Hinkley for the guidance and excellent support given me during the entire period and without her guidance and persistent support, this dissertation would not have been possible. I would also like to thank all the lectures of Postgraduate Diploma in Business Enterprise at Southern Institute of Technology; Monika Barton, Fiona Tyrie, Julian Galt, Tom Downey, Eric Tan and Dr. Jerry Hoffman for the extraordinary support provided during the course of this program.

Last but not least, I would like to convey my sincere thanks to all the participants who took part in the research and also who has directly or indirectly participated in this research study.

Abstract

This dissertation investigates the tourism and hospitality market in Sri Lanka in order to develop a strategic plan for the start-up of an Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy-Sri Lanka. This research involves discovering the feasibility of operating an eco-friendly budget hotel in the Kandy hospitality market in terms of market demand, trends, gaps, competition, segmentation, finance, profitability and country's political and economic environment.

Secondary data has been analysed in the literature review and further secondary data that are related to statistical projections has been analysed in chapter five. Primary research is carried out by a survey and face to face interviews respectively. The respondents were potential target customers and hoteliers, in order to capture information from different stakeholders.

The researcher has developed a business plan that addresses the gaps identified throughout the research. The proposed hotel's core concept addressed the upcoming inbound and domestic tourists; who like to experience eco lodging facilities for an economical price. The business plan discusses in further detail all relevant sections under the headings of business concept, marketing strategies, human resource planning, implementation and financial plan.

Contents

Declaration.....	i
Acknowledgement	ii
Abstract.....	iii
List of Tables	x
List of Figures.....	xii
Glossary	xiv
Chapter 01 – Introduction	1
1.1. The Business Concept.....	1
1.2. Value provided to customers.....	2
1.3. Purpose of the dissertation	3
1.4. The research question for the dissertation.....	3
1.5. Research objectives of the dissertation	3
Chapter 02 - Literature Review.....	5
2.1. The purpose of literature review and its significance	5
2.2.1. Overview of Sri Lankan tourism industry	5
2.2.2 Eco-Tourism and Eco hotel practices.....	5
2.3. Industry trends in hospitality sector	6
2.4. Monthly tourism growth, demand and market gap	8
2.5. Purpose of visit.....	9
2.6. The city of Kandy as a tourist destination.....	10
2.7. Occupancy rates	10
2.8. Gap between eco-tourist needs and eco hotel services	11
2.9. How Sri Lankan political environment effects on hospitality industry	12
2.10. The consequences of economic environment to the proposed business	13
2.11. Doing business in Sri Lanka.....	15
2.12. Conclusion.....	16

Chapter 03 - Methodology	18
3.1 Purpose and relevance of research methodology	18
3.2. Research tools and design	18
3.2.1. Primary research	20
3.2.2. Secondary research	27
3.3. Limitations and controlling bias.....	27
Chapter 04 – Ethics.....	28
4.1. Informed consent.....	28
4.2. Confidentiality.....	28
4.3. Risk of harm	29
4.4. Data storage.....	29
4.5. Culture.....	29
4.6. No deception	29
4.7. Right to withdraw.....	29
Chapter 05 – Results and findings	30
5.1. Survey Analysis.....	30
5.2. Face-to-face interview analysis	50
5.3. Further Secondary analysis	62
Chapter 06 – Business concept	63
6.1.1. The proposed hotel business concept	63
6.1.2. Business model.....	66
6.1.3. Business Vision, Mission, and Goals	67
6.2. Strengths of proposed business model	68
6.3. The benefit of the business to customers and stakeholders.....	70
6.4. Industry and environment analysis.....	71
6.4.1 STEPE Analysis	71
6.4.2. Porter’s Five Forces analysis.....	73

6.4.3. SWOT analysis	76
6.4.4. TOWS Strategic Matrix Analysis.....	77
6.4.5. Competitive analysis.....	78
6.5. Competitive advantage.....	80
Chapter 07 - Marketing plan.....	81
7.1. Marketing Objectives	81
7.2. Marketing strategies	83
7.2.1. Relationship marketing strategy	83
7.2.2. Positioning.....	84
7.2.3. Online presence	84
7.2.4. Cause Marketing.....	84
7.2.5. Partner up.....	85
7.3. The target market of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel.....	86
7.4. Needs, wants, preferences and characteristics of target market segments	88
7.4.1. Needs and wants	88
7.4.2. Preferences.....	88
7.4.3. Characteristics	89
7.5. Appraising and quantifying customer numbers and projected revenues.....	90
7.6. Marketing mix.....	93
7.6.1. Product.....	94
7.6.2. Price	96
7.6.3. Place.....	98
7.6.4. Promotion	99
7.7. Marketing action plan.....	106
Chapter 08 -Human resources.....	112
8.1. The proposed hotel HRM model.....	112
8.2. The proposed hotel human resource objectives	113

8.3. Staffing & organisational flow	114
8.4. Recruitment & Selection Process	118
8.5. Training & Development program	119
8.6. Supervision.....	121
8.7. Performance management	121
8.8. Compensation and benefits	122
8.9. Career development.....	122
8.10. Remuneration	123
8.11. Human resource decision making philosophy of the proposed business	124
Chapter 09 - Key operational and implementation issues	125
9.1. Key operational issues and potential challenges	125
9.1.1. Supplier chain	125
9.1.2. Quality assurance.....	125
9.1.3. Legal requirements	125
9.1.4. Waste management.....	126
9.1.5. Stock control.....	126
9.1.6. Skilled labour demand and high employee turnover	126
9.1.7. Hygiene, sanitation and PEST control.....	127
9.1.8. Managing debtors	127
9.1.9. Energy management	127
9.1.10. Organisational development	128
9.2. Risk management strategy	128
9.3. Action plan	132
Chapter 10 - Financial plan.....	137
10.1. Key resources	137
10.2.1. Main capital expenditure items and source of supply	139
10.2.2. Legal requirements	140

10.3. Purchasing, stock control and staffing issues.....	140
10.4. Justifying expected sales and profit scenario	142
10.4.1. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel : Breakeven analysis for the year 2018	144
10.4.2. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Breakeven analysis for the year 2019	145
10.4.3. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Breakeven analysis for the year 2020	146
10.4.4. Payback period	147
10.5. Financial reports.....	147
10.5.1. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2018	148
10.5.2. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2019	149
10.5.3. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2020	150
10.5.4. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Profit & Loss account for the years ending 2018, 2019 and 2020	151
10.5.5. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Balance Sheet ending for the years 2018, 2019 and 2020	152
10.6. Strategies for business sustainability & Ratio analysis.....	153
10.6.1. Strategies:	153
10.6.2. Ratio analysis:.....	153
10.7. Growth strategies.....	155
10.8. Contingency plan.....	156
Conclusion	158
References.....	159
Appendices.....	166
Appendix 01. Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence - 2008 to 2014	166
Appendix 02. World Disposable Income Map.....	167
Appendix 03. Survey questionnaire	168
Appendix 04. Guideline for interviewer: survey questionnire.....	175
Appendix 05. Interview questionnaire	176
Appendix 06. Guideline for interviewer: Face to Face Interview	182

Appendix 07. Further secondary research.....	184
Appendix 08. Business Canvas Model Analysis.....	188
Appendix 09. Seasonality of Tourist Traffic 2014.....	190
Appendix 10. Tourist Nights & Occupancy Rates by Month 2014	190
Appendix 11. Capital Assets depreciation	191
Appendix 12. Income Statement of the Jetwing hotel	192
Appendix 13. Balance sheet of the Jetwing hotel	193

List of Tables

Table 01. Monthly Tourist Arrivals & Growth Rates in Sri Lanka -2014/15.....	8
Table 02. Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence – Top Ten Countries	14
Table 03. Timeframe of the Survey Process.....	22
Table 04. Timeframe of the Interview Process.....	26
Table 05. The relationship of tourist type, gender and age.....	30
Table 06. The reason of travel & visiting here with:	33
Table 07. Favourite hotel type & rating of reservation in an eco-hotel for next five years....	34
Table 08. Eco-practices of the hoteliers.....	50
Table 09. Target market rating of the interviewed hoteliers.....	51
Table 10. The skilled labour market availability in Sri Lanka	58
Table 11. Customer rating of spending in terms of Accommodation, Food & Beverage, Entertainment, Leisure and Other	60
Table 12. Competitive analysis.....	79
Table 13. Projected unit sales – 2018	90
Table 14. Projected unit sales – 2019	90
Table 15. Projected unit sales – 2020	91
Table 16. Projected revenues – 2018	91
Table 17. Projected revenues – 2019	91
Table 18. Projected revenues – 2020	92
Table 19. Communication objectives	100
Table 20. The hotel’s chosen media channels and reasons for choosing.....	102
Table 21. Pre-launch marketing action plan	107
Table 22. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2018	108
Table 23. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2019	109
Table 24. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2020	110
Table 25. Projected staff recruitments	115
Table 26. Employees responsibilities, duties, relationship and reporting flow	116
Table 27. Induction programme.....	119
Table 28. Training & Development programme.....	120
Table 29. Projected remuneration.....	123
Table 30. Identified potential risks, strategies and actions	129
Table 31. Pre-launch Action Plan	133

Table 32. Post launch Action Plan – 2018.....	134
Table 33. Action Plan – 2019	135
Table 34. Action Plan – 2020	136
Table 35. Start-up cost	138
Table 36. Main capital expenditure items, quantity and source of supply	139
Table 37. Types of stocks & control methods	141
Table 38. Payback period.....	147
Table 39. Ratio analysis.....	153
Table 40. Contingency plan	157
Table 41. Tourist Arrivals Forecast 2016-2020.....	185

List of Figures

Figure 01. Tourist Arrivals and Accommodation Details – 2002 to 2016.....	9
Figure 02. Purpose of Visit 2014	9
Figure 03. Occupancy Rates by Resort Region – 2013 / 14	11
Figure 04. Sri Lanka Tourist Arrivals Target 2010-2016	12
Figure 05. How Sri Lanka & Comparator Economics Rank on the Ease of Doing Business	15
Figure 06. Rankings on Doing Business Topic – Sri Lanka.....	16
Figure 07. Research tools and design	19
Figure 08. Sample Respondents.....	21
Figure 09. Informed Consent – Questionnaire & Face to Face Interview	28
Figure 10. Representative sample of international tourist	31
Figure 11. Provincial representative sample of domestic tourist.....	32
Figure 12. The frequency of tourist returning.....	32
Figure 13. Accommodation percentage of Eco-Hotels.....	34
Figure 14. Respondents rating in terms of the importance of social responsibility.....	35
Figure 15. Respondents rating in terms of the importance of natural surrounding	36
Figure 16. Respondents rating in terms of importance of the hotel location.....	36
Figure 17. Respondents rating in terms of importance of the hotel price.....	37
Figure 18. Respondents rating in terms of eco-hotels as a today’s main trend	37
Figure 19. Respondents rating in terms of building material - Cement &Concrete	38
Figure 20. Respondents rating in terms of building material - Timber & Mud.....	38
Figure 21. Respondents rating in terms of importance of cultural exchange, organic food, responsible tourism & ayurvedic	39
Figure 22. Respondents rating in terms of importance of Room service, Laundry service, Transport arrangements & Ticket bookings	40
Figure 23. Familiarity evaluation of the budget hotel concept	41
Figure 24. Respondents rating of the hotel’s innovative concept and location	42
Figure 25. Respondents average holidays per year & preferred holiday periods	43
Figure 26. Average holiday nights of the respondents	44
Figure 27. Respondents preferred types of reservations and services	45
Figure 28. Respondent’s occupation & average spending on lodging facilities.....	46
Figure 29. Types of media used to update and find about the hotels.....	47
Figure 30. Education background of the respondents.....	47

Figure 31. Respondent’s marital status and average income level	48
Figure 32. Representation of hoteliers interviewed	50
Figure 33. Services & facilities provided by the interviewees	52
Figure 34. Respondents rating about Price, Location, Brand & Service standards in terms of importance to operating a successful hotel business.....	53
Figure 35. True factor of the statement : “The current eco-friendly trends in the hospitality market are leading to responsible tourism”	55
Figure 36. The level of competition in Kandy hotel market.....	57
Figure 37. The raw material availability in terms of quality & standards	59
Figure 38. The proposed hotel floor plan.....	64
Figure 39. Business Canvas Model of the proposed hotel.....	66
Figure 40. Porter’s Five Forces analysis.....	73
Figure 41. SWOT analysis.....	76
Figure 42. TOWS Strategic Matrix Analysis.....	77
Figure 43. Relationship marketing orientation	83
Figure 44. Market Segmentation.....	86
Figure 45. The hotel’s target customers.....	87
Figure 46. The proposed hotel’s Marketing Mix	93
Figure 47. The hotel’s product-service / equipment-people continuum.	94
Figure 48. The hotel’s layers of products	95
Figure 49. The hotel’s pricing model.....	96
Figure 50. The hotel distribution model	98
Figure 51. Communication plan of the proposed hotel.....	99
Figure 52. The hotel’s core message content.....	101
Figure 53. Launching – advertisement.....	104
Figure 54. Promotional advertisement.....	105
Figure 55. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel HR model.....	112
Figure 56. Organisational flow	114
Figure 57. Organisational development model	128
Figure 58. The hotel’s expected Sales, Gross profit and Net profit after tax	142
Figure 59. Total contribution of Travel & Tourism to GDP.....	184
Figure 60. Forecast Visitor Exports & Foreign Tourist Arrivals – 2025	186

Glossary

Eco hotel

An environment friendly lodging facility that follows the practices of green living.

Eco tourism

Ecotourism is about uniting conservation, communities, and sustainable travel.

Alternative tourism

Alternative tourism is the opposite of mass organised tourism. It involves personal travel and authentic and it encourages interaction with the local environment, people and communities.

Green consumerism

The situation in which consumers want to buy things that have been produced in a way that protects the natural environment.

Hotel occupancy rate

The percentage of all units occupied at a given time.

Leisure tourist

Tourist traveling with relation to leisure activities is known as leisure tourist.

Business tourist

Tourist traveling with relation to business is known as business tourist.

Budget hotel

A lodging facility that provide standardized and limited service, at affordable prices.

Visitor exports

Spending within the country by international tourists for both business and leisure trips, including transportation spending.

Chapter 01 – Introduction

1.1. The Business Concept

The business concept is to establish an “Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel” in the world heritage city Kandy, Sri Lanka. The main idea here is to create an innovative concept of providing an eco-friendly experience to the customers for a budget price.

The target customers will be leisure tourists, with limited economic capacity, who are interested in experiencing nature and local culture. The proposed hotel will be significantly targeting inbound tourists who have already visited Sri Lanka and then other inbound tourists and local tourists.

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be located near the ‘Hanthana’ range of mountains where tourists are able to experience the rich green natural beauty of the mountains and forests. This Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be built using timber and mud which would resemble the traditional rural houses in Sri Lanka. Moreover, the hotel will conduct a cultural event in every Saturday night allowing tourists to experience the cultural music, dance and food. It is expected that this feature will help the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel to differentiate itself from its main competitors.

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will position itself to provide healthy and organic food to its customers by cultivating its vegetables and fruits in the hotel’s premises. However, being a budget hotel, the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel only offers complimentary breakfast with its accommodation. There will be a common cooking facility where its customers will be able to cook their food.

The Eco-friendly budget hotel will consist of ten units that can accommodate 2-3 guests per unit. The hotel will also provide facilities like interconnecting the units upon customer’s request. The hotel will consist of a team of eleven members including the owner Mr. Nilan Samarakoon. In terms of customer security, the hotel will install a higher technological fire alarm system for the fire protection and security officers from a reputed company to ensure other safety matters. Apart from lodging facilities, the proposed hotel will also offer concierge facilities like airport pickup and pre-bookings. To strengthen the customer

relationship and customers' loyalty, the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will offer personal assistance to each of its customers.

The hotel distribution channels will include direct sales through online and on premises and indirect sales through wholesalers by 60% and 40% respectively. The hotel's main revenue stream will be rooms which consist with transaction revenue and recurring revenue.

Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will closely work with its key partners: government agencies, industry associations, tour operators, suppliers, financial institutions, insurance companies and logistics services to obtain support and facilities for its daily operation.

1.2. Value provided to customers

The eco-friendly and cultural experience at a budgeted price is the core value that Eco-friendly budget hotel will provide to its customers. There are a considerable number of eco-hotels already existing in Sri Lanka. However, none of them offer services at low prices as they follow a value-driven cost structure such as focusing on creating values regardless of cost. This would mean that they maintain a premium value proposition. The proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will follow a cost-driven structure by keeping the cost to a minimum and offering services at a budget price. Therefore, the proposed hotel customer value proposition will be built considering both budget price and eco-concept.

By being a part of the eco-friendly practices of proposed hotel, the latter will not only create a place in the heart of the customers but also will allow them to feel proud that they are participating in the social responsibility of the society. In addition, cultural events will deliver the fun and excitement to the tourists and this will be another benefit that the customers of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will receive. In line with providing organic food, Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be able to provide healthy value to its customers.

Moreover, customers' value proposition will be increased through the hotel's location as it will be in the midst of a rich green environment. This will help the customers to experience relaxation and peacefulness. The individually focused services that are provided by the proposed hotel will enhance customer satisfaction too.

1.3. Purpose of the dissertation

The main purpose of this dissertation is to examine the viability of establishing an Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy, Sri Lanka. By analysing the market competition, gaps, demand, market segment, volume, finance requirements, profitability, customer preferences, industry trends, customer values, labour market and environment analysis; the researcher will be able to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the business and also implement strategies that will lead towards its business goals.

1.4. The research question for the dissertation

- ❖ Is it feasible to operate an ‘Eco-Friendly Budget hotel’ in Sri Lanka?

Hence, the research question can be divided as follows in terms of understanding depth of the term “feasibility”:

- How is it feasible in terms of competition and point of difference?
- How is it feasible in terms of financial projection and profitability?
- How is it feasible in terms of market segmentation?
- How is it feasible in terms of human resources and operational issues?
- How is it feasible in terms of the political environment?
- How is it feasible in terms of market demand and trends?
- How is it feasible in terms of economy and business environment?

1.5. Research objectives of the dissertation

- To identify the demand, trends, gaps and opportunities in the Sri Lankan hospitality industry.
- To understand the competition in Sri Lankan hospitality context and the points of differences.
- To identify the target market segment and potential customers’ needs and preferences.
- To understand how the political environment reflects with the hospitality industry in Sri Lanka.
- To understand how the economy environment reflects with the hotel businesses in Sri Lanka.

- To understand how the business is being done in Sri Lanka.
- To determine the operational requirements and issues in the business such as in marketing, finance, human resource, operational and others.

Chapter 02 - Literature Review

2.1. The purpose of literature review and its significance

The purpose of writing this literature review is to identify the feasibility of starting an environment-friendly budget hotel business in Sri Lanka by finding its operating strengths and weaknesses. The aim of this literature review is to recognise the current hospitality market, trends, gaps, competition and other influencing macro factors to hospitality-related businesses.

Through the research on current hospitality market, demand, gaps, trends and the other micro and macro factors of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel, the viability of the business will be pre-evaluated and thereby the ground level of operational feasibility will be analysed. This will guide the business founder on deciding whether the proposed business is worth being set up or not and eventually it will help to implement the strategies that are required to establish a successful eco-friendly budget hotel.

2.2.1. Overview of Sri Lankan tourism industry

The Sri Lankan government has found tourism as its long-term economic thrust area as it is one of the current key drivers of economic growth. Sri Lankan tourism has been significantly growing after the end of the post-war period; statistically from 0.45 million tourist arrivals in 2009 to 1.28 million in 2013. According to Sri Lankan tourism strategic plan, expected target of tourist arrivals is 2.5 million for the year of 2016. (Esham, 2014). In year 2014, Sri Lankan tourism has significantly increased to a new milestone of 1,527,153 arrivals; that has exceeded all time high hits historically which is an increase of 19.8% compared to 2013 tourist arrivals which was 1,274,593. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 5)

2.2.2 Eco-Tourism and Eco hotel practices

The attitudes of today's tourists has gradually changed from traditional beach tourism to natural, cultural and social interactions. "There is a new phenomenon, which is broadly termed as 'Alternative Tourism'. Eco-tourism that comes into the category of alternative tourism has emerged with the collaboration of cultural, rural, nature tourism, and its related activities as a niche market." (Arachchi, Yajid, & Khatibi, 2015)

Hector Ceballos-Lascurain introduced the term 'Eco-tourism' in 1983. However, “Their definitions were later revised in 1993 to move the focus to conservation and the role of the tourist from a passive observer of nature to participant together with responsibility for its preservation. Eco-tourism introduced as environmentally responsible travel and visitation to relatively undisturbed natural areas, to enjoy and appreciate nature that promotes conservation” (Arachchi, Yajid, & Khatibi, 2015). Furthermore, the World Tourism Organisation recognised eco-tourism as the fastest growing segment of the tourism industry. (Buckley, 1994; Deardon & Harron, 1993). The concept of “Green consumerism” and other social-environmental movements increased environmental awareness among the general public over the last two decades. Therefore, today’s hotel business are concerned about the natural environment more than ever before by trying to minimise the damage that occurs to the natural environment from their daily operations. (Bohdanowicz, Simanic, & Martinac, 2005)

2.3. Industry trends in hospitality sector

The World Tourism Organisation’s report of “Tourism in the Green Economy 2012” has identified that the tourists’ choices are influenced by the concept of sustainability as they consider how far the business operates in an eco-friendly manner. Thus, the report highlighted that eco-tourism will grow within the next two decades while increasing at a higher rate compared to the entire tourism industry. Moreover, the TripAdvisor’s survey of 2012-2013 has recognised that 79% of global travellers expect that lodging facility providers should maintain eco-friendly practices. (The Case for Responsible Travel, 2014, p. 2) This proves that the current trend of the hospitality industry is leading to environment-friendly hotels.

The ‘Balancing for the Future Success of Tourism in Sri Lanka’ article highlights, the eco-friendly tourism as one of the major trends in Generation Y and younger people as they are highly environmentally conscious. (Biyagamage & Jayawardena, 2013, p. 507). In Sri Lanka, 276 hotels have already adopted the environment-friendly practices due to the high demand for eco-friendly hotels. As the European Union has recognised the importance of eco-friendly hotel practices, they are currently funding a major programme in Sri Lanka which improves hotels’ performances enhancing energy, water and waste management. (Miththapala, Mudadeniya, & Jayawardena, 2013, p. 448)

A study of the hotel industry in Wennappuwa, Sri Lanka has identified that the eco-friendly hotel concept is not only just an environmental protection tool but also a marketing strategy. The aim of the study was to identify the relationship between eco-concept as a hotel marketing tool and customer relationship. “The finding of the present study indicates that a positive relationship was observed between environmental product and place strategies and customer satisfaction of the Hotel Industry in Wennappuwa”. (Perera & Pushpanathan, 2015)

The budget hotel concept is not a new concept in the world of hospitality industry. However, the budget hotels are becoming as a new trend in today’s hospitality context because of its significant growth. As an example, the UK budget hotel sector has achieved remarkable growth during the last few years and currently has 24.2% market share in the UK. (Hotel Britain, 2014, p. 14) However, the eco-friendly budget hotel concept is going to be a totally new concept for Sri Lankan hospitality market as no such eco-friendly budget hotel has been introduced yet. Thus, the researcher has tried to find any academic evidence that proves the existence of such eco-friendly budget hotels and however, unfortunately he could not find any evidence to support this claim. The majority of tourists who visited Sri Lanka are from Europe, India, China, and USA (See the Appendix 1) where the people are very familiar with budget hotels and eco-hotels. Therefore, the proposed eco-friendly budget hotel will be able to attract these customers as they are familiar with both budget and eco hotel concepts. Furthermore, according to an industry report in India, a 5.2 % fall in RevPAR was observed in 2012-2013 with the five-star segments; however, an average increase rate of 10.4 % to 14.7 was registered for budget and economic hotels. (Drillinger, 2013). Therefore, the proposed business has a high probability of survival in the future compared to competitors.

2.4. Monthly tourism growth, demand and market gap

Table 01. illustrates the monthly tourism growth rates in Sri Lanka during 2014 and 2015. Thus, it shows 17.9% increase of overall tourists' arrivals in the year 2015 when considering statistics up to the month of October. As observed in Appendix 1, Sri Lanka's total tourists' arrivals have raised by 19.8% in 2014 compared to 2013 respectively 1,527,153 and 1,274,593. However, due to the rapid growth of tourists' arrivals in Sri Lanka, the market demand for hotel rooms are increasing dramatically.

Month	2014	2015*	% Cha. 2014/15
January	146,575	156,246	6.6
February	141,878	165,541	16.7
March	133,048	157,051	18.0
April	112,631	122,217	8.5
May	90,046	113,529	26.1
June	103,175	115,467	11.9
July	133,971	175,804	31.2
August	140,319	166,610	18.7
September	105,535	143,374	35.9
October	121,576	132,280	8.8
November	119,727		
December	178,672		
Total	1,527,153		
Up to October	1,228,754	1,448,119	17.9

Table 01. Monthly Tourist Arrivals & Growth Rates in Sri Lanka -2014/15
(Tourism Research & Statistics, n.d.)

The following figure 01. highlights the estimated tourist arrivals in 2016 (2.5 million) and the required hotel rooms (45,000 rooms) to cater for these arrivals. According to the 2014 statistics, the available Graded and Supplementary hotel rooms in Sri Lanka were 28,426. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 41) Therefore, the difference between rooms' demand and the supply is approximately around 16,575 which indicates the hassle free market entrance for new hoteliers.

Figure 01. Tourist Arrivals and Accommodation Details – 2002 to 2016 (IFC World Bank Group, 2013, p. 38)

2.5. Purpose of visit

Figure 02. Purpose of Visit 2014(Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 28)

As shown in figure 02, 67.9% of tourists are interested in visiting Sri Lanka mostly for pleasure activities. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 28) The pleasure tourists expect leisure experience paralleled to business tourists who expect business facilities such as meeting rooms and conference halls. As per the above figures only 1.3% business tourists

visited Sri Lanka in the year 2014 which shows that there is a more demand for hotels that offer leisure experience. Therefore, the proposed hotel's demand will be at a higher level as it offers extraordinary leisure experience to its valued customers.

2.6. The city of Kandy as a tourist destination

The city of Kandy was recognised as a World Heritage Site where the Temple of Sacred Tooth Relic has been located. (Timothy & Nyaupane, 2009, p. 137) Therefore, many people are visiting Kandy to worship the Temple of Sacred Tooth Relic from all over the world. Thus, world renowned Kandy Esala Procession which is also known as "Esala Perahera" is one of the top cultural festivals in Sri Lanka which is conducted in mid of every year. (Frey, Lemmer, & Namasivayam, 2001)

The sources from Temple of Sacred Tooth Relic confirmed that there were more than 8,000 international tourists who watched the procession touring the streets in 2012. "Speaking to Sri Lanka Tourism Promotion Bureau Media Unit, President of Kandy City Hoteliers Association Rodney Armstrong stated that almost all city hotels in Kandy and other accommodation houses are 80% occupied from the beginning of Esala procession and will fully occupy in the next four days."(Ceylon Today, 2012)

As Kandy has been a religious and cultural destination, the demand for lodging facilities will also remain constantly high. Thereby, equally the visits of the international and domestic tourists are increasing every year. Since the proposed hotel will be located in the city of Kandy, the market demand also will be at a higher level.

2.7. Occupancy rates

The overall annual room occupancy rate of tourist hotels in Sri Lanka has increased to 74.3% in 2014 from 71.7% in 2013. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 11) Moreover, following figure 03. indicates occupancy rates by resort region in 2014 compared to 2013. As highlighted, the city of Kandy is categorised under the ancient cities, and its occupancy rate had increased by 1.5% in 2014 compared to 2013. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 42) These results confirm the sustainability of the proposed business and also demand of the hospitality market in Kandy.

Figure 03. Occupancy Rates by Resort Region – 2013 / 14 (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 42)

2.8. Gap between eco-tourist needs and eco hotel services

The international journal of ‘Comparison of Eco-Tourism Practices in Sri Lankan Eco Resorts From Customer and Supplier Viewpoint’ has identified that the eco hotel practices in Sri Lanka have not met with the eco-tourists’ expectations as they do not follow the accurate international eco-friendly standards. Sri Lankan hoteliers’ have conceded only a few aspects of eco practicing elements compare to the international eco practices components and standards. (Arachchi, Yajid, & Khatibi, 2015). This issue has created a gap between the needs of the eco-tourists and the services of the eco hoteliers. Therefore, the proposed eco-hotel will significantly put its emphasis on this area and tries to fill the eco-tourists’ needs by following international eco-friendly standards.

2.9. How Sri Lankan political environment effects on hospitality industry

To further promote the Sri Lankan Government's vision, (Mahinda Chinthana, 2010, p. 94) the government has launched a Tourism Development Strategy plan which will maximise the tourist arrivals from 650,000 in 2010 to 2.5 million by 2016 as shown in Figure 04.

Figure 04. Sri Lanka Tourist Arrivals Target 2010-2016 (Tourism Development Strategy 2011-2016, 2010, p. 12)

The other objectives of the strategic plan includes a gaining of USD 3,000 million as Foreign Direct Investment; increasing hospitality related jobs from 125,000 in 2010 to 500,000 by 2016 and the allocation of these economic benefits gained out of tourism to the larger cross section of society while promoting Sri Lanka as the world's most treasured Island for tourism. The ultimate target was to increase the foreign exchange earnings from USD 500 million in 2010 to USD 2.75 billion by 2016. (Tourism Development Strategy 2011-2016, 2010, p. 4)

As mentioned earlier, in line with 2.5 million tourist arrivals by 2016, the estimated requirement of hotel rooms leads to approximately around 45,000. (Tourism Development Strategy 2011-2016, 2010, pp. 4, 8). Therefore, the hotel industry will require more upcoming entrepreneurs to serve the Sri Lankan hospitality industry and thus, it will be highly feasible to start up a new hotel venture in Sri Lanka as there will be a tremendous support from the Sri Lankan government.

Moreover, the Sri Lankan government has introduced a policy framework in order to support entrepreneurs and the tourism industry which includes; simple tax regime and licensing procedures, concession rates on high electricity tariffs and streamlining the process of isolating government land for tourism development projects. Thus, taxes on tourism-related business are subject to a 12% of the income. Also when commencing a business related to leisure and tourism activities, plant and machinery as well as branded consumer products are subject to low taxes. (Tourism Development Strategy 2011-2016, 2010, pp. 6, 7). However, since 1st September 2013, the organisations licensed under the Tourism Act 14 of 1968 were requested to pay 1% as a Tourism Levy. (TDL, 2013)

Furthermore, Sri Lankan Tourism Development Authority (SLTDA) is encouraging the financial institutes to offer low-interest loan facilities and grants for the Small Medium Enterprise sector. Also, SLTDA is providing concessions to the SME sector when taking part in the events organised by them. As an example, SME's were charged only 25% of selling cost whereas the other large companies were charged 50% or full amount when attending a recognised trade fair. (Tourism Development Strategy 2011-2016, 2010, p. 11) Because of the facilities that are offered by the Sri Lankan government, it is self-explanatory for the encouragement provided to strengthen further hospitality related proposed business.

2.10. The consequences of economic environment to the proposed business

Sri Lanka is located in South Asian Region and recognised as a Lower Middle-Income country with a population of 20,483,000. (Doing Business 2015, 2014) The Household Income and Expenditure Survey 2012/2013 has recognised the Mean household income as LKR 45,868 and the Mean Household Expenditure as LKR 41,444. (Household Income and Expenditure Survey 2012/2013, 2015) Thus, it shows that the Household unit could save LKR 4,424 per month which they might spend on other activities such as holidays. Therefore, it could be concluded that Sri Lanka has sufficient domestic market for tourism, even though Sri Lanka highly focused on inbound tourism. Furthermore, as proposed business offers low price accommodation, there are higher potential to meet local tourists' value too in line with their low spending capacity.

Table 02. Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence – Top Ten Countries (Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence, 2015)

Rank	Country	2014	2015	% Cha
1	India	54,154	64,781	19.6
2	China	28,798	53,135	84.5
3	U.K.	39,035	44,813	14.8
4	Germany	32,964	38,725	17.5
5	France	28,313	31,891	12.6
6	Russia	29,371	23,133	(21.2)
7	Maldives	19,992	19,629	(1.8)
8	Australia	12,467	13,868	11.2
9	U.S.A.	10,120	12,674	25.2
10	Japan	10,009	11,074	10.6

Table 02. highlights the top 10 countries that visited Sri Lanka in 2014-15. (World Tourism Data, 2014, p. 7) The most of these countries recognise as economically established countries. As shown in Appendix 02, these countries are maintaining a high level of disposable income; that leads to higher spending capacity and therefore, can directly reflect to generate more foreign earnings in the Sri Lankan hospitality context. There may be a conflict between higher level income tourists' needs and proposed hotel concept. A rich tourist might like to have five-star hotel facility rather than choosing a budget hotel as they do not concern that much about money. However, there is still a niche market that is interested in eco-hotel facilities for the budget price that the proposed hotel is looking forward to serve.

2.11. Doing business in Sri Lanka

As shown in figure 05, Sri Lanka's economy is positioned under the rank number 99 in terms of the ease of doing business. (Doing Business 2015, 2014, p. 7) However, compared to South Asian region, Sri Lanka is placed on top that indicates the proposed business is going to be started in the right place.

Figure 05. How Sri Lanka & Comparator Economics Rank on the Ease of Doing Business (Doing Business 2015, 2014)

Moreover, as detailed in following figure 06, starting a business in Sri Lanka may be quite hard as it is positioning at 104th place in the world. However, compared to a bigger country like India, it holds a much better position as India has fallen to rank 158. (Doing Business 2015, 2014, p. 11) In terms of protecting minority investors, Sri Lanka is in a better position which is one of the major positive fact for the new entrepreneurs and hence an opportunity for the researcher to open an eco-friendly budget hotel here.(Doing Business 2015, 2014, p. 9).

Figure 06. Rankings on Doing Business Topic – Sri Lanka(Doing Business 2015, 2014)

2.12. Conclusion

The Sri Lankan government has found tourism as its long-term economic thrust area as it is one of the current key drivers of economic growth. Sri Lankan tourism has acquired significant growth after the end of the post-war period, from 0.45 million tourist arrivals in 2009 to 1.28 million in 2013. The total tourist arrivals in Sri Lanka have risen by 19.8 percent in 2014 compared to 2013. Thus, the Sri Lankan government has the vision of increasing tourists' arrivals by 2.5 million in 2016.

The estimated required new hotel rooms will be approximately 16,575 to bridge the gap between supply and demand with expected tourist arrivals in 2016. Thus, starting a hospitality venture will be a great idea as the government will also offer additional facilities such as financial grants and low tax schemes to encourage the SME sector.

The tourism experts have recognised that the tourist choices are highly influenced by eco-tourism. As a result, the majority of hotels have already started eco-friendly practices, and this will eventually become a trend. The budget hotels have also become the new trend in today's hospitality context during the past few years; therefore, setting up an eco-friendly budget hotel in Sri Lanka is likely to be highly accepted by today's tourists.

Due to its household income, there is also a considerable domestic tourism market available in the country; even though Sri Lanka is highly focused on inbound tourism. Furthermore,

because Kandy is a religious and cultural destination, the demand for lodging facilities will also remain constantly high. However, there will be a higher level of competition of starting hospitality ventures in Sri Lanka since the tourism industry is gaining more popularity.

Beside the fact that, Sri Lanka currently holds the rank number 99 in terms of the ease of doing business, it is still in a better position compared to other countries in the South Asian region. Therefore, it confirms that the proposed business will be placed in the right place. In conclusion, as per the data revealed in the literature review, most of the factors are favourable to the proposed business and it will have fruitful opportunities for its growth and potential both for international and domestic market. There is an excellent opportunity that it will be feasible to start up an eco-friendly budget hotel in one of the ancient city Kandy in Sri Lanka.

Chapter 03 - Methodology

3.1 Purpose and relevance of research methodology

“A methodology is an approach to the process of research, encompassing a body of methods.” (Collis & Hussey, 2014). In other words, it is a way to find out the results of a given problem on a specific matter or a problem that is also referred to as a research problem. (Research Management. Michigan, 2010). In this Methodology section, the researcher will use different criteria, sources and methods for solving the given research problem which is on setting up an eco-friendly budget hotel in Sri Lanka.

The purpose of this research methodology is to find the answers to the research objectives in a systematic way that will guide the researcher in setting-up his hotel business. By applying the correct methodology, the researcher will be able to analyse the strengths and the weaknesses of the proposed business. Nevertheless, it will also help to analyse the current and the potential business situation which includes the threats, opportunities and issues. These results will help the researcher to develop the business strategies that will lead to his business success. However, if the researcher does not choose the right methodology, the results will be inaccurate and unreliable which will negatively impact the business strategies and decision making. Therefore, picking up the correct research methodology and the process is highly important to find accurate outcomes and strategies for the proposed business. (Research management. Michigan, 2010)

3.2. Research tools and design

The research methods can be divided into two forms that are known as primary research and secondary research. The primary research is a new research that is carried out by the researcher through methodologies such as interviews, surveys, observations and many more. The secondary research can be defined as collecting data from existing sources such as books, reports, journals, online and so on. (Hox & Boeije, 2005).

In this research work, the researcher will use both primary and secondary research methods to explore the research question in a more accurate way. The primary research will focus on understanding potential customer’s preferences, trends, values, pricing, facilities, location, experience, and so on. In this case, the researcher will conduct both a questionnaire survey

and a face to face interview as the primary research. The aim of the questionnaire is to gather general information about customers' behaviour; while the face to face interview will focus on gathering in-depth information of the business environment.

The literature review was useful in designing the questionnaire and the face to face questions, and consequently it will support when the primary data is being analysed. Furthermore, apart from the literature review, here, the researcher will conduct a secondary research that is expected to forecast the statistics related to hospitality and provide information such as future growth, demand, market size, trends, and opportunities of the business. The research tools and design are summarised in figure 07.

Primary research	Questionnaire	<i>To understand in general:</i> Customer preferences, customer trends, spending capacity, values, facilities, location, hotel nights, tourist type, experience and so on.
	Face to face interview	<i>To understand in depth:</i> Demand, competition, seasonality, industry trends, gaps, operational issues, profitability, business values, labour market, suppliers, pricing, facilities, location, experience, and so on.
Secondary research	Literature review Web sites, statistics, reports, journals, articles & books	<i>To understand:</i> Experts ideas, industry changes, regulations, current market demand and supply, gaps, trends, political and economic environments, opportunities, risks and so on.
	Further Secondary research Web sites, reports, statistics and magazines	<i>To find:</i> Forecast statistics and information –future demand, market size, opportunities and trends.

Figure 07. Research tools and design

3.2.1. Primary research

A) Questionnaire

Purpose

The objective of carrying out this research is to understand today's customer preferences, trends, values, pricing, the type of tourists, holiday periods, hotel nights and so on. These outcomes will help the researcher to gain information related to his business in general terms. Research questionnaire is the best research tool since it matches the researcher's needs such as collection of a large amount of information in a short period and also it relatively cost effective. In this research, the following research criteria will be mainly evaluated.

- Today's customer preferences for an eco-friendly budget hotel practices.
- Expected facilities, services and previous experience.
- Holiday period and hotel nights.
- Understanding the type of tourist such as individual / couple / family / group.
- Today's tourist trends.
- Average spending capacity.
- Distribution channel.
- The tourist preference for hotel locations and surrounding.
- To understand the customer values.
- Customer opinions –about lodging facilities.

Design

The questionnaire consists of open and close questions, with a ranking scale. Moreover, the researcher has followed general principles of questionnaire design such as avoid leading questions, jargon, colloquialisms and doubled barrel question. Also, the questionnaire was designed shorter in order to encourage the respondents. Thus, the researcher does not ask questions like; what is your income, and how much you will spend, as these questions are difficult to answer because this sample of respondents use various currencies and therefore, the calculation involves currency exchange rates. Further, survey questionnaire is described in appendix 03.

The sample

The questionnaire will follow stratified random sampling technique. “Stratified random sampling method involves selecting a simple from each of given number of subpopulations or strata” (Mendenhall, Beaver, & Beaver, 2013, p. 245). As discussed earlier, the proposed hotel’s target customers include both international and domestic tourists. However, the hotel will focus highly on inbound tourists which is approximately 75% and the rest will be local tourists. Therefore, the questionnaire sample will also consist same as its target customers; so that out of the hundred respondents, 75 questionnaires will be given to international tourists, and other 25 questionnaires will be distributed among the local tourists as described in figure 08. Since the proposed business is significantly targeting on inbound leisure tourists who has already visited Sri Lanka, this sampling method and process will be highly accurate and a good representative of its target group. If a sample does not match with its target group, the researcher will not be able to gather the correct information and its results may affect the research data and consequently caused business failure. Therefore, it is highly important to have an accurate sample to conduct the research. Moreover, the sample respondents cut off age will be eighteen and no-one under eighteen will be selected.

Figure 08. Sample Respondents

Procedure

The research process will be conducted by the researcher’s sister, Miss. Nilescha Kumari, who has decent research experience background. The questionnaires will be distributed in ‘Kandy’ city center area where a very high number of international tourists can be found. As mentioned earlier, ‘Kandy’ is a world heritage city and therefore thousands of tourist visits the city every day. Miss Nilescha Kumari will select the respondents randomly and ask them to fill the questionnaires. She will pick up the second tourist that she will see in every ten

minutes, respectively to maintain random respondents. Further, guidelines for the Miss. Nillesha were provided and described in appendix 04.

The survey process will start on 15th October 2015 and end by November 2015. Below table 03. shows the timeframe for the questionnaire survey process.

Outcomes	Timeline
Designing the survey questionnaires	2 weeks
Pilot study and finalizing	1 week
Sending, and data collection	3 weeks
Analysis	2 weeks

Table 03. Timeframe of the Survey Process

Validity and reliability

The validity of the sample will be high as the researcher is gathering his required information directly from respondents. Also, validity related to questionnaire design. Since each question in the questionnaire was checked by the supervisor and rewritten to make sure it would get valid answer, validity of this research was reinforced. Thus, this research will be well designed to measure what it is intended to measure. Therefore, the research instrument will allow to hit the research objectives.

Since the research instrument consistently measures what it is anticipated to measure; its accurate representation of respondents will maximise its research reliability. Therefore, the research instrument is considered to be reliable for this research. This means that if the respondent was asked the question again, they would give the same answer.

Pilot study

The pilot study can be used to recognize the plus and minus points in questionnaires well in advance. Thus, it also checks wording and understanding of the questionnaire. Therefore; the pilot study helps to send a perfect error-free and valid questionnaire to the final participants. Considering that, the researcher will send his designed survey questionnaires to some of his friends to seek their advices. Depending on their guidance, the researcher will be able to eliminate the errors and thus design a good questionnaire that will be easier to interpret by the participants.

How will the data be analysed?

The questionnaires produced quantitative data that can be easily analysed using Microsoft Excel Sheet. Therefore, the author will use Microsoft Excel Sheet to analyse the primary data. Using the different tools such as Graphs, Charts and others from the Excel Sheet, the author will display all the collected data that will be easily interpreted by business analysts as discussed in the result section.

B) Face to face interview

Purpose

The reason for carrying out a face to face interview is to understand the hospitality demand, competition, seasonality, industry trends, gaps, operational issues, profitability, business values, pricing, facilities, location and experience in depth. The main advantage of using the Face to face interview in this research work is because of its accurate screening and also the interviewer; Miss Nileshta Kumari will have a full control over keeping the interviewees focused and on track during the whole interview process. Therefore, by selecting the face to face method the researcher will be able to gather in-depth information about the research question from the chosen hoteliers or managers. In this face to face interview, the following research criteria will be evaluated.

- Demand in the hotel business.
- Industry trends.
- Business values, facilities and location.
- Competition, labour market and suppliers.
- Seasonality, occupancy rate and operational issues.
- What are the customer values – in terms of price / service / quality / brand?
- Which types of eco-practices can be followed – waste management, energy management, recycle, organic and so on?
- Profitability and pricing strategies.
- What are the other extra services that customers expect - airport pick-up / Adventure programs?
- Spending capacity in depth – how much for accommodation? Food & beverage, and for other leisure activities?
- Hoteliers experience and opinions – on lodging facilities.

Design

The face to face questionnaire was designed in line with semi-structured technique such as mixing both open and closed ended questions and it is described in appendix 05. This will help to gather both qualitative and quantitative information. Moreover, here, the researcher

has used probing questions expecting to obtain more specific answers and to decrease vague and ambiguous responses.

Sample

The researcher here will follow the simple random sampling method. “A sampling procedure which gives equal chance to all possible samples each of size n which can be drawn from a population of size N , is called simple random sampling (Kushwaha & Kumar, 2009, p. 25). The participant hoteliers will be representing small and medium size hotel business in ‘Kandy’ area where the proposed hotel is going to be located. Thus, most of them are following the eco concept and others will represent the small and medium size budget hotels. Since these hotels in Kandy follows the same concepts as proposed business, it will be representative of the sample. On the other hand, it will allow the researcher to gather accurate and in depth information based on his research question. The researcher expects to interview 20 hoteliers due to its higher potential refusals. However, the minimum expected interviewees to be conducted will be ten.

Procedure

The interviewer will be Miss. Nilescha Kumari, and each interview will be conducted for 08-12 minutes. In line with simple random sampling method, the researcher will take a list of small and medium hoteliers from Sri Lankan Tourism Board and then put their names on a piece of paper, put all pieces of paper into a box and draw chits at random. After that, the researcher will make a telephone call to each selected hotel and ask for permission to conduct a face to face interview with the hotelier or the management. If permission is refused, it will be carried out with the next hotelier in the list. Interview date and time will be scheduled depending on the appropriate time for the hoteliers. All necessary guidance was provided to Miss. Nilescha and its outlined in appendix 06.

Moreover, the interviewer will ask permission to record the interview process. However, the interviewer will also note the answers while conducting the interview process. The interview process will be conducted for two months, and it will start on 1st November 2015. The projected timeframe for the interview process is as following table 04 .

Table 04. Timeframe of the Interview Process

Target	Timeline
Designing the questionnaire	2 weeks
Conduct the interviews	8 weeks
Analysing the data	2 weeks

Validity and reliability

By interviewing hotel owners and management, the researcher will be able to collect true information in regards to his research question. Thus, the interview questions will be designed in order to capture the in-depth information of the research question. Therefore, the research validity is assured as it accurately reach the research objectives. Furthermore, as the research instrument consistently measures what it is intended to measure, its accurate representation of sample confirms that the instrument is highly reliable.

Pilot study

The pilot study of the interview increases the interviewer's confidence to talk with the participants while helping to understand any error or areas that need to be improved. Therefore, Ms. Nilescha Kumari will practice a few interviews with some individuals to improve the interview skills.

How will the data be analysed?

Since this is an interview, the researcher will receive qualitative data. The qualitative data is quite challenging to analyse compared to quantitative data. However, the qualitative data can be analysed by a common theme and categories. Nevertheless, qualitative data is more efficient compared to quantitative data as it represents participant's feedback in depth. Moreover, interview data will be analysed using both Microsoft Word and Excel as it consists of both qualitative and quantitative data.

3.2.2. Secondary research

As stated earlier, the secondary data that were investigated in the literature review, were beneficial to design the questionnaires and subsequently, it will support when the primary data are being analysed.

Moreover, the secondary research details such as forecast statistics and information will be examined in relation to hospitality related projections. These will include future growth, market size, trends and opportunities. These data will provide a clear vision about the potential hospitality business in Sri Lanka. Moreover, projected statistical data and information will be analysed using government reports and other trustworthy reports like ‘Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka’, published by The World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC).

3.3. Limitations and controlling bias

The budget limitation has limited the participation of a large number of respondents in questionnaire survey and face to face interview. Thus, the budget limitation has prevented the researcher accessing some important secondary data too. Moreover, the legal and ethical constraints have prevented the researcher in some ways within the research methodology and so some valuable data and information will not be able to be obtained.

“Bias occurs when the result of study are systematically different from truth” (Health Research Methodology, 2011). Bias leads to incorrect answers to the research question and it will consequently result in business failures. In order to eliminate bias, the researcher used the following mechanisms;

- Following appropriate sample methods.
- Developing clear, short and probe questions and avoiding asking leading questions.
- Picking a neutral researcher who does not have inspiration for achieving one result over another.
- Using an appropriate collection method
- Keeping a neutral research environment

Chapter 04 – Ethics

Ethical considerations were addressed related to studying compliance and regulations of the Southern Institute of Technology ethical practices in research.

4.1. Informed consent

One of the key components of ethically correct behaviour is informed consent. The researcher must provide a clear statement of what the research is about and what role the respondents would play in it. Therefore, in this research, participants are informed about this research objectives and process involved as described in figure 09.

Questionnaire	On the top of the questionnaire, all adequate information will be provided. All the participants who answer the questionnaire will be automatically given the responsibility to voluntarily participate in this research without any influence.
Face to Face Interview	All interviewees will be informed about the interview process, outcomes, and purpose. The researcher will obtain permission from the participants to record the interview and use it as a part of his research work. The interviewees will be requested to sign a consent form where they are informed all the process and consequences of this interview.

Figure 09. Informed Consent – Questionnaire & Face to Face Interview

4.2. Confidentiality

The information of the participants will not be revealed and therefore, their privacy will be protected. The survey questionnaire and each interview will be assessed by using the serial number when reporting the result. Thus, interviewees' name and designations will be kept optionally. This will reduce the risk that can be harmful for the interviewees' employment. Moreover, all studied information, data, and the results will be kept confidential by storing them. (see 4.4 below)

4.3. Risk of harm

The researcher leaves out sensitive questions through the questionnaire and interview process. The researcher respects respondents' comments and values throughout the interview process, and there will no more threatened or physical offence for the respondents' outcomes.

4.4. Data storage

Data will be saved in Google cloud and personal PC with well secured password. Furthermore, the researcher will keep hard copies of all the data in his personal locker. All information and data related to research will be destroyed after the research outcomes will be achieved.

4.5. Culture

Since this research is conducted both international and local respondents, the researcher will genuinely consider each respondent's cultural values and their dignity. Both international tourists and local people may have different values and opinions with respect to their country and culture. Therefore, the researcher will conduct the research in respect of all cultural values by getting a good understanding of them before starting the research.

4.6. No deception

The collected data will not be amended or misrepresented and will be used only for the research purpose. All the process and actions that will be taken in this research will be fully transparent. Moreover, all participants will be given the right to request for a summary of the research outcomes.

4.7. Right to withdraw

The participants are free to withdraw their applications at any time.

Chapter 05 – Results and findings

This section of the report reveals the results of the study and enables the researcher to understand and identify opportunities within the hospitality market in Kandy-Sri Lanka. Different methods have been used to analyse the data retrieved from the survey, face to face interview and further secondary that were conducted. All data received from survey was converted to a Microsoft Excel format and was transformed into visual data form such as, bar charts, pie charts and contingency tables so as to compare and understand the relationships between different factors related to the eco-friendly budget hotel. The Face-to-face interviews and further secondary data were analysed using “Themes”; where the recorded interviews were classified using different coding that represented the respondents.

5.1. Survey Analysis

Question 1, 21 and 22: Type, gender and age of respondents

Type of respondent	Number of R.	Male	Female	18-25 Years	26-35 Years	36-45 Years	46-55 Years	More than 55
International Tourist	75/100	50	25	21	19	11	15	09
Domestic Tourist	25/100	17	08	02	11	10	02	-
Total	100	67	33	23	30	21	17	09

Table 05. The relationship of tourist type, gender and age

The main objective of conducting these questions was to find out the sample representation of the hotel target market. The secondary objective was to identify gender variance of potential target market and their age boundaries. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted by the researcher where 75 international respondents and 25 local respondents were chosen to carry out the research. The above contingency table 05. depicts the relationship of the tourist type, gender and age categories. Out of 75 international respondents, 25 were female and 50 were male. Out of total number of domestic respondents, 17 respondents were male and 8 were female. Therefore, the total male tourists contribution were 67% and total female contribution were 33%. Further, out of 100 respondents, 53 respondents were within age group of 18-35 years which shows that the majority of tourist who visit Sri Lanka are young

and around middle age. Further, this findings will be used when the proposed hotel develops its marketing strategies such as for the distribution channels and communication plan.

Question 2: Write the country you are from (International tourist)

Figure 10. Representative sample of international tourist

The above figure 10. illustrates a number of international tourists represented. The highest percentage is from India with 24%, followed by UK with 14%. Therefore, as mentioned earlier in the secondary data, it can be concluded that both data have shown that India, UK, China, Maldives, Japan, Russia, Australia, Germany, France and USA are the top-ten countries that visit Sri Lanka. Furthermore, it can be concluded that Sri Lanka has been visited by tourists from all over the world such as from Europe, Asia, America and Australian region. Further, this research result and the secondary data give confidence that the proposed business targeting has the right target customer representation as it is significantly targeting tourists from India, UK, China, Russia, Germany, Japan and so on.

Question 3: Where are you from (Domestic tourists)

Figure 11. Provincial representative sample of domestic tourist

Figure 11. analyses the number of domestic tourists’ who live in each Province. The majority of tourists were from Western Province with 32% and second highest 20% were from Central Province. In line with all provinces being represented, it indicates that Kandy is one of reputed local tourist attraction in Sri Lanka and thus, this will be considered when the researcher develops his proposed business marketing strategies like distribution channels, promotional events and communication plan.

Question 4: Will you visit here again

Figure 12. The frequency of tourist returning

Since the proposed business target tourists are who visited Sri Lanka, the aim of this question was to identify the frequency of tourist returning back. As shown in figure 12, 73% tourists’ idea was to definitely to visit Kandy-Sri Lanka again and 22% have stated as probably they

will visit Kandy-Sri Lanka again. Thus, this is a good sign for the proposed business and this will be revisited when the researcher develops his proposed business marketing strategies like promotional and communication plan.

Question 5 & 6 : What is your reason to travel & you are visiting here with

Reason	Number of respondents	With family	By yourself	With friends	With business G	Other
Family V.	14	14	-	-	-	-
Religion	17	13	03	01	-	-
Leisure	55	25	12	18		
Business	07	-	-	-	07	-
Other	05	01	01	02	-	01
Studying	02	-	02	-	-	-
Total	100	53	18	21	07	01

Table 06. The reason of travel & visiting here with:

The main objective here was to understand the major reasons to travel and also to identify the number of tourists and individuals accompanying with them. As can be seen in table 06, 55 tourists were travelling to Kandy-Sri Lanka for leisure which means that the secondary data reviewed in literature review under the statistical report 2014 was reinforced. Furthermore, it was also found that out of those 55 tourists, 25 tourists travelled with their family while 18 of them visited the Kandy with their friends. This shows that leasured tourists generally travel within a group of people, which is good for the Sri Lankan hospitality market and for the proposed business. This result indicates that there would be an increase in hotel occupancy.

The second main reason of visiting Kandy-Sri Lanka was religion purpose. This strengthen the secondary data which were discussed in literature review such as Kandy is a World Heritage city and religious attraction due to Temple of Tooth is a site visited by many tourists. Further, this will be considered when the researcher implement marketing strategies for the proposed hotel of him such as “Temple of Tooth” can be used as a promotional landmark as it is a World Heritage Site.

Question 7: Have you ever stayed in an eco-hotel before?

Figure 13. Accommodation percentage of Eco-Hotels

Based on the respondents, 43% stated that they were accommodated in an eco-hotel before and 57% have never stayed in an eco-friendly hotel. (Figure 13) Therefore, it can be concluded that a reasonable percentage of tourists are familiar with eco hotels and that shows a positive sign for the proposed eco-hotel.

Question 8 & 9: What is your favourite hotel category and will you take a holiday in an eco-hotel within next five year time?

Hotel type	Amount	Definitely	Very likely	Not sure	Unlikely	No
Beach	10	-	06	03	01	-
Motel	10	-	06	02	01	01
Eco	35	10	24	01	-	-
Budget	12	-	05	06	01	-
Guest house	11	-	07	04	-	-
U. S. Star	10	-	05	03	02	-
Cabana	09	03	06	-	-	-
Other	03	-	01	02	-	-
Total	100	13	60	21	05	01

Table 07. Favourite hotel type & rating of reservation in an eco-hotel for next five years

The objective here was to understand tourists' favourite hotel type and also whether they are willing to take accommodation in an eco-hotel within next five years. As described in table 07, the majority of tourists stated that their favourite hotel was an eco-hotel and out of these, 24 tourists also claimed that they would take accommodation again in an eco-hotel during the next five year. 10 tourists stated that they would definitely take accommodation in an eco-

hotel within next five year while only one tourist stated that he/she was not sure. This result indicates that eco customers are willing to continue their favourite hotel category as eco-hotels and hence are loyal customers.

Further, 12 tourists stated that their favourite hotel category was budget hotel and out of these respondents, 5 stated that they were willing to take accommodation to an eco-hotel facility during the next five year time which was an advantage for the researcher's proposed innovative concept of eco and budget hotel concepts combination.

Moreover, from the above table it also can be seen that out of 100 tourists, 60 stated that they would very likely take accommodation in an eco-hotel within next five years and 13 said that they would definitely take an initiative even though their favourite hotel types vary. This indicates that eco-hotel market will significantly increase in future and thus there is high probability for the proposed business.

Question 10: When you are making a choice to stay at an eco-hotel; rate the followings in terms of importance to your decision. (1=Less important & 5=Most important)

10.1. As a Social Responsibility

Figure 14. Respondents rating in terms of the importance of social responsibility

Figure 14. shows, 38% respondents rated social responsibility 5 and 46% respondents rated it 4 which states that today's customers are highly socially responsible when they make a eco-hotel reservations. This also supports the topics that have been discussed in literature review and thus shows a higher potential for the eco hospitality market. Further, in line with other respondents; 14% rated 3, 10% rated 1 and another 10% rated 2.

10.2. Natural Surrounding

Figure 15. Respondents rating in terms of the importance of natural surrounding

As shown in figure 15, out of 100 respondents, 57 rated 5 and 28 of respondents rated 4, considering natural surrounding which shows that today's tourists are highly concerned about the natural environment when they are choosing eco hotels. This will be a plus point to the proposed Eco-friendly Budget Hotel as it will be located in rich green environment.

10.3. Location - easy access

Figure 16. Respondents rating in terms of importance of the hotel location

The 54% of tourists rated easy access to location 5 and 31% of tourists rated 4 while others rated 3. (Figure 16) According to this result, it can be concluded that the majority of tourists consider easy access for their preferred lodging facility. Further, the proposed hotel will be located in Kandy city area where the potential customer needs will be fulfilled.

10.4. Price

Figure 17. Respondents rating in terms of importance of the hotel price

The above figure 17 shows that the 77% tourists are highly concerned about the product price when they are making choice of eco-hotel accommodation. Therefore, the proposed hotel budget concept will be positively affected, as it helps to deliver quality services for economical price.

10.5. Because I think the eco hotels are a main trend of today.

Figure 18. Respondents rating in terms of eco-hotels as a today's main trend

Out of 100 respondents, 36 of them rated 5 and 34 of them rated 4; which indicates most of tourists believe that the eco-hotels are today's trend. (Figure 18) This also reinforces the topics that have been discussed in the literature review.

10.6.1. Hotel Design - Cement & Concrete

The objective here was to understand potential customers' idea and their preferences of hotel designing.

Figure 19. Respondents rating in terms of building material - Cement & Concrete

27% tourists rated cement and concrete 1 and 17% rated 2. However, 29% rated 4 and 11% rated 5. (Figure 19) This result indicates that some tourists like cement constructed eco hotels while others do not have such a preference or do not consider this as an important factor while choosing hotels

10.6.2. Hotel design - Timber & Mud

Figure 20. Respondents rating in terms of building material - Timber & Mud

Above figure 20. shows that the 33% of respondents rated timber and mud as high importance and 15 respondents rated 4 while 29% rated 3. According to this result, it can be concluded that the majority of eco tourists like their accommodation to be built with timber and mud. Thus, this result also reinforces the proposed hotel design as it is going to be built with timber and mud.

10.7. Hotel concept - Cultural exchange, Organic food, Responsible tourism and Ayurvedic

Cultural Exchange			Organic Food			Responsible Tourism			Ayurvedic		
Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average
01	01	01%	01	00	00%	01	01	01%	01	00	00%
02	17	17%	02	02	02%	02	00	00%	02	10	10%
03	10	10%	03	08	08%	03	30	30%	03	31	31%
04	33	33%	04	35	35%	04	40	40%	04	43	43%
05	39	39%	05	55	55%	05	29	29%	05	16	16%

Figure 21. Respondents rating in terms of importance of cultural exchange, organic food, responsible tourism & ayurvedic

The researcher’s aim was here to find the preferred hotel concepts of his potential customers. Out of 100 customers, 39% rated cultural exchange 5 as most important and 33% rated 4 which also is considered as important when purchasing eco accommodation. (Figure 21)

55% respondents rated organic food as 5, while 35% rated it just as important, that was 4. This result indicates that the today’s eco tourists are highly interested in organic food at their hotel accommodation and it will be one of main reasons when deciding to buy their accommodation. According to the rating result of responsible tourism concept, majority of tourists said it was more important when they making their purchasing decision of hotel accommodation and 29 % of respondents rated 5 as very important and 40% of them rated 4.

In line with analysed result of Ayurvedic concept, it can be concluded that is not highly important for customer’s decision of purchasing, as only 16% of respondents rated 5 and 43% and 31% of respondents rated it 4 and 3 accordingly.

Furthermore, the above analysed result also shows that the researcher’s proposed hotel concept is acceptable and highly accurate. That’s why the final hotel concept emphasises cultural exchange, organic food and responsible tourism.

10.8. Services - Room service, Laundry service, Transport arrangements and Ticket bookings

Room Service			Laundry Service			Transport Arrangements			Ticket Bookings		
Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average	Rate	Total	Average
01	11	11%	01	17	17%	01	00	00%	01	05	05%
02	20	20%	02	21	21%	02	00	00%	02	05	05%
03	46	46%	03	37	37%	03	21	21%	03	23	23%
04	15	15%	04	13	13%	04	48	48%	04	28	28%
05	08	08%	05	12	12%	05	31	31%	05	39	39%

Figure 22. Respondents rating in terms of importance of Room service, Laundry service, Transport arrangements & Ticket bookings

The main objective here was to understand the preferred services of proposed eco hotel’s potential customers. (Figure 22) In line with room services, only 8% rated it as a highly importance which indicates today’s eco customers do not pay much attention to room service from eco hotels.

Only 12% tourists rated the laundry service 5 and 17% rated it as a less importance, which shows tourists are not much interested to laundry services from eco hotels. However, in line with transport arrangement service, 31% of tourists rated 5 and 48% rated 04 which clearly states today’s tourists prefer this service to be offered by eco hotels.

Out of 100 tourists, 39% rated 05 under the ticket booking service and 28% rated 04 which distinguishes the tourists are highly interested to be offered ticket booking services by eco-hotels. Thus, this result indicates that the proposed hotel services of transport arrangements and ticket booking services which are offered to customers will be suitable concepts.

Question 11: Are you familiar with “Budget hotel” concept?

Figure 23. Familiarity evaluation of the budget hotel concept

As above figure 23. shows, 8% of respondents were extremely familiar with budget hotel and 17% were very familiar; 27% respondents were quite familiar and 34% were somewhat familiar. This result shows that the majority of today’s tourists are familiar with budget hotels and thus, the researcher could use promotion to help more people to become even more very familiar.

Question 12 & 13: What do you think about opening a new hotel that is combined with both eco and budget hotel concepts? & Setting up and eco-friendly budget hotel in Kandy is a Idea?

	Excellent idea	Good idea	Neutral	Bad idea	Very bad idea	Total
Excellent idea	44	04	-	-	-	48
Good idea	11	32	-	-	-	43
Neutral	07	02	-	-	-	09
Bad idea	-	-	-	-	-	-
Very bad idea	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	62	38	-	-	-	100

Figure 24. Respondents rating of the hotel’s innovative concept and location

The purpose here was to understand the potential of the customer's opinion about the proposed hotel innovative concept and its location. As shown in above figure 24, 48 tourists said it was an excellent idea to be opened a new hotel that combined both eco and budget hotel concepts. Out of these tourists, 44 said it was an excellent idea to setup this hotel in Kandy and 04 said it was a good idea. Furthermore, 43 tourist said it was a good idea to open a new hotel that combined both eco and budget hotel concepts and out of them, 11 said that it was an excellent idea to open this hotel in Kandy. Thus, 32 said it was a good idea. This results clearly states that the idea and the location chosen by the researcher are correct and highly acceptable in today's hospitality market.

Question 14 & 15: How often do you take holidays per year & When do you prefer to take a holiday?

	Mar-May	Jun-Aug	Sep-Oct	Dec-Feb	Total
Once	07	06	04	38	55
Twice	06	11	05	18	40
Three times	01	-	-	03	04
Four times	-	-	-	01	01
More than four t.	-	-	-	-	-
Total	14	17	09	60	100

Figure 25. Respondents average holidays per year & preferred holiday periods

The purpose of these questions was to understand the potential customer preferences of their holiday periods and their average holidays per year. Out of 100 tourists, 55 stated that they took holidays once a year and out of them, 38 said that they took holidays from December to February. Further, out of 40 respondents who said twice, 18 took holidays from December to February. (Figure 25) Therefore, it can be concluded that the seasonality in December to February and thus, majority of tourists take holidays once or twice per year. Further, the researcher will highly consider this fact when he formulates strategies for the proposed business such as staffing and marketing strategy.

Question 16: How many days would you like to take as your holiday?

Figure 26. Average holiday nights of the respondents

The objective here was to find the average hotel night of the proposed hotel's target customer. The majority of 64% said that they took 8-14 days as their holidays and 28% said 3-7 days. (Figure 26)

Question 17 & 18: Would you like to make your reservation as? & What type of service you would prefer?

	S. Service	Personalised S.	S & P Service	Total
Bed and Breakfast	07	04	44	55
Half Board	04	04	09	17
Full Board	-	01	09	10
Only room	01	09	08	18
Total	12	18	70	100

Figure 27. Respondents preferred types of reservations and services

The researcher’s aim was here to find the potential customer preference of reservation type and service that they preferred. Out of 100, 55 said that they made their reservation as bed and breakfast and 17 said half board. In line with service type, 70 tourists said that they preferred self-service and personalized service combination. Further, out of these 70 tourists, 44 said that they made their reservation as bed and breakfast. (Figure 27) This result clearly states that today’s tourists are highly interested in bed and breakfast while expecting both self and personalised service combination which exactly proposed hotel will be offered.

Question 19 & 23: How much would you like to spend for your lodging facilities? & Occupation

	Student	Unemp.	P. Time	F. Time	Retired	Self-employee	total
Lowest as possible	01	03	05	17	-	01	27
Somewhat budget	03	04	08	20	07	11	53
Average	01	02	03	10	03	01	20
Very High	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Extremely high	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	05	09	16	47	10	13	100

Figure 28. Respondent's occupation & average spending on lodging facilities

As per Figure 28, 53 respondents have said somewhat budget and 27 said lowest as possible. Other 20 said average and no one stated very high or extremely high which indicates no one wants to spend high amount for their accommodation. Thus, this result shows that respondents' occupation does not affect spending on lodging facilities as everyone is willing to spend low, budget or average for their accommodation. In this case, the proposed hotel will be benefited as its offers economical lodging facility.

Question 20: What type of media are you using to find and updates about hotels?

Figure 29. Types of media used to update and find about the hotels

As above figure 29. shows, 45% respondents used social media for update and finding about the hotels. Apart from that, 26% used internet sites and 12% used newspapers and magazines. This result indicates that the present day tourist highly prefers social media and internet sites to find and update about lodging facilities. So, the proposed business’s marketing strategies will be developed related to the preference of the respondents. This will mean that the strategies will be more productive.

Question 24: Educational background

Figure 30. Education background of the respondents

As outlined in figure 30, 49% tourists finished their secondary education and 29% were graduates. Moreover, 10% tourists were qualified with postgraduate degree and 1% were qualified with doctoral degree. This analysed data shows that the majority of tourists are well

educated and thus, consequently it will increase responsibility of tourism as they are well educated.

Question 25, 26 & 27: Are you single or married / relationship?, If single rate your income, If married / relationship rate your income.

	V. Low	Low	Average	High	V. High	Total
Single	10	10	15	-	-	35
Married	03	26	24	10	02	65
Total	13	36	39	10	02	100

Figure 31. Respondent's marital status and average income level

The researcher's objective here was to understand the respondents' income level which is in line with their family status. As above figure 31. indicates, 35 tourists were single and 65 were married. Out of that 35 singles, 10 tourists said that their income was very low and another 10 said it was low. Rest of 15 stated that their income was average. However, in line with married 65 tourists, 10 said their income was high and 02 said very high. Further, there were only 03 tourists who said that their income was very low. Therefore, it can be concluded that the single tourist's income is generally low compared to married tourists or tourists who are in relationship because they may have two income sources.

Question 28: What is your opinion about opening an Eco-friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy-Sri Lanka?

This was an open question and the response rate was quite low; only 35 tourists responded. Most of the respondents said opening an eco-friendly budget hotel in Kandy - Sri Lanka was a good idea and quite few said it will be a good investment.

5.2. Face-to-face interview analysis

Question 1: What Best describes your type of hotel

Figure 32. Representation of hoteliers interviewed

The researcher's objective here was to capture a reasonable representation of his interviewed respondents. As observed in the above figure 32, 60% of respondents were eco-hoteliere and other categories represented only 10% apiece. Therefore, it can be concluded that the respondent representation was acceptable, so the output data were accurate.

Question 2: What are the eco practices that your hotel follows? (Number of Eco hotels = 6)

Eco-practise	R2	R3	R6	R7	R8	R9	Total
Organic food	Y	-	-	-	-	-	1
Energy Conservation	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	6
Renewable Energy	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Water Conservation	-	Y	-	Y	-	-	2
Land Conservation	-	-	-	-	-	Y	1
Recycling Program	-	-	-	-	Y	-	1
Waste/Toxicity Reduction	-	Y	Y	-	Y	-	3
Community Programs/ Charity	-	-	-	-	Y	Y	2
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	2	3	2	2	4	3	16

Table 08. Eco-practices of the hoteliers

Above table 08. indicates, all eco-hoteliere follow the energy conservation as one of their eco practices and out of 6 hoteliers, 3 of them follow the waste / toxicity reduction. Two stated that they conducted community programs. According to this analysed data, it can be

concluded that the eco hoteliers were not much interested to the other eco-practices even though they are representing eco-hotels. This will be followed up in the Business section below.

Question 3: Rate your target market starting the most important from number 1-6.

Target market	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
Business	4	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	1
Leisure	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
Honeymoon	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4
Backpacker	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	4	3	3
Educators	5	5	-	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Others	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 09. Target market rating of the interviewed hoteliers

According to analysed data, out of 10 hoteliers, 9 rated leisure as 1 and 5 respondents rated 2 on backpackers while 4 hoteliers rated 2 on business customers. (Table 09) Therefore, it can be concluded that the hoteliers key target group is mostly leisure customers followed by backpackers and business tourists and also this point was same in the proposed business then this would be considered when the proposed business competitor strategies are developed.

Question 4: What type of facilities / services do you offer to your customers? Tick each one you offer.

Services / Facilities	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	Total
TV	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	10
Internet	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	09
Locker	-	-	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-	01
Alarm clock	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	10
Gymnasium	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Laundry	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	01
Concierge	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Food & beverage	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	10
Car parking	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	09
Disability accesses	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-	01
Total	05	05	05	04	05	05	07	06	05	04	51

Figure 33. Services & facilities provided by the interviewees

The researcher’s objective here was to identify the general services and facilities that his competitors offer. All hoteliers said that they offered television, alarm clock, food and beverage. Out of 10, 9 said that they offered Internet and car parking as their services. However, other services and facilities were offered by only one respondent. (Figure 33) Therefore, taking this as an opportunity the researcher can focus on the other services as well to be provided in his proposed hotel which would create differentiation with its competitors.

Question 5: Rate the followings in terms of importance to operating a successful hotel business.

Figure 34. Respondents rating about Price, Location, Brand & Service standards in terms of importance to operating a successful hotel business

As shown in figure 34, out of 10 hoteliers, 5 said, price was highly important to operate a successful hotel business while other 5 stated it as just important. In terms of location, 8 respondents said it was important and 2 said it was highly important. In line with high level of service standards, 8 respondents said it was highly important and 2 classified it as important. Moreover, in terms of brand, 7 respondents said it was important and others stated it was neutral. Therefore, according to the hoteliers' judgment, it can be concluded that the price, location, service standards and brand are highly important to run a successful hotel business and these would be followed in further business section.

Question 6: Main theme – Key to customer satisfaction and its importance

The majority of respondents stated, providing valuable services for the customer's money was the key to customer satisfaction. Further, their opinion was mainly that hoteliers should fulfil customer expectations beyond what they had expected. Thus, by providing good customer service, personal care, variety of services, standards, rewards and through good customer relationship, customer expectations can be achieved. Furthermore, customer satisfaction is highly important in order to have repeat customers and to increase the reputation of the business. Consequently this maximises customers' loyalty and business profit.

Question 7: Main theme – Best way to promote hotel businesses in the market

Most of the hoteliers said that the online advertisements and paper / magazine advertisements were the best way to promote a hotel business in the current hospitality market. Most of them stated that they had already implemented media channels including; Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, hotel websites and hospitality magazines. However, some hoteliers stated that they believed that public relations, cause marketing and good word of mouth were the best promotional channels in current hospitality market. Some of these strategies will be considered when the proposed hotel develops marketing mix.

Question 8: Main theme – Sri Lankan current hospitality market and ‘Kandy’ current hospitality market

Almost every respondent stated that the current Sri Lankan hospitality market was booming in line with increasing tourist arrivals. They stated, that the Sri Lankan hospitality market demand was high due to the insufficient number of established accommodation providers. Moreover, the majority of the hoteliers added that the Kandy current hospitality demand was quite high in order to meet the required room supply. Further, they stated that such situations were highly affecting the Kandy hospitality market during peak-season so more lodging facility providers are required. As such, it can be concluded that the proposed business can have a brighter opportunity in Kandy.

Question 9: “The current eco-friendly trends in the hospitality market are leading to responsible tourism” According to you, this statement is

Figure 35. True factor of the statement : “The current eco-friendly trends in the hospitality market are leading to responsible tourism”

The majority that is 80% of respondents found that the idea of current eco-friendly trends in hospitality market that was leading to responsible tourism to be very true. Others stated on this idea as somewhat true. (Figure 35) According to this result, it can be concluded that the majority of hoteliers believe the eco-friendly trends in hospitality market are leading to responsible tourism and therefore, potential eco hotels demand will be increased in line with populating responsible tourism being more popular in the tourist community.

Question 10: Main theme – Tourism seasonality in Sri Lanka

Based on the opinions of hoteliers interviewed, the Sri Lankan tourism peak-season is from December to February and off-peak season is from March to June. Most of them noticed December as the busiest month in Sri Lankan hospitality market. However, in line with Kandy, August is also counted as a busy month according to Kandy hoteliers mainly because of the ‘Esala Pageants’, which is the Sri Lankan top cultural event that is celebrated in August. Furthermore, this result obviously proves that the statement of President - Kandy City Hoteliers Association, Mr. Rodney Armstrong as discussed in the literature review part to be true.

Question 11: Main theme – Strategies that are used during the quiet period

According to respondents' statements, it can be concluded that the majority of hoteliers use promotion / discounts, packages and reduce employee working hours as their strategies to run their business smoothly during the dry period. Further, some of them start marketing activities during this time to promote their business while some of them rotate employees to their other busiest branches. Then, some of these strategies would be considered in business section.

Question 12: Main theme – Average occupancy

After a careful review of the interview feedback, it can be concluded that the hotels' annual average occupancy rate stands between 80% - 85% which shows a bright sign for the proposed business as the researcher expects 63%, 70% and 80% annual occupancy rate within year 1, 2 and 3 respectively. However, this result indicates some difference in Sri Lankan annual occupancy rate which was 74.3% in 2014 as discussed earlier in literature review.

Question 13: Main theme – opinion on the new concept of eco-friendly budget hotel

All interviewees expressed that it was a good idea and would be good investment. Moreover most of them stated that this concept had a good opportunity to be successful in the Sri Lankan hospitality market. However, some of hoteliers agreed that this was a good idea but quite challenging to implement. The main reason that they believed this concept would be successful in Sri Lanka as its eco experience at an economical price. They stated that nowadays customers who visit Sri Lanka were more budget conscious and keen on eco-hotel prices therefore, this business would be successful. As proven earlier in the literature review, Sri Lanka has considerable eco hotels but none of them offer this service for the budget price. Moreover, some of hoteliers also added that nowadays tourist were highly social responsible and therefore, this business would be successful.

Question 14: Rate the level of competition in Kandy hotel market

Factor	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	Total
Very low	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Low	Y	Y	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Y	3
Medium	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	6
High	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Y	-	1
Very high	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10

Figure 36. The level of competition in Kandy hotel market

As shown in the above figure 36, 6 of the hoteliers stated that the level of competition in Kandy was medium while other 3 said that it was rather low. Only one hotelier marked competition in Kandy as high. According to this analysed data, it can be concluded that the competition in Kandy hospitality market is medium / low, which is good for the proposed business as this helps to start-up and run the business smoothly.

Question 15: Main theme – Differentiate between competitors

Majority of hoteliers said that they differentiated by their service, quality and standards from their competitors. This had been achieved by offering excellent customer service and good facilities to their valued customer. At the same time, some of hoteliers classified their hotel location and personal relationship as the key factors that are differentiated them from their competitors. According to the researcher’s analysis it can be concluded that there is not much difference between each hotels that are differentiated them from each other. Therefore taking this opportunity would enable the researcher to implement new factors and use them as competitive advantages.

Question 16: Rate the skilled labour market availability in terms of following hospitality areas in Sri Lanka.

	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High	Total
Housekeeping				R1,R2,R3, R4,R5, R7,R8,R9, R10	R6	10
Duty managers		R2,R3,R5	R1,R4,R6, R7,R8,R9 R10			10
Receptionists			R1,R2,R3, R4,R5,R6, R7,R8,R9, R10			10
Guest relations			R1,R2,R3, R4,R5,R6, R7,R8,R9, R10			10
Chef de cuisine	R3,R8,R9	R1,R4,R5, R6,R7,R10	R2			10
Sous chef	R1,R3,R5, R8,R9,R10	R2,R4,R6, R7				10
Concierge		R2	R1,R3,R4, R5,R6,R7, R8,R9,R10			10
F&B attendants			R1,R3	R2,R4,R5, R6,R7,R8, R9,R10		10
Valet / laundry		R2,R3,R7, R8,R9,R10	R1,R4,R5, R6			10
Finance			R3,R4,R5, R6,R7,R8, R9,R10	R1	R2	10
Marketing			R4,R5,R6, R7,R8,R10	R1,R3, R9	R2	10
HR			R4,R5,R6, R7,R8,R9, R10	R1,R3	R2	10

Table 10. The skilled labour market availability in Sri Lanka

In line with above analysed data (Table 10), it can be concluded that the skill housekeeping labour market and f&b attendants are high in Sri Lankan hospitality context. However, according to the interviewees, skill sous chef and Chef de cuisine availability is very low. Thus, valet / laundry skill availability also can be considered as low. Other all employees' category availability can be concluded as medium which shows bright sign to the Sri Lankan hospitality sector.

Question 17: Rate the raw material availability (Fruits & Vegetable, Linen, Chemical) in terms of quality and standards

Figure 37. The raw material availability in terms of quality & standards

Out of the 10 hoteliers, 8 stated that the quality of fruits and vegetable availability as medium and 2 classified it as high. In line with quality linen availability, 7 hoteliers marked it as low and 3 referred as medium. Moreover, out of 10 hoteliers, 9 stated the quality of chemical availability in Sri Lanka as low and one referred as very low (Figure 37). Therefore, it can be concluded that the quality of fruits and vegetable availability in Sri Lanka is medium and the quality linen and chemical availability is low. The researcher would be focus on these more.

Question 18: Main theme – Operational issues

Most of the hoteliers have named that the staffing, hygiene, food waste and pest control as today’s major operational issues in hospitality market. However, some of them said that energy management, sanitation, stock control, skill shortage, material supply, marketing cost, yield management, organisation development, legal requirements and debt management were the key operational issues in current hospitality market. To overcome these issues, currently they are following strategies such as offering good incentives and maintaining a happy working environment for their employees, following the company procedures and standards to maintain hygiene, sanitation and pest control, daily monitoring in line with energy efficiency, introducing pre-prepared food items and working closely chef and manager together in order to reduce the food waste, and following the stock controlling methods to manage the stock. Thus, they use qualified and experienced employees to manage the debt

and yield. Respondents also said that the skill shortage was one of the issues that they cannot implement any strategy for, as it is beyond their control.

Question 19: Main theme – Pricing strategy

Due to pricing being one of the key business secrets, most of hoteliers refused to share their own pricing strategy. However, some of them answered and they said that they followed cost plus pricing and market penetration pricing strategies which considering current market price and demand. So, some of these strategies will be followed when the proposed hotel pricing is developed. Further, some of them stated that their product price was always increased and decreased because of market fluctuation. Therefore, it is clear that the lodging facilities cannot be sold at a fix price and it’s always changed due to market demand and supply while ensuring business profit.

Question 20: Main theme – Profitability

The researcher’s objective was by this question to realise the current hotel businesses’ profitability and to get an idea about how their business is done. Almost all hoteliers said that they were happy with their profitability. Therefore, it can be concluded that every hotel is doing well and making sufficient profit itself.

Question 21: Rate 1 to 5 in terms of customers spending (1=highest, 5=lowest)

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
Accommodation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Food & Beverage	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Entertainment	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	4
Leisure & adventure	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	3
Other	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	5	-
Total	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4

Table 11. Customer rating of spending in terms of Accommodation, Food & Beverage, Entertainment, Leisure and Other

As shown in table 11, all the hoteliers said the accommodation was the highest spending category of today’s customer and then, the food and beverage. However, some of hoteliers rated entertainment at third place while others rated leisure and adventure as third spending

category. Furthermore, majority of hoteliers did not rate on other spending however, two hoteliers rated other spending as a fifth place which describes transport arrangements that are made by hotels.

Question 22: Main theme - opinion and comments

There were not such an opinion and comment that given by hoteliers. However, generally they have wished to the researcher's studies and to the proposed business. Thus, they said this was a good idea and this would be a good investment.

Question 23: Main theme – hoteliers profile

Since this is an optional question, some of hoteliers did not share their age, occupation, education background and industry experience. However, in line with hoteliers who provided the answers, it can be concluded that the all of them are qualified with hospitality education so they have more than 10 years industry experience. Therefore, it can be guaranteed; the answers which were gathered from interviews are accurate and will be very useful to make right decisions about the proposed hotel business.

(Note: only seven hoteliers were allowed to record the interview process)

5.3. Further Secondary analysis

Further secondary research key findings as follows. The complete analysis is described in appendix 07. (references in appendix 07)

- The Sri Lankan travel and tourism sector's direct contribution to GDP was forecast to increase by 1.3% in 2015 and 6.1% from 2015-2025, which is up to LKR 842.5 billion and this will be a 4.5% of total GDP in 2025.
- Sri Lanka was ranked at 24th place in terms of long-term growth (2015-2025) to the total contribution of travel and tourism to GDP.
- According to Trading Economics global macro models and analysts' expectations, projected tourist arrivals in 2016; Quarter 1-1817843, Quarter 2-1882611, Quarter 3-1947379, Quarter 4-2012147 and in 2020 – 2637789.
- Forecast travel and tourism contribution to the investment is estimated to increase by 8.3% in 2015 and by 5.5% pa over the next 10 years; representing LKR 213.4 billion, that is 3.9% of the total investment.
- Forecast travel and tourism contribution to the employment in 2025 is; 438,000 jobs which is 5.2% of total employment in Sri Lanka.
- The total contribution of Travel & Tourism to employment, including jobs indirectly supported by the industry in 2025 is; 943,000 jobs which is 11.1% of total.
- Visitor exports value - the forecast tourist arrival of 3,314,000 in 2025 is expected to generate LKR 825.5 billion.
- Business travel spending is expected to grow by 4.1% in 2015 to LKR 101.0 billion, and rise by 6.6% pa to LKR 192.0 billion in 2025.
- Leisure travel spending is expected to grow by 1.1% in 2015 to LKR 646.1 billion, and rise by 5.9% pa to LKR 1,145.4 billion in 2025.
- The domestic travel spending is projected to increase by 6.4% in 2015, which is up to LKR 300.6 billion and also expected to grow by 5.5% pa to LKR 511.9 billion in 2025.

Chapter 06 – Business concept

6.1.1. The proposed hotel business concept

The Proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be opened in January of 2018 in Kandy, Sri Lanka. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be surrounded by ‘Hanthana’ mountains where tourists will be able to experience the natural beauty of the mountains and forests. The hotel’s core concept was developed using “Eco” and “Budget” hotel concepts in order to provide an environment-friendly accommodation at a low price. Thus, this idea of the researcher has been validated by the research findings; such as majority of tourists and hoteliers have stated that the opening a new hotel that is combined with both eco and budget hotel concepts together was an excellent idea. Moreover, the eco hotel concept will also help in building a budget hotel as it will reduce the operational costs while it is protecting the environment at the same time. Similarly, the smaller number of facilities that the proposed hotel offers, will help to keep its product cost at minimum and consequently aid in implementing the budget concept, such as selling a room at a low price.

The Hotel will be built using timber and mud that represents traditional rural houses in Sri Lanka and this is a potential customer preference that can be proved through the result of research question 10.6.2. Besides, there will be a cultural event on every weekend that will allow the tourists to experience the cultural music, dance, and food. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will position itself to provide healthy and organic food to its customers by cultivating its own vegetables and fruits in the hotel’s premises. Further, the research findings also indicated that the organic food is highly favoured in nowadays and it is a major choice of today’s eco tourists.

This hotel will follow the budget hotel concept, therefore it will only offer complimentary organic breakfast. There will be a common cooking facilitative area however, where the customers will be able to cook their own food. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will consist of ten units that will accommodate 2-3 guests per unit. The hotel will also provide facilities for interconnecting units in order to the customer's request. There will be also an exterior dining area and playing area for the badminton, tennis and children's activities. The hotel's floor plan drawn in figure 38.

Figure 38. The proposed hotel floor plan

In line with reducing the hotel production cost and with the eco-friendly concept and the research findings; the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will follow the following eco practices.

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel's Eco Practices

- Use of organic linen to the hotel housekeeping and introducing linen reuse programs such as damaged linen for housekeeping rags and kitchen towels.
- Staff training about the green practices and providing necessary information to the guests about green practices.
- Use of Energy Star labelled appliances, equipment and recycled amenities for the hotel operations.
- Designing the hotel's interior by allowing daylight and fresh air exchange.
- Installing energy efficient light bulbs and setting up a renewable energy source -solar power.
- Setting up 2.5-gallons per minute showerheads and 1.6-gallon toilets in all guestrooms.
- Use of non-toxic cleaning agents and laundry detergent hotel's operations.
- Use of non-disposable dishes, containers and cups.
- Following the waste management standards.
- Collecting rainwater and use for the gardening and setting up a grey-water recycling plant that can be reused from kitchen, bath and laundry water for garden and landscaping.

The hotel general manager will be the researcher – Mr. Nilan Samarakoon, who has seven-years' experience in hospitality industry and he is a graduate in Strategic Hospitality Management from the University of Gloucestershire, UK. The proposed hotel will consist of a team of eleven members including two part-time employees and one temporary employee. The temporary employees will be allocated with regard to seasonality requirements. Furthermore, required security officers for the hotel will be outsourced from a reputed company. According to the research findings, staffing is a massive operational issue in today's hospitality context. Therefore, the researcher will use tactics like offering good incentives, employee welfare and create a satisfactory and comfortable working environment.

6.1.2. Business model

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will follow Business Canvas Model as its business model which is expected to achieve the business objectives successfully. The business canvas model is help the business to move beyond product-centric thinking. (Osterwalder, 2013) It describes nine critical components such as value propositions, segments, customer relationship, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, cost structure, and key partners. (White, 2013) The proposed hotel business canvas model is described in figure 39 and further analysis is revealed in appendix 08.

Key Partners Government agencies Industry association Tour operators Suppliers Financial institutes Logistic services Insurance companies	Key Activities Housekeeping Food & beverage Guest relations Marketing Human resource Finance	Value Proposition Hotel core concept (eco-lodging facilities at budget price) Organic food Hotel design & location Cultural exchange Personalised service	Customer Relationship Individual focus – long term	Customers Segments 75% inbound tourists who are interested in experiencing nature & culture with a limited budget. 25% domestic tourists who are interested in experiencing nature & culture with a limited budget.
Cost structure Fixed cost Salary, insurance, marketing, Variable cost	Revenue stream The hotel’s revenue stream is room sales. Thus, it consists of transaction and recurring revenue.			
Key Resources Hotel design & location Financial capability Qualified & experienced Management			Channels Direct sales- 60% (online & at premises) Indirect sales- 40% (via tour operators)	

Figure 39. Business Canvas Model of the proposed hotel

6.1.3. Business Vision, Mission, and Goals

Vision “To be the best Eco-friendly Budget Hotel in Sri Lanka.”
Mission “To provide outstanding eco-friendly lodging facilities at budget price for our customers.”

Business objectives and Goals

The goals of proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel are established using SMART objectives as management is keen to succeed the business. The SMART objective elements include Specific, Measurable, Agreed, Realistic and Time bound. (Richman, 2016, p. 65)

1st year - Primary objectives

- To achieve 63% rooms occupancy by the end of 2018.
- To achieve LKR 11285000 revenue by the end of 2018.
- To achieve LKR 3902242 Net profit by the end of 2018 financial year.

2nd year Primary objectives

- To achieve 70% rooms occupancy by the end of 2019.
- To achieve LKR 13437250 revenue by the end of 2019.
- To achieve LKR 5260519 Net profit by the end of 2019 financial year.

3rd year – Primary objectives

- To achieve 80% rooms occupancy by the end of 2020.
- To achieve LKR 16036250 revenue by the end of 2020.
- To achieve LKR 6593689 Net profit by the end of 2020 financial year.

The business further goals:

- To be the best eco-friendly budget hotel in Sri Lanka by the end of 2025 in relation to customer service, employee satisfaction, profitability and the brand awareness.
- To expand the business brand by opening up new hotels in other provinces 2028.

6.2. Strengths of proposed business model

According to the proposed hotel innovative business concept, it will have a high capability of attracting its target customers. Meanwhile, the business core concept is developed considering the today's hospitality trends. Therefore, the business sales will be maximised. On the other hand, owing to the proposed hotel following the budget concept along with the eco concept, it will cover the niche market of eco-lodging facilities at a low price where the current hospitality market gap exists.

Combination of eco and the budget concept has many advantages that towards proposed business to its goals. For example, eco practices like waste management, energy management and recycling will automatically reduce the hotel's operational costs such as electricity and food costs. This is a convenience to have the budget hotel concept as the hotel production cost is low. Moreover, the budget hotel has a higher potential to recover or maintain its operations well, even in an economy crisis, for its operational cost and product cost is low. Because of the low production cost, the hotel will be able to sell its product at a low price where customers will pursue to purchase products even though the economy is not

functioning well. Likewise, this has been proven by Indian budget hotel sector and UK budget hotel sector during the past few years which was already discussed in literature review.

The proposed hotel design; environment; use of organic food and cultural events that will be conducted every weekend, will be also implemented to attract customers and those differentiate it from its competitors. Moreover, personalised service will be another strength that the proposed business will provide to build a good customer relationship and retain loyalty.

In line with hotel target segment and its representation such as highly targeting inbound tourists, the business will have bright future as international tourism which is booming in Sri Lanka. By targeting approximately 25% of local tourists, this will also help to run the business smoothly in terms of inbound tourism off-seasons.

By introducing recurring revenue stream, the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be able to increase customer loyalty, potential sales and revenue. Thus, 60% of the business transaction revenue is expected to help the business to cover its day-to-day operations and to run smoothly until recurring revenue flow into the business cash flow.

Moreover, by introducing a distribution method such as 60% direct and 40% indirect sales, there will be another strength of the proposed business. For example, 40% of indirect sales are more often purchased earlier by tour operators where management is not exposed to any risk. These types of dealings are often made at low price due to commissions where some of the profits go to tour operators. To the other 60% direct sales, management can make their decision regarding the price of products and selling them at a good price. However, in this case selling a product is not guaranteed; so, by implementing both direct and indirect sales, the proposed hotel can be run smoothly to achieve its goals.

6.3. The benefit of the business to customers and stakeholders

Benefits to customers

The main advantage of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel to its customers is an eco-friendly experience that will be provided at a budget price. Thus, at the same time the hotel will be able to exchange local culture with its customers, and this will be another benefit that the proposed hotel customer will have. Along with management experience and employing skilled staff, the proposed hotel will be able to provide standard services to its customers. Nevertheless, the personalised assistance and individual caring also will be another benefit that Eco-Friendly Hotel customers will gain when they are accommodated in the proposed hotel. On the other hand, customers will be able to have organic food that is a priceless benefit that the proposed hotel's customers will get compared to today's negative health habits. Easy accessibility, airport pick-up arrangements, concierge services and travel guides will be additional valuable benefits that Eco-Friendly Hotel will provide to its customers which are expected to increase the business value proposition.

Benefits to Stakeholders

In line with hotel concept and healthy value proposition, the hotel will be able to attract more customers and that will consequently generate higher revenue to the business. Thus, healthy value proposition will create loyal customers and automatically increase the hotel's profit. When a business has higher level profit, stakeholders can re-invest the profit in their businesses and expand the business for future growth.

Furthermore, the hotel eco-practice methods and hotel's budget concept will help to reduce the business operation cost. Therefore, business profit will be maximised which will be another benefit that stakeholders will be receiving. Moreover, as the proposed hotel concept was developed in line with government values such as responsible tourism, the business start-up and operating will be much easier for its stakeholders in order to support the current government.

As the proposed hotel's business concept is matched with today's customer requirements, and as it covers a gap in hospitality market Sri Lanka, the future of the proposed business will be secured. Therefore, stakeholders' investment will also be secured because the business will have a high potential to develop. Apart from this, the proposed hotel's ongoing

capturing values will be maximised and therefore hotel's stability, brand awareness and profit will be high where the stakeholders will be benefited. Thus, these values captured include higher retention, the share of customer such as percentage of an individual customer's purchase of a product that is a single brand, and customer equity, which is the total combined customer lifetime values of all of the hotel's customers.

6.4. Industry and environment analysis

6.4.1 STEPE Analysis

Social-Cultural

Today's customer lifestyle and customer preferences are changing rapidly. However, it is going to have a positive effect on the proposed hotel. For instance, customer preference of responsible tourism, organic food, and cultural focus will help to increase the proposed hotel sales. Thus, the primary and secondary research findings were also cited that today's tourists are highly social responsible and interested in the organic food when they are choosing an eco-lodging facilities. Nevertheless, a lifestyle like taking holidays will positively affect the proposed business and thus, the research findings illustrated that nowadays the tourists at least take 1 or 2 holidays per year. In another hand, Sri Lankan culture is reputed as one of most hospitable culture with a warm smile. Therefore, Sri Lankan culture will be a support to the proposed business, as it will help to attract more customers. These discussed factors prove that the social and cultural environment is favourable for the proposed hotel.

Technological

The hospitality industry is highly influenced by new technologies. For an example, online distribution channels, property management systems (PMS), food and beverage equipment, and so on. Furthermore, research findings indicate that the online presence is the best distribution and marketing channel for proposed business which proves how the new technology is positively affected to the proposed business. Interviewed hoteliers stated that the new technology such as energy star labelled appliances, solar power units and CFL bulbs reduced their operational costs. Therefore, it can be concluded that new technology will help hospitality businesses to increase their sales and efficiency while it is increasing business profit.

Economic

As shown in the literature review, Sri Lankan economy was rising after the post-war ended in 2009. “Economic growth in Sri Lanka has been among the fastest in South Asia in recent years. Growth averaged 6.3 percent between 2002 and 2013, with Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita rising from US\$859 in 2000 to US\$3,256 in 2013.” (The World Bank, 2015) Thus, its economy has grown by 4.4% in the first quarter of 2015 and 6.7% in the second quarter (Sri Lanka: Economy, 2015). Moreover, further secondary research findings stated; in year 2014, the total contribution of travel and tourism sector to GDP was LKR 1,067.4 billion which was 11.1% of total GDP and it is projected to rise by 2.5% in 2015. Further, it is forecast to rise by 6.1% pa to LKR 1,979.2 billion in 2025 which will represent 10.5% of total GDP in Sri Lanka. Besides, Sri Lanka was recognised as Lower Income country till 2014 and recently it was categorised as Lower Middle-Income Country. (Doing Business 2015, 2014) In line with all these facts above, it can be concluded, that the Sri Lankan economy is favourable for the proposed business. Since the proposed business will significantly target inbound tourists, the global economy situation may also affect its operations. However, as the proposed hotel is a budget hotel, the negative effect of the global crisis will be minimised.

Political

As discussed in literature review, Sri Lankan government vision towards to increase 2.5 million tourist arrivals by 2016 and therefore, the government has introduced new policies and frameworks that are expected to support small and medium enterprises in the tourism industry. For an example, simple and low tax regime, simple licensing procedures, loans, concession rates on high electricity tariffs, streamlining the process of isolating government land for tourism development projects and so on. However, recently Mr. Mahinda Rajapakse's government has changed, and the new president, Mr. Maithreepala Sirisena's government is showing higher political stability along with their vision and progress in last few months. Further, the new government's foreign policy will increase international relationship and consequently, it will be favourable for the tourism industry in Sri Lanka. (Philips, 2015) Therefore, it can be concluded that the political environment in Sri Lanka is highly favourable to the proposed hotel.

Environmental

Sri Lankan natural environment is favourable for the tourism industry as it consists of many natural resources such as beaches, waterfalls, rivers, lakes, mountains, forests, wildlife and so on. Thus, there are no natural disasters like earthquakes and storms compared to other tourism destinations.

6.4.2. Porter's Five Forces analysis

Figure 40. Porter's Five Forces analysis

Threat of new entry

The threat of new entry will be low in the hotel industry as it requires higher investment for start-up. Moreover, legal requirements and licensing procedure also contain many complication formalities in hospitality-related businesses in Sri Lanka compared to other businesses. The interviewed hoteliers also have mentioned that the legal requirements and its procedures were today's one of major operational issue in current hospitality management. Considering all these facts, it can be concluded that the threat of new entry is will be low for the proposed hotel business. However, since hospitality is booming in Sri Lanka, some star hotels are expected to be opened. (Wijedasa, 2014) Thus, these hotels will not be a threat for the proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel as it has product differentiation such as eco-cultural experience at an economical price.

Bargaining power of the suppliers

According to the research findings, the availability of quality fruits and vegetable suppliers in Sri Lanka is medium and quality linen and chemical supplier availability are low. Therefore, it can be concluded that the suppliers bargaining power is high. Existing hotels will also increase the bargaining power of suppliers as it creates higher demand for raw materials. However, the proposed hotel's strategies like cultivating its vegetable, fruits, and importing the required raw materials may reduce the threat of suppliers bargaining power.

Bargaining power of the customers

As discussed in the literature review, the estimated required new hotel rooms will be approximately 16,575 to bridge the gap between supply and demand with expected tourist arrivals in 2016. Since the demand of rooms is high, the customer bargaining power will be low and according to the proposed hotel's product differentiation and low price, customer bargaining power will remain low.

Substitutes

Substitutes will be low as there are few options that inbound tourist can get in terms of their accommodation such as renting a caravan or staying with some friends or relatives. Even though, for locals it will be same in terms of accommodation substitutes.

Competitive rivalry

In line with interviewed hoteliers, six stated that the level of competition in Kandy is medium while other 3 were saying it is rather low. Only one hotelier has classified competition in Kandy to be high. Further, literature review elaborated that the available Graded and Supplementary hotel rooms in 2014, Sri Lanka were 28,426. (Annual Statistical Report, 2014, p. 41) Considering all these, it can be concluded that the competitive rivalry for the proposed business will be medium and to overcome this rivalry, the proposed hotel will introduce its products with differentiation and for a budget price.

6.4.3. SWOT analysis

Figure 41. SWOT analysis

According to the SWOT analysis (figure 41), the researcher has developed further strategies for the proposed business which in line with TOWS Strategic Matrix Analysis and outlined in figure 42.

6.4.4. TOWS Strategic Matrix Analysis

	External opportunities (O) Increase sales and market share. Experts' advice and training. To make required raw materials or import them.	External threats (T) Competition Security Global crisis Substitutes
Internal strengths (S) Hotel core concept Hotel design Location Organic good Skilled and qualified management Finance capabilities Personalised service	SO For management experience and the proposed business financial capabilities, it could be integrated an excellent marketing strategy to increase the hotel sales. Thus, hotel's core concept, location, and design can be used as its promotion functions. The experts' advice and training could be outsourced in line with hotel strong financial capabilities.	ST The hotel can use its core concept, design, location and personalised service as its competitive advantage. Since the hotel follows budget hotel concept, it has a higher capability to survive in the recession times. Thus, hotel financial strength also will be an extra advantage during the crisis period. In terms of security, the hotel can outsource from reputed security officers by using the financial strength the hotel.
Internal weaknesses (W) Skilled and experienced staff Quality raw materials	WO In terms of unskilled staff, the hotel can outsource training programs from experts. The hotel can make its required raw materials like vegetable and fruits or can import its required goods like chemical, linen, and amenities.	WT Overcoming weaknesses by making them as strengths. Increasing strengths capacities to face threats.

Figure 42. TOWS Strategic Matrix Analysis

6.4.5. Competitive analysis

Comparative factor	The proposed hotel (Strengths & Weaknesses) Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel	Competitor - 1 (Strengths & Weaknesses) Madulkelle Eco & Tea Lodge	Competitor – 2 (Strengths & Weaknesses) Gadadessa Resort	Competitor – 3 (Strengths & Weaknesses) Polwathta Eco Lodge
Location	3 km from the city (S) Rich Green environment with mountains (S)	32 km from the city (W) Surrounding to mountains and tea plantation (S)	16.1 km from the city (W) Surrounding to mountains (S)	18 km from the city (W) Situated in rural village (S)
Concept	Innovative – combination of budget and eco concepts among the local cultural experience (S)	Only eco concept (W)	Only eco concept (W)	Only eco concept (W)
Architectural design	Build using mud & timber (S)	Not specific – cement building (W)	Build using timber (S)	Build using timber (S)
Products and services	One product – which can be accommodate 2 / 3 people (W) Services- (Less) Airport pickup, bed and breakfast, and concierge (W)	One product – which can be accommodate three people (W) Services- (More) Swimming pool, bar, Spa, Wellness Center, Business Center, full board (S)	Four products – Basecamp, Octagon House, Treehouse, Campsite (S) Services- (More) Ayurvedic treatments, adventure programs, and full board (S)	Three lodge – Superior, Dormitory, Mud houses (S) Services- (More) River bath, adventure programs, and full board (S)

Eco- practices	More – practices (S) 100% organic food and harvest, organic amenities, waste management, water recycling, solar power, charity programs & information, and eco-friendly design	Less – practices (W) 60% vegetable and herbs - harvest by its own and some social responsible programs for its employees	Less – practices (W) Waste management, solar power and wind power.	Less – practices (W) Social- responsible programs for its employees
Quality and standards	Will be high (S)	High (S)	High (S)	Low (W)
Customer service	Self and Personalised service combination (S)	General (S)	Personalised (S)	General (W)
Price	Will be low (S)	High (W)	High (W)	Medium (W)
Financial capabilities	High (S)	High (S)	High (S)	Low (W)
Skilled employees	May low – in line with unskilled labor market (W)	Medium (S)	Medium (S)	Low (W)
Years of existence	Not yet (W)	More than five years (S)	Less than five years (S)	More than five years (S)
Advertising	Online, paper, events and magazine (S)	Online, paper, magazines, events, radio (S)	Online, magazines, events, paper, radio (S)	Online (W)

Table 12. Competitive analysis (Polwathta Eco Lodge, n.d.) (Madulkelle , n.d.) (Gadadessa Resort , n.d.)

6.5. Competitive advantage

According to the industry analysis, the main competitive advantage of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be its core concept of nature-friendly experience for a budgeted price. Thus, the proposed hotel location is much near to Kandy city center compared to its other competitors. Therefore, it will be a potential competitive advantage to the proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel. Nevertheless, the hotel's nature-friendly atmosphere and its architectural design will be another competitive advantages as they will be a help to attract more customers.

Moreover, the proposed hotel will follow a high number of eco-practices compared to its competitors. This will be a further competitive advantage in terms of attracting more eco-friendly customers, and consequently it helps to minimise the operation cost. Apart from that, personalised service, organic food, cultural exchange and financial capabilities will be the other competitive advantages of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel.

Chapter 07 - Marketing plan

7.1 Marketing Objectives

Once a business has established its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats available through the marketing audit, the business will be able to redefine its marketing objectives and how these will fit with the overall business objectives. The primary and secondary research that was carried out by the researcher will also help to develop good quality marketing objectives for the proposed business. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel marketing objectives were developed using SMART criteria and the key marketing objectives for the business are as follows.

1st year - Marketing objectives

- **To increase the hotel occupancy up to 63% by the end of 2018 financial year.**
The occupancy was forecast considering the findings from the research such as annual average occupancy rate in Sri Lanka and average annual occupancy rate in Kandy hotels and also by considering the novelty of the business.
- **To increase the number of inquiries from proposed hotel marketing communications activities by 20% by the end of 2018.** (This is compared to inquiries that are received from the pre-launch)
To achieve this objective, the proposed business will follow strategies that are in line with research findings; which include online presence, positioning, cause marketing and partner up.
- **To increase the brand awareness by 20% by the end of 2018.** (This is compared to brand awareness which existed in the business pre-launch time)
This objective was developed according to the research findings such as rating based on the importance of brand awareness and thus, importance of word of mouth, reputation and public relations.

2nd year - Marketing objectives

- **To increase hotel room sales (occupancy) up to 70% by the end of 2019 financial year.**
- **To enhance customer relationship by 30% at the end of 2019.**
This objective was developed according to the research findings; importance of customer relationship.
- **Grow market share by 10% in Kandy hospitality market by the end of 2019.**
According to the research findings; Kandy hospitality market has a higher availability to grow-up and considering that, this objective was developed.
- **To increase by 30% the number of inquiries from proposed hotel marketing communications activities by the end of 2019.**
- **Increase cause marketing by 50% at the end of 2019.**
This objective was developed in line with hoteliers' opinion that leads to increase public relations.
- **To increase the brand awareness by 40% at the end of 2019.**
- **To reduce marketing cost by 10% at the end of 2019.** (That compared to the total marketing cost of pre-launch and post-launch)
The research findings indicate that the marketing cost is one of operational issues in today's hospitality market and therefore, the researcher has developed this marketing objective expecting to reduce operational issues.

3rd year - Marketing objectives

- **Target new customers by the end of 2020.**
According to research findings; tourists' arrivals in Sri Lanka are rapidly growing and in line with that this objective was developed.
- **Launch new services by end of 2020.**
Research findings illustrated that the customers are willing to have more services and thus, hoteliers were offered a variety of services to create differences. Considering these facts, researcher has developed this marketing objective to fulfil the customer needs and to maximize the differentiation with his competitors.
- **To increase share of customers by 20% at end of the 2020.**

7.2. Marketing strategies

The marketing role involves activities including managing a customer driven marketing strategy and the marketing mix. (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 70). The customer driven marketing strategies will help the business to reach its marketing objectives in a systematic way. The proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will follow a customer driven marketing strategy that was developed evaluating hotel segmentation, differentiation, positioning and targeting. Further, business key marketing strategies as follows.

7.2.1. Relationship marketing strategy

Figure 43. Relationship marketing orientation
(Christopher, Payne, & Ballantyne, 2009)

Relationship marketing (Figure 43) can be defined as a strategy to “focus on building a relationship with customers instead of always exclusively trying to sell them something.” (52 Types of Marketing Strategies , 2014) Thus, if the customers are happy with business products, they will spend more money on that specific business or brand. Therefore, the proposed business will integrate relationship marketing as its marketing strategy by introducing loyalty programs, offering quality products, personalised service and by maintaining a long term relationship with its customers. Moreover, this strategy and tactics also were developed in line with the research findings; such as most of hoteliers have mentioned the importance of customer relationship to run successful business and thus, loyalty programs, quality services and personalised service will help to maintain good customer relationships.

7.2.2. Positioning

According to the research findings, positioning is one of the best ways to market hotel products without spending money to create a brand, image or position in the marketplace. This can happen through pricing a product on the high end to create an air of quality, or pricing it on the low end to make it seem like good value. The proposed hotel will sell its products at low cost to create its customer value and positioning.

7.2.3. Online presence

In line with increasing number of online users, it is a necessary factor that today's businesses utilize social networks, blogs and websites to promote their business. Therefore, the proposed business will improve an online presence that expects to attract more customers while providing required information to its current and potential customers. Further, this strategy's efficiency has been proved by research findings such as most of the tourists have stated that they find hotels via social media. The interviewed hoteliers also stated that their online presence is the best way to reach their target customers.

7.2.4. Cause Marketing

Cause marketing such as sponsoring a charity is one of a good way to develop brand loyalty. (Edmunds, n.d.) If today's businesses do not stand for a cause, it may be a reason to turn its customers to competitors. "The number of consumers who say they would switch from one brand to another if the other brand was associated with a good cause has climbed to 87 percent, a dramatic increase in recent years, according to a Cone Cause Evolution Survey." (Gordon, n.d.) Moreover, the research findings stated that some hoteliers follow cause marketing as their marketing strategy. Considering all these facts, the proposed hotel will follow cause marketing as its marketing strategy to reach its marketing objectives and as well as its business objectives. For example, the proposed business will sponsor children's education in the local community.

7.2.5. Partner up

According to interviewed hoteliers, partner up with hospitality related businesses and organizations is one of the best strategies that will help to achieve the hotel's marketing objectives. Therefore, the proposed business will increase the effectiveness of marketing dollars by partnering with other businesses who target the same consumers. (Ray, n.d.) For example, partnering with local tourist attractions, Sri Lankan Tourism Board and Sri Lankan Hotel Association will help to achieve the proposed business marketing objectives as it helps to increase and find the target customers. Thus, it will also help to conduct cost effective marketing campaign for partners to bear the cost.

7.3. The target market of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel

The proposed hotel target market will be analysed using market segmentation. Market segmentation helps to answer the key marketing question; which customers will the business serve. “Buyers in any market differ in their wants, resources, locations, buying attitude and buying practices. Through market segmentation companies divide large, heterogeneous market into small segments that can be reached more efficiently and effectively with product and service that match their unique needs.” (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013) The researcher has to try different segmentation, alone and in combination, to find his proposed business target market.

Geographic	Demographic
<p style="text-align: center;">Inbound tourists India, UK, China, Germany, France, Maldives, Russia, Australia, USA and Japan.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Domestic tourist Representing all province of Sri Lanka.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Low income tourist Represent all ages Represent all genders Represent all occupations</p>
Psychographic	Behavioural
<p style="text-align: center;">Personal characteristics: Environment friendly people and people who like to experience the culture.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Regular occasion – leisure tourist Benefit sought – quality, budget price, self & personalised service combination.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Loyalty Attitude towards product</p>

Figure 44. Market Segmentation

The proposed hotel target market is a combination of relevant characteristics from the four segments as shown in figure 44. The proposed hotel key target audience stands in these demographic and psychographic segments shown so that the hotel can target lower income tourist who have personal characteristics of nature and cultural friendly. Moreover, in line with research findings, the proposed hotel will target inbound tourists who are mainly from ten countries including India, UK, China, Germany, France, Maldives, Russia, Australia,

USA and Japan that are aiming to cover its 75% of target customers. Thus, the other 25% will represent the local tourists, covering all provinces of Sri Lanka. The geographic segment was also assessed in the research. The researcher will pay special attention to tourists who are looking for quality services for budget price. It also epitomises the behavioural segment in line with geographic, demographic and psychographic segments. In line with the analysed market segmentation, the proposed hotel target customers are described in figure 45.

<p style="text-align: center;">Inbound tourist : 75% <i>(Visited & New)</i></p> <p>From: India, UK, China, Germany, France, Maldives, Russia, Australia, USA and Japan</p>	<p>Tourist who has characteristics of environment and cultural friendly.</p> <p>Tourist who has limited budget.</p> <p>Tourist who is looking for leisure tourism.</p> <p>Tourist who is interested in benefits sought.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Domestic tourist : 25%</p> <p>From: Representing all nine provinces of Sri Lanka</p>	<p>Tourist who has characteristics of environment and cultural friendly.</p> <p>Tourist who has limited budget.</p> <p>Tourist who is looking for leisure tourism.</p> <p>Tourist who is interested in benefits sought.</p>

Figure 45. The hotel's target customers

As was shown in the research findings, Sri Lanka shows significant growth in both international tourist arrivals and domestic tourism. Further, it was indicated that today's customer preferences are leading to green hotel and budget hotel. Considering these, it can be concluded that the proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be able to reach its target audience without any problems as it is in today's trend and in line with tourism growth in Sri Lanka.

7.4. Needs, wants, preferences and characteristics of target market segments

7.4.1. Needs and wants

The most basic concept underlying marketing, is human needs. “The human needs are states of felt deprivation.” (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 6). These include food, clothes, safety, affection and self-expression. In line with the proposed hotel target customers, their basic need will be accommodation, food and beverage as these are the basic requirements of lodging facilities.

The wants can be defined as “The form human needs take as they are shaped by culture and individual personality.” (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 6) Therefore, the proposed hotel customers’ wants will be to have accommodation in an eco-friendly manner or providing accommodation that allows tourist to experience the local culture. In terms of food and beverage, the customer’s wants will be organic food, seafood, vegetarian or ethnic foods. Therefore, the proposed hotel will introduce green practices, cultural exchange and organic food in order to satisfy customer wants while providing their basic needs.

7.4.2. Preferences

“Marketers must take into account that no two customers are the same.” (Flamberg, 2014) The customer preference can vary even if the customers stand in same market segmentation. However, since the proposed hotel target customers are tourists who are interested in experiencing the nature and culture with a limited budget, their key preferences will include green practices, hotel nature friendly atmosphere, location, budget price, organic food, quality services and security. Thus, these preferences also were proved by the research findings. Moreover, Mr. Robert Bradford – president and CEO of CSSP Inc. has identified that most people will choose a hotel considering its price, atmosphere, service, type of lodging, habit and convenience of the location. (Bradford, n.d.)

7.4.3. Characteristics

Marketing a product or service in a business is not an easy task. But, through understanding customer characteristics, marketers can shape their marketing strategies to overcome their target customer's needs and wants. (Bradley, n.d.) Since the Eco-Friendly Budget hotel will target nature friendly leisure tourists with budget price, their characteristics will be as follows; this reinforced by the research findings.

- They are most likely to be socially responsible.
- They like to relax in natural environment.
- They are more likely to eat healthy food.
- They would like to stay outside rather than staying in the hotel room.
- Leisure tourists like to experience adventure activities.
- They are more likely to use public transport.
- They are more likely to be engaged with local culture.
- They are happy with limited facilities.

7.5. Appraising and quantifying customer numbers and projected revenues

The proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel’s expected unit sale price is LKR 4500.00. This price is a minimum assumption price per unit without considering the seasonality and thus, at 100% occupancy. However, selling a unit at LKR 4500 such as per fixed price is not ethical and realistic in the hospitality industry due to occupancy changes and seasonality, which should reflect its unit price. Therefore, the researcher will calculate average monthly hotel room occupancy and its projected unit selling price by taking into consideration research findings such as 2014 Seasonal Tourist Traffic and Average Monthly Occupancy Rate in Sri Lanka. (Appendix 09 & 10). Thus, the first year calculation will also consider the proposed business as a new venture to Sri Lankan hospitality market. Nevertheless, since the proposed business will locate in Kandy, the special seasonality like “Kandy Perahara” has also been considered in deciding and quantifying the number of customers and thus in projecting the revenue of the business. The proposed hotel’s projected unit sales are quantified in Table 13, 14 and 15 and its projected revenues outlined in table 16, 17 and 18.

Table 13. Projected unit sales – 2018

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Au	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Days per month	31	28	31	30	31	30	31	31	30	31	30	31
Average Occupancy	55%	57%	60%	56%	50%	56%	65%	75%	62%	65%	64%	85%
Projected unit sales	171	160	186	168	155	168	202	233	186	202	192	264

Table 14. Projected unit sales – 2019

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Au	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Days per month	31	28	31	30	31	30	31	31	30	31	30	31
Average Occupancy	81%	75%	70%	60%	55%	58%	68%	87%	64%	66%	67%	90%
Projected unit sales	251	210	217	180	171	174	211	270	192	205	201	279

Table 15. Projected unit sales – 2020

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Au	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Days per month	31	28	31	30	31	30	31	31	30	31	30	31
Average Occupancy	95%	92%	80%	70%	65%	68%	75%	96%	70%	75%	76%	98%
Projected unit sales	295	258	248	210	202	204	233	298	210	233	228	304

Table 16. Projected revenues – 2018

Month	Projected unit selling price (considering seasonality & occupancy)	Sales revenue
Jan	5500	940500
Feb	5500	880000
Mar	4500	837000
Apr	4000	672000
May	3500	542500
Jun	3500	588000
Jul	4000	808000
Aug	6000	1398000
Sep	4500	837000
Oct	5000	1010000
Nov	5500	1056000
Dec	6500	1716000
Total		11285000

Table 17. Projected revenues – 2019

Month	Projected unit selling price (considering seasonality & occupancy)	Sales revenue
Jan	6000	1506000
Feb	5750	1207500
Mar	5000	1085000
Apr	4250	765000
May	3750	641250
Jun	3750	652500
Jul	4500	949500
Aug	6500	1755000
Sep	4750	912000
Oct	5000	1025000
Nov	5250	1055250
Dec	6750	1883250
Total		13437250

Table 18. Projected revenues – 2020

Month	Projected unit selling price (considering seasonality & occupancy)	Sales revenue
Jan	6250	1843750
Feb	6000	1548000
Mar	5250	1302000
Apr	4500	945000
May	4000	808000
Jun	4000	816000
Jul	4750	1106750
Aug	6750	2011500
Sep	5000	1050000
Oct	5250	1223250
Nov	5500	1254000
Dec	7000	2128000
Total		16036250

When the researcher has calculated the 2nd year and 3rd year revenues, the room prices were subject to changed. The main reasons are that the researcher has considered the expected business growth, positioning, occupancy changes and projected inflation rate in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the forecast guest arrivals and revenues are highly accurate and more realistic.

7.6. Marketing mix

“According to Philip Kotler, the marketing mix in the form of ‘Four P’s’ explains the seller’s view of the market but not the buyer’s view. In the modern times, when we accept the modern concept of marketing, the marketing mix can also be explained in the form of ‘Four C’s’ from the customer’s point of view”. (Jain, 2010). Four C’s can be described as customer solution, customer cost, convenience and communication. Therefore, it is important to create consumer driven marketing mix as it is the key way to succeed in today’s business world. Moreover, a marketing mix will help the business to maximise its chances of achieving steady and continual success in its operations by answering marketing questions like; what to offer, at what price to offer, where to offer and how to promote. Considering all these factors, the researcher has formulated an effective marketing mix for the proposed hotel as described in figure 46.

Product / Service	Price
<p>Core product: Accommodation</p> <p>Actual products: Timber & mud rooms, Organic foods, personalized service, Green & cultural experience</p> <p>Augmented products: Rewards, Packages, Discounts, Transport arrangements</p>	<p>Market penetration pricing</p> <p>60% - transaction revenue 40% - recurring revenue</p>
Place	Promotion
<p>Direct - 60% Online and at hotel premises</p> <p>Indirect – 40% Travel agents & tour operators (Selective distribution strategy)</p>	<p>Websites & social media</p> <p>Cause marketing</p> <p>Public relations</p>

Figure 46. The proposed hotel’s Marketing Mix

7.6.1. Product

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will provide high quality services while offering some products. According to Kotler, “Services are products too. They vary in their level of delivery from personal-based to equipment-based delivery.” (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, 2013, p. 277) The proposed hotel’s main product is lodging facilities; which allow customers to experience the nature and culture at a budgeted price. The hotel sub products include organic food, personalised service, concierge services and transport arrangements which are being introduced considering the researcher’s business concept and research findings. Further, due to the proposed hotel core product, it will be differentiated from its competitors. Figure 47. describes the position of the Eco Friendly Budget Hotel product-service / equipment-people continuum.

Figure 47. The hotel’s product-service / equipment-people continuum.

As the proposed hotel belongs to service industry, the business will reflect the services’ characteristics of intangibility, variability, inseparability and perishability. The perishability of services is the most negative fact that will affect the proposed hotel as services cannot be stored for future use. For example, if the hotel room was not accommodated in a particular day, it is a loss to the business forever, as that day cannot be replaced again. If it is a physical product, the business could store it and sell it later.

Layers of products

Kotler states that there are three layers of product which include core product, actual product and augmented product. The core product answers the question of what the customer is really buying. The actual product can be designed around the core product which has characteristics of quality level, features, styling, brand and packaging. The augmented products can be defined as additional benefits and services that can be offered around the core and actual products. (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 277) Further, the proposed hotel's three layers of products are outline in figure 48.

Figure 48. The hotel's layers of products

7.6.2. Price

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel pricing model has been designed considering the customer perceptions of values, product cost and other internal and external factors such as marketing strategies, objectives, competitors' strategies found from the research, and the nature of the market. The proposed hotel pricing model is outlined in figure 49. This model will help the business to keep their product prices in an appropriate position that is in line with the customer value and product cost. Thus, there is no demand above the customer perception on value and no profit below the product cost.

Figure 49. The hotel's pricing model (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 364)

Moreover, along with mentioned pricing model; the proposed hotel will implement market penetration pricing strategy in order to achieve its business objectives. "Market penetration pricing is a pricing strategy of charging very low initial prices to create a new market or grab market share in an established market." (Hirschey, 2009, p. 565) The key reasons of following market penetration pricing as follows;

- Delivering of an innovative product; Kotler stated that the market penetration pricing is more appropriate for innovative products. (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 371)
- Setting a low price will lead to increase large number of guests, and market share within a short time.
- A large number of sales and market share will lead to discourage the competitors.

As discussed in earlier chapters, the proposed hotel pricing model will consist of 60% of transaction revenue and 40% of recurring revenue. The transaction revenue will help the business to cover its day-to-day operation cost and run the business smoothly until recurring revenue flows to business finance. The main reason of introducing recurring revenue is that it helps to maximise the business sales. However, in that case, the proposed business profit margin will be low in order to credit sales purchase by tour operators. Because, the tour operators generally purchase products at a bulk price or they take their commissions. However, the hotel's direct sales (transaction revenue) will help business to balance its finance while increasing its profit as they can make direct sales at a good price.

7.6.3. Place

The main aim of the proposed hotel distribution strategy is that it distributes its products to right customer at the right place, at the right time. The efficient and effective distribution strategy leads business to achieve its overall marketing objectives. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel distribution strategy is described in figure 50. The proposed hotel distribution strategy and channels were created based on research findings and business marketing objectives such as considering the market size, customer preference, experts’ opinion, production quantity, promotion strategies, and pricing model.

1. Online	Through hotel website (www.eco-budgethotel.lk)
2. At premises	‘Hanthana, Kandy’ - Sri Lanka
3. Tour operators	Through “Walkers tours” and “Aitken Spence” Tours

Figure 50. The hotel distribution model

Further, the hotel distribution strategy will act in accordance with selective distribution method. The selective distribution can be defined as “where a firm uses more than one outlet but restricts availability of the product or service to a limited number of outlets.” (Reid & Bojanic, 2010, p. 320). This will help business to maintain its values and brand image while increasing its profit.

As discussed earlier, the proposed hotel’s direct sales will represent 60% of its total sales and thus, it is the best method to follow as it reserves a higher profit margin per unit that is in comparison to indirect sales through tour operators. However, indirect sales has advantages like maximising the business sales through its value adding resales in respect to tour operators’ marketing strengths. Considering all these facts, the proposed hotel will use direct and indirect distributions as both will aid to accomplish the marketing objectives.

7.6.4. Promotion

The promotion is an activity that business communicates and encourages its target customer to purchase its product or service. (Kotler, Burton, Deans, Brown, & Armstrong, Marketing, 2013, p. 74) The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel communication plan's main purpose is to inform its values to its target audience and inspire them to purchase hotel products. The proposed hotel communication plan is presented in Figure 51. and it was developed in line with market research key findings. Moreover, since the business significantly targeting tourists who have already visited Sri Lanka, the researcher will try to find their contact details and then integrate with the business communication plan.

Figure 51. Communication plan of the proposed hotel

Identify the target customers

The proposed hotel target customers include domestic and international tourists from UK, India, Germany, France, USA, Russia, China, Maldives, Australia and Japan.

Determine the objectives

The proposed hotel communication objectives are summarised in table 19. The proposed hotel communication aim is not just selling products. It leads to increase business awareness, knowledge, Liking, preference, conviction and purchase.

Awareness	The communication plan will provide essential information to its customers such as product types, values and benefits expecting an upturn in business awareness.
Knowledge	Rather than just introducing business products, the hotel will communicate its experience, services and social benefits to support customers to make their decision.
Liking	If the consumers strongly dislike a particular product or service, the researcher will create a communication strategy that will make the customer feeling more favourable to purchase that particular product. Thus, the liking can be measured by market research.
Preference	The consumer may like the products, but may not prefer it. Therefore, the hotel communication objectives will highly focus on increasing its customer preferences. This will be measured comparing business past consumer preferences and current consumer preferences.
Conviction	The communication plan will create a strong feeling about the hotel products that lead customers to purchase its products rather than just a preference.
Purchase	Some customers may buy the hotel products and some may not. At this point the researcher will introduce promotions, discounts and packages that pursue the customers to the purchase the product.

Table 19. Communication objectives

Design a message

The proposed hotel will design its communication message considering three elements such as message content, structure and its format.

- **Message content**

The proposed hotel core message content signifies by three appeals that expect to attract high volume of target audience. The core message content of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel is shown in figure 52.

Rational appeals	Increase self-interest of consumers by communicating hotel values and benefits.
Emotional appeals	Create positive emotions - through sharing nature and cultural friendly experience.
Moral appeals	Increasing the consumer's sense of right to purchase; such as hotel products are socially responsible and therefore, the consumer will feel it is right to buy.

Figure 52. The hotel's core message content

- **Message structure**

The conclusion will be made by customers based on the arguments of the message presented in one-side; such as it will discuss product strengths and values.

- **Message format**

The message format will be clear and attractive. It will be presented in readable fonts, pictures and colours. Thus, the researcher also will be concerned about the message size and its relevance.

Choosing media

The proposed hotel will use personal and non-personal media channels depending on their advantages and considering research findings. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel’s chosen media channels, and reasons for choosing and the advantages are described in table 20.

Type of media	Basic reasons to elected	Advantages
Online presence Websites Facebook Twitter LinkedIn WeChat YouTube	Geographic segmentation: As the proposed hotel’s target customers are located in different countries and various locations. High volume of social media users in target countries: For example; China 381.6 million, India 120.5 million, Russia 65.5 million, Germany 33.1million, and UK 34.5 million. (Statista, 2015) Two way communication Helping to build customer relationship, loyalty and public relations.	Large audience Efficiency No cost Easy to build up customer relationship
Magazines	Advertising on industry related magazines is highly accurate as it only focuses on the actual target audience. For example; Caterer – UK & international	Low cost Highly focussed on target group Large audience
News papers	Targeting local residence.	Large audience Low cost
Billboards	Targeting local tourist.	Low cost Large audience

Table 20. The hotel’s chosen media channels and reasons for choosing

Select message source

	<p>The proposed hotel will involve a celebrity as its message source. The Sri Lankan famous chef (Dr.) Pubilis Silva, will act as a message source of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel message in order to attract more customers. He is, the master Chef of Mt. Lavinia Hotel and he is well-known for his successful efforts in introducing Sri Lankan cooking and food to international world. (Silva, 2011)</p>
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Customer feedback

The proposed business will conduct annual research to understand the effect on audience and thus, it will compare current customer feedbacks with previous customer feedback.

The proposed hotel's designed opening and promotional advertisements are shown in figure 53. and 54. These advertisements were designed considering hotel's communication strategy.

Figure 53. Launching – advertisement

Grand Opening

Be the first to experience our new
"Eco - Friendly Budget Hotel"

01st of
January 2018
Kandy - Sri Lanka

Book Now and take advantage of

- EXCLUSIVE RATES**
- FREE FOODS**
- CULTURE AND MORE**

Web : www.eco-budgethotel.com
E-mail : eco-budgethotel@gmail.com
Tel : 0094-81-2310941

Follow us on

Figure 54. Promotional advertisement

**Eco-Friendly
Budget Hotel**

*Experience the
Nature & Local Culture
at Economical Price.*

Web : www.eco-budgethotel.com
E-mail : eco-budgethotel@gmail.com
Tel : 0094-81-2310941
Address : Hanthana, Kandy, Sri Lanka.

Follow us on

7.7. Marketing action plan

The following tables 21, 22, 23 and 24 describe the marketing action, key aims, types of channels that will be used, who is conducting, timeline and the allocation of budget. Further, marketing plan assumptions include; reducing marketing cost by 10% at the end of 2019 compared to total marketing cost of pre-launch and in year 2018, reduce 10% of the marketing cost at the end of 2020 that is in comparison to 2019, increase cause marketing by 50% at the end of year 2019 and in third year to outsource a marketing manager.

Table 21. Pre-launch marketing action plan

Action	Aim	Responsible / Conduct by	Budget LKR	Jan 2017	Feb 2017	Mar 2017	Apr 2017	May 2017	Jun 2017	Jul 2017	Aug 2017	Sep 2017	Oct 2017	Nov 2017	Dec 2017
Market research	Understand the market	General manager	10000												
Paper release	Awareness / PR	General manager	6000												
Magazine release	Awareness / PR	General manager	6000												
Web launch	Information, attract and sales	GM / experts	10000												
FB launch	Awareness / PR / information	General manager	500												
YouTube release	Awareness / PR	General manager	4000												
Twitter launch	Awareness / PR / information	General manager	500												
LinkedIn	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
WeChat launch	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
Billboards	Awareness/attract	GM / experts	12000												
Total budget			50000												

Table 22. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2018

Action	Aim	Responsible	Budget LKR	Jan 2018	Feb 2018	Mar 2018	Apr 2018	May 2018	Jun 2018	Jul 2018	Aug 2018	Sep 2018	Oct 2018	Nov 2018	Dec 2018
Market research	Understand the market	General manager	7000												
Paper advertise	Awareness / PR / remind	General manager	2000												
Magazine advertise	Awareness / PR / remind	General manager	3000												
Cause marketing	PR	General manager	15000												
Web maintain	Information, attract and sales	GM / experts	5000												
FB marketing	Awareness / PR/information	General manager	500												
YouTube marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	4000												
Twitter marketing	Awareness / PR / information	General manager	500												
LinkedIn marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
WeChat marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
Billboards maintain	Awareness / attract	GM / experts	12000												
Total budget			50000												

Table 23. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2019

Action	Aim	Responsible	Budget LKR	Jan 2019	Feb 2019	Mar 2019	Apr 2019	May 2019	Jun 2019	Jul 2019	Aug 2019	Sep 2019	Oct 2019	Nov 2019	Dec 2019
Market research	Understand the market	General manager	15000												
Paper release	Awareness / PR / remind	General manager	6000												
Magazine release	Awareness / PR / remind	General manager	15000												
Cause marketing	PR	General manager	30000												
Web marketing	Information, attract and sales	GM / experts	10000												
FB marketing	Awareness / PR/information	General manager	500												
YouTube marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	4000												
Twitter marketing	Awareness / PR / information	General manager	500												
LinkedIn marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
WeChat marketing	Awareness / PR	General manager	500												
Billboards maintain	Awareness / attract	GM / experts	8000												
Total budget			90000												

Table 24. Post-launch marketing action plan - 2020

Action	Aim	Responsible	Budget LKR	Jan 2020	Feb 2020	Mar 2020	Apr 2020	May 2020	Jun 2020	Jul 2020	Aug 2020	Sep 2020	Oct 2020	Nov 2020	Dec 2020
Market research	Understand the market	Marketing manager	15000												
Paper advertise	Awareness / PR / remind	Marketing manager	6000												
Magazine advertise	Awareness / PR / remind	Marketing manager	6000												
Cause marketing	PR	Marketing manager / GM	30000												
Web maintain	Information, attract and sales	GM / experts	10000												
FB marketing	Awareness / PR / information	Marketing manager	500												
YouTube marketing	Awareness / PR	Marketing manager	4000												
Twitter marketing	Awareness / PR / information	Marketing manager	500												
LinkedIn marketing	Awareness / PR	Marketing manager	500												
WeChat marketing	Awareness / PR	Marketing manager	500												
Billboards maintain	Awareness / attract	Marketing manager	8000												
Total budget			81000												

Implementation process

Action plan implementation process is not an easy task in competitive hospitality market as competitors may follow the same strategies. Therefore, the proposed business should launch their strategies fast and in an efficient way to accomplish the marketing objectives. Thus, to perform better in the implementation process, the researcher will be expedient with the business marketing plan in terms of time, budget and each action process. Nevertheless, here the researcher will take advice from media and advertising experts to achieve success in the implementation process.

Monitoring & control

During the marketing plan implementation, the researcher will continually monitor and evaluate the process in order to keep it in right track. The marketing plan control process includes; setting specific goals, measuring the performance, evaluating performance and finally taking action, if there is gap in between expected performance and current performance.

Chapter 08 -Human resources

8.1. The proposed hotel HRM model

The importance of human resources has been given much attention in today's business world as it leads employees to perform well. Simply it is defined that "Human Resources Management (HRM) is a management function that helps managers to recruit, select, train and develop members for an organisation."(Aswathappa, 2005) The proposed hotel human resource model will consist of elements of obtaining people, developing them, monitoring them, rewarding them and engaging them. These model elements were developed considering the research findings such as skilled employee availability, average employee turnover and hoteliers' opinions about staffing. Further, the proposed hotel HR model is described in figure 55.

Figure 55. The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel HR model

8.2. The proposed hotel human resource objectives

Year 2018

- Conducting a training and induction program that starts before the hotel operations.
- Increasing employee satisfaction by 25% at the end of 2018. (That compared to employee satisfaction at pre-launch).
- Increasing employee performance by 25% at the end of 2018. (That compared to employee performance evaluations in June 2018)
- Reducing employee turnover as minimum by the end of 2018.
- Increasing Employee Choice by 25% at the end of 2018.
- Increasing Employee Engagement by 25% at the end of 2018.

Year 2019

- Maintaining training programs of consistency and reducing training cost by 20% at end of 2019.
- Recruiting new employees by end of 2019.
- Increasing employee satisfaction up to 30% at the end of 2019.
- Increasing employee performance up to 30% at the end of 2019.
- Reducing employee turnover up to 30% at the end of 2019.
- Increasing Employee Choice up to 30% at the end of 2019.
- Increasing Employee Engagement up to 30% at the end of 2019.

Year 2020

- Maintaining training programs of consistency at same cost which was in 2019.
- Increasing employee satisfaction up to 35% at the end of 2020.
- Increasing employee performance up to 35% at the end of 2020.
- Reducing employee turnover up to 35% at the end of 2020.
- Increasing Employee Choice up to 35% at the end of 2020.
- Increasing Employee Engagement up to 35% at the end of 2020.

8.3. Staffing & organisational flow

Since the proposed hotel is a small business establishment, the researcher as General Manager, will take the responsibility of hotel human resources management activities. There will be eleven employees including one casual, four part timers, four full timers and two outsourced security officers. Moreover, business marketing, accounting and finance activities also will be taken care of by the researcher. However, according to the expected business growth, marketing, accounting and other required staff will be hired. At the starting point, the hotel organisational flow will be as in figure 56. and projected staff recruitments outline as in table 25.

Figure 56. Organisational flow

Table 25. Projected staff recruitments

Job positions	Staff needed in 2018	Staff needed in 2019	Staff needed in 2020
General Manager	01 - Full timer	01 - Full timer	01 - Full timer
Room Division Manager	01 - Full timer	01 - Full timer	01 - Full timer
Room Attendants	02 - 1 Full time + 1 Casual	02 - 1 Full time + 1 Casual	02 - 1 Full time + 1 Casual
Receptionist	01 - Full time	02 - 1 Full time + 1 Part-timer	02 - 1 Full time + 1 Part timer
Head Chef	02 - Part timers	02 - Part timers	02 - Part timers
Kitchen staff	02 - Part timers	02 - Part timers	02 - Part timers
Security	02 - Full time	02 - Full timers	02 - Full timers
Marketing	-	-	01 - Part time
Accounts and Finance	-	-	01 - Part time
Total	11	12	14

Furthermore, understanding employee role, responsibilities and organisational relationship are highly important to any type of business, in order to increase its employees and overall business performance. Therefore, the researcher has summarised employee responsibilities, duties, relationship and reporting flow of his proposed hotel in table 26.

Table 26. Employees responsibilities, duties, relationship and reporting flow

Position	Responsibilities & Duties	Relationship
General Manager	<p>Runs entire business by increasing profit, customer satisfaction, and brand name and guides other employees.</p> <p>Since this is a small hotel, he takes responsibilities of marketing, human resource, accounting and finance.</p>	<p>Reports to owner (In this case, the researcher and owner will be same)</p> <p>Relationship towards to all employees of the hotel</p>
Room Division Manager	<p>Responsible for housekeeping, front office department. Thus, she or he also works as a duty manager.</p> <p>Duties include: supervision, budgeting, creating working schedules, preparing final reports, standards, policies and procedures,</p>	<p>Reports to General Manager</p> <p>Relationship - specially with front office & housekeeping</p>
Housekeeping attendants	<p>Responsible for hotel's cleanliness.</p> <p>Duties: cleaning rooms public area</p>	<p>Report to Room Division Manager</p> <p>Relationship – with housekeeping</p>
Receptionist	<p>Responsible to welcome guest and reservations.</p> <p>Duties: answering phone calls, providing information, issuing keys, payments, check in and check out</p>	<p>Reports to Room Division Manager</p> <p>Relationship-with front office & housekeeping departments</p>

Head Chef	Responsible for food preparation. Duties: planning menu, food control, food hygiene and sanitation.	Reports to General Manager or Duty Manager Relationship – with kitchen department
Kitchen support staff	Responsible for kitchen sanitation food arrangements. Duties: cleaning, washing, helping to food pre-preparation and serving.	Reports to Head Chef Relationship – with kitchen department
Security	Responsible for hotel security and creating safe environment. Duties: security patrol, safety checking like fire alarms, car parking, maintaining lost and found.	Reports to General Manager or Duty manager. Relationship - with all departments

(Andrews, Hotel Front Office Training Manual, 1982)(Andrews, Hotel Housekeeping Training Manual , 1985, pp. 9,10,11)(Hayes & Nineier, 2007)

8.4. Recruitment & Selection Process

“Recruitment is the process of attracting new people to the organisation” and the selection process can be defined as; “the process of identifying a particular person to fill a particular post either from within or from outside organisation.” (Simms, 2005, p. 25) The proposed hotel recruitment and selection process will take the following steps. This process will help the researcher to hire the right people for his business and consequently it will lead the business to function at an optimal level.

- I. **Identifying Recruiting Panel:** Will be the hotel owner’s.
- II. **Advertising:** Will be advertised through newspapers and social media.
- III. **Job Applications:** Should be sent with the resume and covering letter.
- IV. **Short Listing:** Will take place depending on the qualification, experience of candidates and in line with essential skills for doing the job.
- V. **Interview stage:** Face to face interview will be conducted. Generally, it will take 15-20 minutes. The Room Division Manager position interviews may be extended up to 30 minutes, because each candidate should present a 10 minute PowerPoint presentation. The purpose of this is to find a qualified, skilled and responsible person for this managerial position.
- VI. **Selection:** Candidates will be selected in line with agreed selection criteria such as qualifications, experience, personality, communication skills and attitudes.
- VII. **Check reference:** The owner will check candidates’ references.
- VIII. **Unconditional Offer Letter:** An offer letter informing that he / she has been selected and mentioning his / her work starting day, will be sent to the selected candidate.
- IX. **Contract Agreement:** The hotel will arrange an appointment to sign the employment contract with its selected candidates.

(Rudman, 2007, p. 273)

8.5. Training & Development program

Training and Development is the process of improving each employee's performance in terms of attitude, skills and behaviour. An effective employee's performance will enhance the overall performance of the organisation. (StudyValue, n.d.) As the research has found, the skilled employees in some fields of hospitality industry are limited. Therefore, it is essential to introduce training and development programs for the proposed hotel employees in line with increasing their performance. Further, interviewed hoteliers stated that the training programs would lead to increase employee motivation. Moreover, since the hotel business belongs to service industry, it is highly important of employees to perform well because that leads to customer satisfaction. Therefore, the researcher will introduce a five-day program which includes induction and training. This will be conducted prior to the start of the hotel and the hotel induction (table 27) and training program (table 28) design as follows.

Induction programme:

Time	Content
08.30 – 09.30	Introduction to the hotel goals, objectives and culture
09.30 – 10.30	Introduction to the hotel policies and procedures
10.30 – 11.00	Breakfast
11.00 – 12.00	Introduction to hotel employees and hotel tour
12.00 - 12.30	Introduction to the organisational benefits and welfare

Table 27. Induction programme

Induction will be started at 8.30 and will be finished by 12.30. Moreover, estimated cost for the hotel induction program is LKR 10000.00.

Training & Development program:

Purpose:

- Achieving the hotel objectives and goals by increasing employee performance.

Goals:

- Making the employees understand their responsibilities and duties.
- Developing the employee relations.
- Making the employees understand the rules and regulations of the organisation and procedures such as health and safety.
- Motivating employees
- Increasing the employees satisfaction and creating a joyful working environment

Type of training	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Evaluation
Off-the job training: 8.30 – 13.30	-	✓				
On-the job training: 8.30 – 15.30			✓	✓	✓	

Table 28. Training & Development programme

The training will be conducted using two methods such as on the job training and off the job training. Off – the job training will take one day at the hotel premises and the training sessions will be conducted by the researcher and human resource experts. On the job training will take three days and will be conducted by the researcher and outsourced experts as designed by TOWS Strategic Matrix analysis. The estimated cost of training program is approximately LKR 40000.00. Moreover, further necessary training will be conducted by the researcher or the hospitality experts depending on potential necessities.

8.6. Supervision

The human resource supervision of the proposed hotel will merge with its performance management system. The hotel performance management system will involve activities including: planning, monitoring, developing, appraising and rewarding. The general manager will be the person who responsible for employee supervision and in some cases, the duty manager also will take part in it. The hotel supervision will remain consistent and fair to all employees. Moreover, it will communicate performance expectations regularly and link employee performance to development, compensation, and rewards. For example, a morning staff meeting is conducted every day and this provides necessary supervision for its employees to run the day-to-day operation smoothly. Apart from this general supervision, further supervision will be provided through linking with the performance management process.

8.7. Performance management

Performance management is a way of improving organisation performance by improving individual and team performance. (Armstrong, 2009, p. 9) Thus, performance management helps businesses to monitor and supervise employee performance while increasing business overall efficiency, productivity and profitability. The recent research of Harvard Business Review has verified that the businesses that follow employee performance management systems perform better financially compared to businesses that do not follow the performance management. (Alan N, 2002, p. 290)

Furthermore, Hayes stated that the employees were able to do their jobs well when performance management and performance appraisals were properly implemented.(Hayes, 2009, p. 296) Therefore, the proposed hotel will follow behavioural competence based performance evaluation which in line with absolute standard approach to its non-executive staff. Absolute standard approach can be defined as comparing employees' performance to establish or standardize any other employee performance. (David Hayes, 2009, p. 303) However, there are various types of absolute standard evaluation methods which include essay appraisal, critical incident appraisal, the checklist, the graphic rating scale, forced choice and behaviourally anchored rating scales.(Mostafa, 2009, p. 93) Considering all these types, the hotel will follow incident appraisal method to evaluate its non-executive staff. Thus, this will be conducted every six months. For the executives, the hotel will integrate

objective based performance evaluation which in line with target outcomes approach method. The Target outcome approach is evaluating employee performance based on their target achievements which will be arranged by the researcher. (David Hayes, 2009, p. 309) This evaluating process will be conducted every four months as the researcher is keen to achieve business human resource objectives and business overall objectives. Moreover, the employee evaluation process will begin on the day of induction.

8.8. Compensation and benefits

According to the research findings, the high employee turnover is a huge operational issue in Sri Lankan hospitality industry. Therefore, the proposed hotel will introduce both monetary and nonmonetary rewards expecting to reduce employee turnover and to increase employees' motivation and performance. Monetary reward is rewarding employees through money such as profit sharing, paid vacation and bonus.(Andrew Ballentine, 2012, p. para2) In line with the monetary rewards, the hotel will introduce two-week paid vacation in order to increase employee motivation.

Non-monetary rewards mean satisfying employees by offering noble opportunities such as flexible schedules, training programs and pleasant working environment. (Ballentine, McKenzie, Wysocki, Kepner, 2012, para. 3) In line with nonmonetary rewards. the proposed business will offer flexible working schedules, training programs and will maintain good working environment. However, wealth of studies has recognised that the hospitality employees are highly motivated by cash incentives and rest of them are highly focused on happy and safe working environment. (Simons & Enz, 1995)

8.9. Career development

The proposed hotel human resource philosophy is not just developing people to achieve business objectives. It is also towards achieving their own career aspirations permitting them to reach their full potential. Therefore, the hotel will introduce variety of career enhancement programs and will be sponsoring for professional courses. Moreover, the hotel management will offer promotions to its employees rather than recruiting staff from outside. Thus, management will also allow employees to transfer to other departments in order to achieve their career interests and potential development.

8.10. Remuneration

Remuneration is very important as it leads to employee satisfaction, motivation and also can reduce employee turnover. On the other hand, it directly impacts business profit. Therefore, remuneration is a critical decision that every top management must decide. Further, the research findings stated that the skilled chefs' availability in the Sri Lankan hospitality market is low and therefore, the researcher has introduced competitive salary scales for them.

Moreover, interviewed hoteliers also stated that the skilled room attendants and f & b attendants' availability is high in Kandy hospitality market. This is a positive matter for the proposed business as these employees' demand is low. Further, hoteliers also said that the skilled duty managers, receptionists, marketing executives, HR, marketing and finance staffs' availability is medium. Considering all these facts, the proposed hotel will offer attractive salaries and wages for its employees. Moreover, salaries and wages will be increased by 5% in every year. The proposed hotel projected remuneration is shown in table 29.

Job positions	Year 2018 LKR	Year 2019 LKR	Year 2020 LKR
General Manager	50000	52500	55125
Room Division Manager	40000	42000	44100
Room Attendants:			
Full time permanent	30000	31500	33075
Casual (wages- hourly)	150	157.5	165.3
Receptionist:			
Full time	30000	31500	33075
Part-time	-	15750	16538
Head Chef: part-time	25000	26250	27563
Kitchen staff: part-time	15000	15750	16538
Security	30000	31500	33075
Marketing	-	-	16000
Accounts and Finance	-	-	16000

Table 29. Projected remuneration

8.11. Human resource decision making philosophy of the proposed business

“Human resource decision making entails finding the most effective ways of investing in people.”(Wicks, n.d.) The proposed hotel decision making process has been centralised with its human resource core model. Further, business ethics, culture and local cultural values will be significant and prioritised when the hotel human resource decision making takes place.

Chapter 09 - Key operational and implementation issues

9.1. Key operational issues and potential challenges

It is common knowledge that operational issues and implementation issues can affect profitability and consequently make business failures. The previous research has acknowledged some key issues such as key challenges that the proposed business has to face during its operations. These include supply chain issues, quality standards challenges, organisation development, facility management issues, high labour turnover, labour supply, energy management, legal requirements, hygiene and sanitation, pest control and security. Therefore, the researcher has developed following strategies to manage or eliminate his proposed business operational issues.

9.1.1. Supplier chain

The research findings informed that the hotels in Kandy were facing an issue in line with finding quality raw material suppliers such as quality chemical suppliers and linen suppliers. So, this affects the proposed business. Therefore, the proposed hotel will import its essential raw materials from overseas and also will make sure of consistent supply.

9.1.2. Quality assurance

According to the interviewed hoteliers, maintaining a quality service in consistently is not an easy task. Therefore, the proposed hotel will introduce standard operating procedures (SOP) that include housekeeping SOPs, food serving SOPs, front office SOPs and customer service SOPs. SOP is a set of written instruction of a particular activity which is followed by the hotel. It provides individuals information on performing a job properly, and it keeps consistency of quality and integrity of hotel services. Employee training and usage of quality raw material also will be led to increase hotel service quality and its consistency.

9.1.3. Legal requirements

According to the research findings, legal requirements are the other operational issue that hoteliers stated. The lodging facilities require higher level of safety and security environment for its customers; the hotel's main priority is a safe environment. The Sri Lankan

government is also very strict about safety and security in lodging facilities so that there is a bundle of certifications that need to be approved for a lodging establishment. This process may take a longer time due to requirements and tough supervision. Considering all these facts, the proposed hotel will start its licensing and approving process quite earlier and will make sure that the required standards are fulfilled.

9.1.4. Waste management

As the primary research clarified, food waste is a big operational issue in the current hospitality market. This will be another major challenge that the proposed hotel will face. Therefore, the researcher will implement strategies such as working closely with the chef and helping him to calculate required food covers, using new technology to store food, monitoring and involving in food purchasing.

9.1.5. Stock control

Stock management is also another operational issue that was stated by interviewed hoteliers and this will be one of key challenges that proposed business will face. To manage stock efficiently in the proposed business, the researcher will follow stock management methods like FIFO, JIT, Minimum stock level and Re-order lead time. Further, some of these methods have been reinforced by the research findings.

9.1.6. Skilled labour demand and high employee turnover

According to interviewed hoteliers' opinion, finding skilled staff and minimise employee turnover will be a massive challenge to the proposed hotel. However, to overcome this issue, the hotel will offer slightly higher salary, flexible working schedules, training programs and pleasant working environment. Thus, these practices were also proved by the research findings. Furthermore, the hotel's HR performance management will work as a support function to reduce its employee turnover.

9.1.7. Hygiene, sanitation and PEST control

The primary research has found that the hygiene, sanitation and PEST control are major challenges that hoteliers are face today and these will be major challenges for the proposed hotel too. Therefore, the proposed hotel will follow PEST control procedures, kitchen hygiene procedures, and maintain a good personal health practices to increase hotel's overall hygiene standards.

9.1.8. Managing debtors

As a marketing strategy, the hotel will offer its services for credits. However, managing debtors is quite challenging and may end up with losses and this fact was considered by research findings. Therefore, the hotel will sign legal agreement with its debtors and will follow the strategies like charging penalty for late payments in order to collect the payments on time.

9.1.9. Energy management

According to the research findings, electricity unit cost is high in Sri Lanka and therefore, it is a big challenge to manage electricity cost in line with customer usage. However, the hotel will be followed tactics like monitoring, using energy star labelled appliances, designing the hotel's interior by allowing daylight, installing energy efficient light bulbs and setting up renewable energy sources like solar power to reduce its energy cost.

9.1.10. Organisational development

Organisational development can be defined as “the process of planned change and improvement of organisations through the application of knowledge of the behavioural sciences” (McKenna, 2000, p. 509) According to research findings, the organisation development is another operational issue that nowadays hotel management face and consequently, this will be another key challenge that proposed hotel will face due to its employees’ culture, behaviour and values may be different from each other. However, the hotel will implement following organisational development model (Figure 57) in order to deliver sustainable organisational performance.

Figure 57. Organisational development model (Foster, 2013)

9.2. Risk management strategy

Risk management simply can be defined as the act or practise which deals with risks. This process include planning for risks, identifying risks, analysing risks, developing strategies for risks, monitoring risks and finally control the risks. (Kerzner, 2009, p. 462) There are risks everywhere but understanding them before they become issues is an easy way to manage and prevent using viable solutions. If not, risk can be a disaster. Therefore, the researcher has identified the proposed hotel potential risks and table 30. will outline the strategies and actions which will be taken to overcome those risks

Table 30. Identified potential risks, strategies and actions

Risk factor	Like hood	Consequences	Strategy	Action
Changes in budget	Unlikely	Inability to carry out planned activities, standards and quality. Inability to recruit planned workforce.	Manage	Pre-arranged LKR 2000000 to pump business cash flow. Obtaining a short term loan.
Cash flow shortage	Likely	Inability to meet financial objectives and consequently being an unsustainable business	Manage	Obtaining credit agreements with suppliers. Obtaining an overdraft facility.
Debtors	Likely	This will affect the cash flow and business finance.	Manage	Controlling credit and introducing legal agreements to the creditors.
Reducing projected sales	Unlikely	Inability to cover day to day expenses.	Manage	Introducing sales promotions, discounts and packages.
Risk of delivering quality and standards	Likely	Customer satisfaction can be reduced and it may occur investigations of government authorities.	Eliminate	Introducing quality benchmarks, SOPs, training programs and performance management system. Collecting customer feedback and consist monitoring.

Employee turnover	Likely	Increase of training and human resource cost. Decrease of employee relationship which results low employee performance.	Eliminate	Creating good working environment, introducing good salary schemes, personal development programs, incentives and welfare. Preparing employee contract with fair policies.
Natural disaster	Unlikely	Damages to people, equipment and properties.	Transferring	Taking an insurance policy
Accidents at work place	Unlikely	Effect of reducing smooth operation and reducing employee satisfaction.	Transferring	Insuring the employees.
Loss, thieves and customer accidents	Unlikely	Effect of reducing brand image and customer satisfaction	Manage / transferring	Insuring Outsource qualified security offices.
Stock wastage	Likely	Reducing smooth operation and profit	Elimination	Introducing stock control methods
Food waste	Likely	Reducing business profitability	Manage	Close monitoring and management that help calculate daily required food covers, procurement management and new technology for food storing
Hygiene and sanitation	Unlikely	Reducing customer satisfaction and sales. Making customers sick.	Eliminating	Introducing key practices of hygiene and sanitation, and PEST control. Introducing training programs

Economy downturn	Unlikely	Reducing sales causing high cost operations and business failures.	Manage	<p>Reducing staff and reducing selling price.</p> <p>Using pre-prepared saving: LKR 2000000 to run smooth business in crisis time.</p>
Rules and regulations changers	Unlikely	Increase of taxes causing minimal profit. Regulations which tighten up on hotel business.	Manage	<p>Managing cost and increasing profit margin to pay taxes.</p> <p>Keeping the quality and standards of products by following SOPs and quality benchmarks.</p>

9.3. Action plan

The Eco-Friendly Budget hotel action plan consists of main two elements such as pre-launch activities and post-launch activities. The progress and potential activities of the action plan will be evaluated by the General Manager every two weeks. As well, the marketing campaign will be conducted throughout the year and its budget allocation will be done every six months. Table 31. outlines the pre-launch action plan and table 32, 33 and 34 outline the post-launch action plan for the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel.

Table 31. Pre-launch Action Plan

Task	Responsibility	Jan 2017	Feb 2017	Mar 2017	Apr 2017	May 2017	Jun 2017	Jul 2017	Aug 2017	Sep 2017	Oct 2017	Nov 2017	Dec 2017
Marketing research	General manger												
Marketing Champaign	General manager												
Securing location	General manager												
Construction	General manger / experts												
Business registration	General manager												
Open bank account	General manager												
Obtaining other certifications	General manager												
Employee recruitment	General manager												
Employee training / induction	General manager / experts												
Purchasing: equipment, furniture	General manager												
Set-up reservation system	General manager / experts												

Table 32. Post launch Action Plan – 2018

Task	Responsibility	Jan 2018	Feb 2018	Mar 2018	Apr 2018	May 2018	Jun 2018	Jul 2018	Aug 2018	Sep 2018	Oct 2018	Nov 2018	Dec 2018
Launch	All												
Marketing research	General manger												
Market Champaign	General manager												
Training and Development	General manager / experts												
Performance appraisals	General manger												
Housekeeping operations	RD manager												
Maintenance and facility management	RD manager												
Reservation	RD manger												
Food and beverage	Head chef												
Accounts and finance	General manager												

Table 33. Action Plan – 2019

Task	Responsibility	Jan 2019	Feb 2019	Mar 2019	Apr 2019	May 2019	Jun 2019	Jul 2019	Aug 2019	Sep 2019	Oct 2019	Nov 2019	Dec 2019
Marketing research	General manger												
Market Champaign	General manager												
Training and Development	General manager / experts												
Performance appraisals	General manger												
Housekeeping operations	RD manager												
Maintenance and facility management	RD manager												
Reservation	RD manger												
Food and beverage	Head chef												
Accounts and finance	General manager												

Table 34. Action Plan – 2020

Task	Responsibility	Jan 2020	Feb 2020	Mar 2020	Apr 2020	May 2020	Jun 2020	Jul 2020	Aug 2020	Sep 2020	Oct 2020	Nov 2020	Dec 2020
Market research	General manager / Marketing manager												
Marketing campaign	General manger / Marketing manager												
Training and Development	General manager / experts												
Perform appraisals	RD manager												
Housekeeping operations	RD manager												
Maintenance and facility management	RD manger												
Reservation	RD manager												
Food and beverage	Head chef												
Accounts and finance	General manager / Accounts manage												

Conclusion

The businesses face risks and these have been identified and cover a lot of aspects of the business as discussed. The plans for contingencies and business risk will ensure that the business can continue even if there are challenges.

Chapter 10 - Financial plan

“The financial plan or the budget helps guide the day-to-day decision making of the business. Comparing forecast numbers to actual results yields important information about the overall financial health and efficiency of the business” (Hill, n.d.). The proposed hotel finance needs to be well organised and well managed as the initial investment in the business is relatively high. Thus, it is important that financial projections are calculated accurately in order to have a smooth start-up. For achieving accurate financial projections, here the researcher will make reliable assumptions and a realistic sales forecast. The following section outlines the proposed business required resources, finance, capital expenditure, source of supply, purchasing, projected sales, payback period, cash flow forecast, profit & loss accounts and balance sheet for the first three years of operations.

10.1. Key resources

Physical resources

The key physical assets of the proposed hotel include land, building, equipment, furniture, machineries and linen.

Intellectual resources

The intellectual resources of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel are its brand image, copyrights, customer database and proprietary knowledge. All of these elements will lead the proposed business to a develop strong business model even though they take time to stimulate and develop.

Human resources

All businesses need human resources to perform their day to day activities. As discussed earlier, since the hospitality industry is a service based industry; human resources of the proposed business have an important role. As mentioned in chapter eight, the total number of employees proposed hotel will be eleven which including full time, part time, casual and outsourced staff.

Finance

The start-up finance of proposed hotel is illustrated in following table 35. In line with projected required resources; the hotel start-up cost will be LKR 25000000. The researcher will invest the total start-up requirement of LKR 25000000 from his own cash which comes from selling one of his lands. The owner's equity will cover the initial investment and the business revenue will cover operation expenses regarding planned smooth business operation. Thus, there will be pre-arranged finance and overdraft facility, in case that proposed business requires further finance support.

Resources	Amount LKR
Land	9000000
Construction (buildings)	9500000
Furniture	610000
Equipment & appliance	220000
Business registration fee	75000
Pre-paid insurance	250000
Pre-training	50000
Pre-marketing & promotion	50000
Broadband setup fee	8000
Electricity setup fee	25000
Telephone setup fee	5000
PMS setup fee	20000
Linen	221000
Food purchase	40000
Chemicals	10000
Miscellaneous	30000
Cash position (before VAT)	4886000
Total	25000000

Table 35. Start-up cost

10.2.1. Main capital expenditure items and source of supply

Items	Quantity	Price	Total price	Source of supply
Double bed	10	25000	250000	From local supplier
Single beds	10	15000	150000	From local supplier
Drawers	10	12500	125000	From local supplier
Tables	5	5000	25000	From local supplier
Chairs	20	2500	50000	From local supplier
Kitchen tables	2	5000	10000	From local supplier
Computer	1	25000	25000	From local supplier
Refrigerator	1	40000	40000	From local supplier
Vacuum cleaner	4	7500	30000	From local supplier
Microwaves	2	12500	25000	From local supplier
Scrub machine	1	15000	15000	Will be imported from China
Solar power unit	1	75000	75000	From local supplier
Irons boards	2	5000	10000	From local supplier
Bed set (double)	25	5000	125000	Will be imported from India
Bed set (single)	20	3000	60000	Will be imported from India
Bath towels	60	400	24000	Will be imported from India
Hand towels	60	200	12000	Will be imported from India

Table 36. Main capital expenditure items, quantity and source of supply

The table 36 details main capital expenditure of items, quantity and source of supply of the proposed hotel. Furthermore, chemicals and some of amenities will be imported from India due to products' quality and cheaper price. Because Sri Lankan government promotes tourism related businesses, there will be light regulations for exporting required raw materials for the proposed business. So, import taxes may not be affected.

10.2.2. Legal requirements

The Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel key legal requirements are as follows;

- The proposed hotel must proceed a certificate of business registration.
- Regulations made under Section 49 (1) of the Tourism Act No. 38 of 2005, by the Ministry of Economic Development with the concurrence of the Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority (SLTDA, n.d.)
- The business should maintain current accounts referring its own name in a bank in Sri Lanka.
- Majority shares in the capital contribution or paid up capital should be held by citizens of Sri Lanka
- Building and construction approval.
- Council approval from Kandy city council.
- Approval from central environmental authority - Sri Lanka.
- Safety and hygiene certifications.
- Wages Board Ordinance of 1941, Shop and Office Employees Act of 1954 and Factories Ordinance of 1950. (Working Hours and Holidays, n.d.)
- EPF and ETF requirements in line with Act No. 15 of 1958. (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, n.d.) (Employees' Trust Fund Board , n.d.)
- Bookkeeping, accounting and annual accounts.
- All records will be kept for Seven years.
- Personal data will be protected in line with government regulations.

10.3. Purchasing, stock control and staffing issues

Purchasing

The proposed hotel will follow two types of purchasing methods which include petty cash and purchase orders. However, the proposed hotel will mainly use purchasing orders as their purchasing methods and petty cash will only be used for buying food ingredients and for purchasing stationery due to their unit price is low. Since the other procurements are larger and regular deliveries, the proposed hotel will use purchase orders for their purchasing. Thus, the requisition forms act as a formal agreement and the management can use this form to check and verify delivered good quantity and quality. (DuBois, n.d.) Moreover, the purchase

orders also can be used as a legal document which leads to safe procurement process for the proposed hotel.

Stock control

Efficient stock control allows businesses to have the right amount of stock in the right place at the right time. Thus, efficient stock controlling ensures that money is not invested unnecessarily while ensuring that the production process run smoothly as there are no problems arising in line with supply. The proposed hotel management will follow different types of stock controlling methods due to types of stocks. Thus, some of these have been mentioned by interviewed hoteliers too. The table 37. outlines the hotel main types of stocks and stocks controlling methods.

Table 37. Types of stocks & control methods

Stocks	Control methods
Linen	Minimum stock level and stock review
Chemicals	Re-order lead time
Fruit and vegetables	Just in Time (JIT)
Food ingredients	First in first out
Amenities	Minimum stock level and stock review.

(Stock control and inventory, n.d.)

Staffing

Apart from the interviewed hoteliers, human resource experts also state that the staffing is a critical function that they face in their role. Thus, staffing issues lead management to decide whether employees are outsourced, hired or eliminated. (Duggan, n.d.) High turnover in the hospitality industry may affect the proposed business staffing. If the business is short staffed, the management will put new employees as a short-term solution. However, this will interrupt the business in long-term running as they may not be well trained and experienced and due to their poor working relationship. Thus, employee high turnover will lead to reduced employee morale and consequently it will lower the level of good customer service.

The hotel industry seasonality is another factor that negatively affects the proposed business staffing because the workload is significantly changed. According to the seasonality changes, management will prepare business working schedules and it may lead to reduce employee

satisfaction due to long shifts or short working hours. However, as mentioned earlier in the HR chapter, the proposed hotel HR model will minimise the above discussed issues and will increase employee performance and overall performance of business.

10.4. Justifying expected sales and profit scenario

Figure 58. The hotel’s expected Sales, Gross profit and Net profit after tax

Figure 58. is described the proposed hotel expected sales, Gross profit and Net profit after tax and it is clearly shown that the proposed business sales, Gross profit and Net profit are increasing in each year. Further, as discussed in Chapter 5, the proposed business projected sales has been calculated considering research findings such as tourism growth, Average Monthly Occupancy Rate and Tourist Traffic in Sri Lanka. Thus, the first year calculation will also consider the proposed business as a new venture to the Sri Lankan hospitality market and since the proposed business will locate in Kandy, the special seasonality like “Kandy Perahara” has also been considered in projecting monthly sales. Therefore, it can be justified that the proposed hotel sales projections are highly accurate and realistic. Consequently, this validates the proposed business expected profit scenarios as it is accomplishing the expected sales. Apart from that, the hotel’s start-up cost, variable cost, fixed cost, semi-variable cost and taxes have been calculated using truthful and realistic data that was found from research findings and therefore, the projected profit scenario for the proposed hotel will be highly realistic. Besides, the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel break-even

analysis and payback period described in next section and these analysis justified further; about the business projected sales and profit scenario. The hotel break-even analysis has been calculated on a monthly basis as its average room price changed in every month and thus it leads to get accurate break-even. The hotel break-even analysis shows its monthly basis contribution margins, CS ratio, BEP in Currency (LKR), BEP in Units and Margin of Safety.

10.4.1. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel : Breakeven analysis for the year 2018

Monthly Breakeven Analysis - 2018												
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avilable Rooms Per Month	310.00	280.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00
Occupancy Rate	55%	57%	60%	56%	50%	56%	65%	75%	62%	65%	64%	85%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	5,500.00	5,500.00	4,500.00	4,000.00	3,500.00	3,500.00	4,000.00	6,000.00	4,500.00	5,000.00	5,500.00	6,500.00
Sales Forecast												
Unit sales	171.00	160.00	186.00	168.00	155.00	168.00	202.00	233.00	186.00	202.00	192.00	264.00
Sales	940,500.00	880,000.00	837,000.00	672,000.00	542,500.00	588,000.00	808,000.00	1,398,000.00	837,000.00	1,010,000.00	1,056,000.00	1,716,000.00
Variable cost												
Food purchase	15,000.00	14,000.00	16,500.00	15,000.00	13,500.00	15,000.00	18,000.00	21,000.00	16,500.00	18,000.00	17,000.00	24,500.00
Initial Foods purchase	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33	3,333.33
Chemical purchse	6,000.00	5,500.00	6,750.00	6,000.00	5,250.00	6,000.00	7,500.00	9,000.00	6,750.00	7,500.00	7,000.00	10,500.00
Initial chemical purchase	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33	833.33
Miscellaneous purchase	2,000.00	1,900.00	2,150.00	2,000.00	1,850.00	2,000.00	2,300.00	2,600.00	2,150.00	2,300.00	2,200.00	2,950.00
Initial Miscellaneous	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00	2,500.00
Utilities	75,000.00	65,000.00	90,000.00	75,000.00	60,000.00	75,000.00	105,000.00	135,000.00	90,000.00	105,000.00	95,000.00	175,000.00
Initial utility	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67	3,166.67
Sales commisions (5%)	-	18,810.00	17,600.00	16,740.00	13,440.00	10,850.00	11,760.00	16,160.00	27,960.00	16,740.00	20,200.00	21,120.00
Wages	13,000.00	12,000.00	14,500.00	12,900.00	11,000.00	12,900.00	16,000.00	19,000.00	13,500.00	15,000.00	14,250.00	22,500.00
ETF & EPF	1,950.00	1,800.00	2,175.00	1,935.00	1,650.00	1,935.00	2,400.00	2,850.00	2,025.00	2,250.00	2,137.50	3,375.00
Total Variable cost	122,783.33	128,843.33	159,508.33	139,408.33	116,523.33	133,518.33	172,793.33	215,443.33	168,718.33	176,623.33	167,620.83	269,778.33
Total contribution	817,716.67	751,156.67	677,491.67	532,591.67	425,976.67	454,481.67	635,206.67	1,182,556.67	668,281.67	833,376.67	888,379.17	1,446,221.67
CS Ratio	87%	85%	81%	79%	79%	77%	79%	85%	80%	83%	84%	84%
Fixed Cost												
Marketing	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	7,142.86	7,142.86	7,142.86	7,142.86	7,142.86	7,142.86	7,142.86
Registration fee	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00	6,250.00
Insurance	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33
Training	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	10,000.00	5,714.29	5,714.29	5,714.29	5,714.29	5,714.29	5,714.29	5,714.29
Salary	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00
EPF & ETF	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00	43,500.00
PMS Setup fees	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67	1,666.67
Depreciation	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00
Total Fixed Cost	410,756.00	410,756.00	410,756.00	410,756.00	410,756.00	403,613.14	403,613.14	403,613.14	403,613.14	403,613.14	403,613.14	403,613.14
Break Even Analysis												
BEP In Currency	472,432.61	481,211.57	507,464.21	518,273.28	523,115.81	522,187.24	513,406.80	477,145.15	505,511.70	489,153.69	479,767.53	478,903.18
BEP In Sales Unit	86	87	113	130	149	149	128	80	112	98	87	74
Margin of Safety	468,067.39	398,788.43	329,535.79	153,726.72	19,384.19	65,812.76	294,593.20	920,854.85	331,488.30	520,846.31	576,232.47	1,237,096.82
Profit before income tax	406,960.67	340,400.67	266,735.67	121,835.67	15,220.67	50,868.52	231,593.52	778,943.52	264,668.52	429,763.52	484,766.02	1,042,608.52

10.4.2. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Breakeven analysis for the year 2019

Monthly Breakeven Analysis - 2019												
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avilable Rooms Per Month	310.00	280.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00
Occupancy Rate	81%	75%	70%	60%	55%	58%	68%	87%	64%	66%	67%	90%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	6,000.00	5,750.00	5,000.00	4,250.00	3,750.00	3,750.00	4,500.00	6,500.00	4,750.00	5,000.00	5,250.00	6,750.00
Sales Forecast												
Unit sales	251.00	210.00	217.00	180.00	171.00	174.00	211.00	270.00	192.00	205.00	201.00	279.00
Dollar sales	1,506,000.00	1,207,500.00	1,085,000.00	765,000.00	641,250.00	652,500.00	949,500.00	1,755,000.00	912,000.00	1,025,000.00	1,055,250.00	1,883,250.00
Variable cost												
Food purchase	23,000.00	19,000.00	19,500.00	16,000.00	15,000.00	15,500.00	19,000.00	25,000.00	17,000.00	18,500.00	18,000.00	26,000.00
Chemical purchse	10,000.00	8,000.00	8,500.00	6,500.00	6,000.00	6,000.00	8,000.00	11,000.00	7,000.00	7,750.00	7,500.00	11,500.00
Miscellaneous purchase	2,800.00	2,400.00	2,450.00	2,100.00	2,000.00	2,050.00	2,400.00	3,000.00	2,200.00	2,350.00	2,300.00	3,100.00
Utilities	155,000.00	115,000.00	120,000.00	85,000.00	75,000.00	75,000.00	115,000.00	175,000.00	95,000.00	110,000.00	105,000.00	185,000.00
Wages	22,050.00	17,850.00	18,375.00	14,700.00	13,650.00	13,650.00	17,850.00	24,675.00	15,750.00	17,062.50	16,800.00	26,775.00
EPF & ETF	3,307.50	2,677.50	2,756.25	2,205.00	2,047.50	2,047.50	2,677.50	3,701.25	2,362.50	2,559.38	2,520.00	4,016.25
Sales commisions (5%)	34,320.00	30,120.00	24,150.00	21,700.00	15,300.00	12,825.00	13,050.00	18,990.00	35,100.00	18,240.00	20,500.00	21,105.00
Total Variable cost	250,477.50	195,047.50	195,731.25	148,205.00	128,997.50	127,072.50	177,977.50	261,366.25	174,412.50	176,461.88	172,620.00	277,496.25
Total contribution	1,255,522.50	1,012,452.50	889,268.75	616,795.00	512,252.50	525,427.50	771,522.50	1,493,633.75	737,587.50	848,538.13	882,630.00	1,605,753.75
CS Ratio	83%	84%	82%	81%	80%	81%	81%	85%	81%	83%	84%	85%
Fixed cost												
Marketing	9,000.00	9,000.00	9,000.00	9,000.00	9,000.00	6,428.57	6,428.57	6,428.57	6,428.57	6,428.57	6,428.57	6,428.57
Insuarance	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33
Training	7,200.00	7,200.00	7,200.00	7,200.00	7,200.00	5,142.86	5,142.86	5,142.86	5,142.86	5,142.86	5,142.86	5,142.86
Salary	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00
EPF & ETF	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50	48,037.50
Depreciation	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00
Total Fixed Cost	433,826.83	433,826.83	433,826.83	433,826.83	433,826.83	429,198.26	429,198.26	429,198.26	429,198.26	429,198.26	429,198.26	429,198.26
Break Even Analysis												
BEP In Currency	520,375.55	517,402.94	529,313.68	538,067.80	543,074.86	532,998.11	528,207.21	504,302.31	530,687.97	518,454.28	513,138.54	503,369.60
BEP In Sales Unit	87	90	106	127	145	142	117	78	112	104	98	75
Margin of Safety	985,624.45	690,097.06	555,686.32	226,932.20	98,175.14	119,501.89	421,292.79	1,250,697.69	381,312.03	506,545.72	542,111.46	1,379,880.40
Profit before income tax	821,695.67	578,625.67	455,441.92	182,968.17	78,425.67	96,229.24	342,324.24	1,064,435.49	308,389.24	419,339.86	453,431.74	1,176,555.49

10.4.3. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Breakeven analysis for the year 2020

Monthly Breakeven Analysis - 2020												
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avilable Rooms Per Month	310.00	280.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	310.00	300.00	310.00	300.00	310.00
Occupancy Rate	95%	92%	80%	70%	65%	68%	75%	96%	70%	75%	76%	98%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	6,250.00	6,000.00	5,250.00	4,500.00	4,000.00	4,000.00	4,750.00	6,750.00	5,000.00	5,250.00	5,500.00	7,000.00
Sales Forecast												
Unit sales	295.00	258.00	248.00	210.00	202.00	204.00	233.00	298.00	210.00	233.00	228.00	304.00
Dollar sales	1,843,750.00	1,548,000.00	1,302,000.00	945,000.00	808,000.00	816,000.00	1,106,750.00	2,011,500.00	1,050,000.00	1,223,250.00	1,254,000.00	2,128,000.00
Variable cost												
Food purchase	28,000.00	24,000.00	23,000.00	19,000.00	18,000.00	18,000.00	21,000.00	28,500.00	19,000.00	21,000.00	21,000.00	29,000.00
Chemical purchse	12,500.00	10,500.00	10,000.00	8,000.00	7,500.00	7,500.00	9,000.00	13,000.00	8,000.00	9,000.00	9,000.00	13,500.00
Miscellaneous purchase	3,300.00	2,900.00	2,800.00	2,400.00	2,300.00	2,300.00	2,600.00	3,350.00	2,400.00	2,300.00	2,300.00	3,400.00
Utilities	205,000.00	165,000.00	155,000.00	115,000.00	105,000.00	105,000.00	135,000.00	205,000.00	115,000.00	135,000.00	135,000.00	210,000.00
Wages	28,875.00	23,992.50	22,942.50	18,743.00	17,692.50	17,692.50	20,842.50	29,400.00	18,742.50	20,842.50	20,842.50	29,925.00
Sales commisions (5%)	37,665.00	36,875.00	30,960.00	26,040.00	18,900.00	16,160.00	16,320.00	22,135.00	40,230.00	21,000.00	24,465.00	25,080.00
ETF & EPF	4,331.25	3,598.88	3,441.38	2,811.45	2,653.88	2,653.88	3,126.38	4,410.00	2,811.38	3,126.38	3,126.38	4,488.75
Total Variable cost	319,671.25	266,866.38	248,143.88	191,994.45	172,046.38	169,306.38	207,888.88	305,795.00	206,183.88	212,268.88	215,733.88	315,393.75
Total contribution	1,524,078.75	1,281,133.63	1,053,856.13	753,005.55	635,953.63	646,693.63	898,861.13	1,705,705.00	843,816.13	1,010,981.13	1,038,266.13	1,812,606.25
CS Ratio	83%	83%	81%	80%	79%	79%	81%	85%	80%	83%	83%	85%
Fixed cost												
Marketing	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67	3,416.67
Insuarance	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33	20,833.33
Training	40,000.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32,000.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Salary	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	268,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00
FPF & ETF	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	40,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75	55,239.75
Depreciation	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00	28,506.00
Total Fixed Cost	516,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75	361,260.75	476,260.75	508,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75	476,260.75
Break Even Analysis												
BEP In Currency	624,545.00	575,468.18	588,402.42	453,371.70	605,104.95	641,324.97	586,410.48	561,643.72	592,633.60	576,258.00	575,219.56	559,130.19
BEP In Sales Unit	100.00	96.00	112.00	101.00	151.00	160.00	123.00	83.00	119.00	110.00	105.00	80.00
Margin of Saftety	1,219,205.00	972,531.82	713,597.58	491,628.30	202,895.05	174,675.03	520,339.52	1,449,856.28	457,366.40	646,992.00	678,780.44	1,568,869.81
Profit before income tax	1,007,818.00	804,872.88	577,595.38	391,744.80	159,692.88	138,432.88	422,600.38	1,229,444.25	367,555.38	534,720.38	562,005.38	1,336,345.50

10.4.4. Payback period

“Payback period is the period of time over which the accumulated cash flow which will equal the initial outlay.” (Dayananda, Irons, Harrison, Herbohn, & Rowland, 2002, p. 97) The proposed hotel payback period is 3 years and 11 months and the calculation is mentioned in table 38.

Year	Cash Flow	Accumulated Cash flow
0	- 25,000,000.00	- 25,000,000.00
1	5,408,721.00	(19,591,279.00)
2	5,786,278.02	(13,805,000.99)
3	7,120,840.07	(6,684,160.92)
4	7,120,840.07	436,679.15
Payback Period	3 Years & 11 Months	$(6684160.92/7120840.07*12)$
Assumption	Third Year Net Cash Flow remained same for the Fourth Year	

Table 38. Payback period

10.5. Financial reports

Key assumptions

- All the figures are in Sri Lankan Rupees (LKR)
- Average annual occupancy in year 2018 is 63%, year 2019 is 70% and year 2020 is 80%.
- Monthly occupancy rate and monthly average room price are changed due to seasonality.
- Value Added Tax (VAT) - 11% and Income tax 12%
- Employee Provident Fund (EPF) - 12% and Employee Trust Fund (ETF) - 3%
- Salary and wages increase yearly by 5%
- Marketing Budget decrease yearly by 10%
- Sales Commission 5% on credit sales
- Cash sale 60% and credit sales 40%
- Credit collection period - 30 days
- Training cost reduces by 20% in second year and third year it will remain same.
- Insurance will be paid in total at the beginning of each financial year.
- Estimated construction cost is calculated exclusively VAT.
- VAT payment / collection will be made quarterly.
- Depreciation calculation will be made in line with straight line method.
- The Capital assets depreciation – see the appendix 11.

10.5.1. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2018

Cash Flow Statement (LKR)														
	Start-Up	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Avilable Rooms Per Month	-	310	280	310	300	310	300	310	310	300	310	300	310	3,650
Occupancy Rate	-	55%	57%	60%	56%	50%	56%	65%	75%	62%	65%	64%	85%	63%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	-	5,500.00	5,500.00	4,500.00	4,000.00	3,500.00	3,500.00	4,000.00	6,000.00	4,500.00	5,000.00	5,500.00	6,500.00	4,833.33
Sales Forecast														
Unit sales	-	171	160	186	168	155	168	202	233	186	202	192	264	2,287
Sales	-	940,500.00	880,000.00	837,000.00	672,000.00	542,500.00	588,000.00	808,000.00	1,398,000.00	837,000.00	1,010,000.00	1,056,000.00	1,716,000.00	11,285,000.00
Cash sales (60%)	-	564,300.00	528,000.00	502,200.00	403,200.00	325,500.00	352,800.00	484,800.00	838,800.00	502,200.00	606,000.00	633,600.00	1,029,600.00	6,771,000.00
Credit sales (40%)	-	376,200.00	352,000.00	334,800.00	268,800.00	217,000.00	235,200.00	323,200.00	559,200.00	334,800.00	404,000.00	422,400.00	686,400.00	4,514,000.00
Receipts														
Cash sales	-	564,300.00	528,000.00	502,200.00	403,200.00	325,500.00	352,800.00	484,800.00	838,800.00	502,200.00	606,000.00	633,600.00	1,029,600.00	6,771,000.00
Credit sales collection - 30 Days	-	-	376,200.00	352,000.00	334,800.00	268,800.00	217,000.00	235,200.00	323,200.00	559,200.00	334,800.00	404,000.00	422,400.00	3,827,600.00
Owners equity	25,000,000.00													
Output Vat		62,073.00	99,462.00	93,962.00	81,180.00	65,373.00	62,678.00	79,200.00	127,820.00	116,754.00	103,488.00	114,136.00	159,720.00	1,165,846.00
Total Income/Receipts	25,000,000.00	626,373.00	1,003,662.00	948,162.00	819,180.00	659,673.00	632,478.00	799,200.00	1,289,820.00	1,178,154.00	1,044,288.00	1,151,736.00	1,611,720.00	11,764,446.00
Disbursements														
Food purchase	40,000.00	15,000.00	14,000.00	16,500.00	15,000.00	13,500.00	15,000.00	18,000.00	21,000.00	16,500.00	18,000.00	17,000.00	24,500.00	244,000.00
Chemical purchase	10,000.00	6,000.00	5,500.00	6,750.00	6,000.00	5,250.00	6,000.00	7,500.00	9,000.00	6,750.00	7,500.00	7,000.00	10,500.00	93,750.00
Miscellaneous purchase	30,000.00	2,000.00	1,900.00	2,150.00	2,000.00	1,850.00	2,000.00	2,300.00	2,600.00	2,150.00	2,300.00	2,200.00	2,950.00	56,400.00
Utilities	38,000.00	75,000.00	65,000.00	90,000.00	75,000.00	60,000.00	75,000.00	105,000.00	135,000.00	90,000.00	105,000.00	95,000.00	175,000.00	1,183,000.00
Marketing	50,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	50,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	100,000.00
Linen purchase	221,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	221,000.00
Land	9,000,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9,000,000.00
Building	9,500,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9,500,000.00
Furniture	610,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	610,000.00
Equipment	220,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	220,000.00
Registration fee	75,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	75,000.00
Insurance	250,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	250,000.00
Training	50,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	40,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	90,000.00
PMS setup fee	20,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20,000.00
Salary	-	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	290,000.00	3,480,000.00
Wages	-	13,000.00	12,000.00	14,500.00	12,900.00	11,000.00	12,900.00	16,000.00	19,000.00	13,500.00	15,000.00	14,250.00	22,500.00	176,550.00
Sales commissions (5%)	-	-	18,810.00	17,600.00	16,740.00	13,440.00	10,850.00	11,760.00	16,160.00	27,960.00	16,740.00	20,200.00	21,120.00	191,380.00
EPF (12%)	-	36,360.00	36,240.00	36,540.00	36,348.00	36,120.00	36,348.00	36,720.00	37,080.00	36,420.00	36,600.00	36,510.00	37,500.00	438,786.00
ETF (03%)	-	9,090.00	9,060.00	9,135.00	9,087.00	9,030.00	9,087.00	9,180.00	9,270.00	9,105.00	9,150.00	9,127.50	9,375.00	109,696.50
Income tax (12%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Input Vat	177,540.00	10,780.00	9,504.00	12,694.00	10,780.00	8,866.00	20,680.00	14,608.00	18,436.00	12,694.00	14,608.00	13,332.00	23,424.50	347,946.50
Sttlement of Vat Payable								239,756.00						
Total Expenses	20,291,540.00	457,230.00	462,014.00	495,869.00	473,855.00	449,056.00	567,865.00	750,824.00	557,546.00	505,079.00	514,898.00	504,619.50	616,869.50	26,407,509.00
Net cash flow	4,708,460.00	169,143.00	541,648.00	452,293.00	345,325.00	210,617.00	64,613.00	48,376.00	732,274.00	673,075.00	529,390.00	647,116.50	994,850.50	10,117,181.00
Cash position	4,708,460.00	4,877,603.00	5,419,251.00	5,871,544.00	6,216,869.00	6,427,486.00	6,492,099.00	6,540,475.00	7,272,749.00	7,945,824.00	8,475,214.00	9,122,330.50	10,117,181.00	
VAT calculator (11%)														
Output Vat		103,455.00	96,800.00	92,070.00	73,920.00	59,675.00	64,680.00	88,880.00	153,780.00	92,070.00	111,100.00	116,160.00	188,760.00	
Input Vat	177,540.00	10,780.00	9,504.00	12,694.00	10,780.00	8,866.00	20,680.00	14,608.00	18,436.00	12,694.00	14,608.00	13,332.00	23,424.50	
NET VAT	-	177,540.00	92,675.00	87,296.00	79,376.00	63,140.00	50,809.00	44,000.00	74,272.00	135,344.00	79,376.00	96,492.00	102,828.00	165,335.50
VAT Payments / Refund							239,756.00							653,647.50

10.5.2. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2019

Cash Flow Statement (LKR)													
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Avilable Rooms Per Month	310	280	310	300	310	300	310	310	300	310	300	310	3,650
Occupancy Rate	81%	75%	70%	60%	55%	58%	68%	87%	64%	66%	67%	90%	70%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	6,000.00	5,750.00	5,000.00	4,250.00	3,750.00	3,750.00	4,500.00	6,500.00	4,750.00	5,000.00	5,250.00	6,750.00	5,104.17
Sales Forecast													
Unit sales	251	210	217	180	171	174	211	270	192	205	201	279	2,561
Dollar sales	1,506,000.00	1,207,500.00	1,085,000.00	765,000.00	641,250.00	652,500.00	949,500.00	1,755,000.00	912,000.00	1,025,000.00	1,055,250.00	1,883,250.00	13,437,250.00
Cash sales (60%)	903,600.00	724,500.00	651,000.00	459,000.00	384,750.00	391,500.00	569,700.00	1,053,000.00	547,200.00	615,000.00	633,150.00	1,129,950.00	8,062,350.00
Credit sales (40%)	602,400.00	483,000.00	434,000.00	306,000.00	256,500.00	261,000.00	379,800.00	702,000.00	364,800.00	410,000.00	422,100.00	753,300.00	5,374,900.00
Receipts													
Cash sales	903,600.00	724,500.00	651,000.00	459,000.00	384,750.00	391,500.00	569,700.00	1,053,000.00	547,200.00	615,000.00	633,150.00	1,129,950.00	8,062,350.00
Credit sales collection - 30 Days	686,400.00	602,400.00	483,000.00	434,000.00	306,000.00	256,500.00	261,000.00	379,800.00	702,000.00	364,800.00	410,000.00	422,100.00	5,308,000.00
Cash in Hand	10,117,181.00												
Output Vat	174,900.00	145,959.00	124,740.00	98,230.00	75,982.50	71,280.00	91,377.00	157,608.00	137,412.00	107,778.00	114,746.50	170,725.50	1,470,738.50
Total Income/Reciepts	11,882,081.00	1,472,859.00	1,258,740.00	991,230.00	766,732.50	719,280.00	922,077.00	1,590,408.00	1,386,612.00	1,087,578.00	1,157,896.50	1,722,775.50	14,841,088.50
Disbursements													
Food purchase	23,000.00	19,000.00	19,500.00	16,000.00	15,000.00	15,500.00	19,000.00	25,000.00	17,000.00	18,500.00	18,000.00	26,000.00	231,500.00
Chemical purchase	10,000.00	8,000.00	8,500.00	6,500.00	6,000.00	6,000.00	8,000.00	11,000.00	7,000.00	7,750.00	7,500.00	11,500.00	97,750.00
Miscellaneous purchase	2,800.00	2,400.00	2,450.00	2,100.00	2,000.00	2,050.00	2,400.00	3,000.00	2,200.00	2,350.00	2,300.00	3,100.00	29,150.00
Utilities	155,000.00	115,000.00	120,000.00	85,000.00	75,000.00	75,000.00	115,000.00	175,000.00	95,000.00	110,000.00	105,000.00	185,000.00	1,410,000.00
Marketing	45,000.00	-	-	-	-	45,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	90,000.00
Linen purchase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Land	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Building	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Furniture	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Registration fee	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Insurance	250,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	250,000.00
Training	36,000.00	-	-	-	-	36,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	72,000.00
PMS setup fee	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salary	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	320,250.00	3,843,000.00
Wages	22,050.00	17,850.00	18,375.00	14,700.00	13,650.00	13,650.00	17,850.00	24,675.00	15,750.00	17,062.50	16,800.00	26,775.00	219,187.50
Sales commisions (5%)	34,320.00	30,120.00	24,150.00	21,700.00	15,300.00	12,825.00	13,050.00	18,990.00	35,100.00	18,240.00	20,500.00	21,105.00	265,400.00
EPF (12%)	41,076.00	40,572.00	40,635.00	40,194.00	40,068.00	40,068.00	40,572.00	41,391.00	40,320.00	40,477.50	40,446.00	41,643.00	487,462.50
ETF (03%)	10,269.00	10,143.00	10,158.75	10,048.50	10,017.00	10,017.00	10,143.00	10,347.75	10,080.00	10,119.38	10,111.50	10,410.75	121,865.63
Income tax (12%)	532,123.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	532,123.86
Settlement of Vat Payable	653,647.50	-	-	-	-	-	511,879.50	-	-	-	-	-	1,165,527.00
Input Vat	57,398.00	15,884.00	16,549.50	12,056.00	10,780.00	19,750.50	15,884.00	23,540.00	13,332.00	15,246.00	14,608.00	24,816.00	239,844.00
Total Expenses	2,192,934.36	579,219.00	580,568.25	528,548.50	508,065.00	596,110.50	1,074,028.50	653,193.75	556,032.00	559,995.38	555,515.50	670,599.75	9,054,810.49
Net cash flow	9,689,146.64	893,640.00	678,171.75	462,681.50	258,667.50	123,169.50	151,951.50	937,214.25	830,580.00	527,582.63	602,381.00	1,052,175.75	15,903,459.02
Cash position	9,689,146.64	10,582,786.64	11,260,958.39	11,723,639.89	11,982,307.39	12,105,476.89	11,953,525.39	12,890,739.64	13,721,319.64	14,248,902.27	14,851,283.27	15,903,459.02	
VAT calculator													
Output Vat	165,660.00	132,825.00	119,350.00	84,150.00	70,537.50	71,775.00	104,445.00	193,050.00	100,320.00	112,750.00	116,077.50	207,157.50	1,478,097.50
Input Vat	57,398.00	15,884.00	16,549.50	12,056.00	10,780.00	19,750.50	15,884.00	23,540.00	13,332.00	15,246.00	14,608.00	24,816.00	239,844.00
NET VAT	108,262.00	116,941.00	102,800.50	72,094.00	59,757.50	52,024.50	88,561.00	169,510.00	86,988.00	97,504.00	101,469.50	182,341.50	
VAT Payments						511,879.50						726,374.00	

10.5.3. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Cash Flow Statement for the year 2020

Cash Flow Statement (LKR)													
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Avilable Rooms Per Month	310	280	310	300	310	300	310	310	300	310	300	310	3,650
Occupancy Rate	95%	92%	80%	70%	65%	68%	75%	96%	70%	75%	76%	98%	80%
ARR (Average Room Rate)	6,250.00	6,000.00	5,250.00	4,500.00	4,000.00	4,000.00	4,750.00	6,750.00	5,000.00	5,250.00	5,500.00	7,000.00	5,354.17
Sales Forecast													
Unit sales	295	258	248	210	202	204	233	298	210	233	228	304	2,923
Dollar sales	1,843,750.00	1,548,000.00	1,302,000.00	945,000.00	808,000.00	816,000.00	1,106,750.00	2,011,500.00	1,050,000.00	1,223,250.00	1,254,000.00	2,128,000.00	16,036,250.00
Cash sales (60%)	1,106,250.00	928,800.00	781,200.00	567,000.00	484,800.00	489,600.00	664,050.00	1,206,900.00	630,000.00	733,950.00	752,400.00	1,276,800.00	9,621,750.00
Credit sales (40%)	737,500.00	619,200.00	520,800.00	378,000.00	323,200.00	326,400.00	442,700.00	804,600.00	420,000.00	489,300.00	501,600.00	851,200.00	6,414,500.00
Receipts													
Cash sales	1,106,250.00	928,800.00	781,200.00	567,000.00	484,800.00	489,600.00	664,050.00	1,206,900.00	630,000.00	733,950.00	752,400.00	1,276,800.00	9,621,750.00
Credit sales collection - 30 Days	753,300.00	737,500.00	619,200.00	520,800.00	378,000.00	323,200.00	326,400.00	442,700.00	804,600.00	420,000.00	489,300.00	501,600.00	6,316,600.00
Cash in Hand	15,903,459.02												
Output Vat	204,550.50	183,293.00	154,044.00	119,658.00	94,908.00	89,408.00	108,949.50	181,456.00	157,806.00	126,934.50	136,587.00	195,624.00	1,753,218.50
Total income/Receipts	17,967,559.52	1,849,593.00	1,554,444.00	1,207,458.00	957,708.00	902,208.00	1,099,399.50	1,831,056.00	1,592,406.00	1,280,884.50	1,378,287.00	1,974,024.00	17,691,568.50
Disbursements													
Food purchase	28,000.00	24,000.00	23,000.00	19,000.00	18,000.00	18,000.00	21,000.00	28,500.00	19,000.00	21,000.00	21,000.00	29,000.00	269,500.00
Chemical purchse	12,500.00	10,500.00	10,000.00	8,000.00	7,500.00	7,500.00	9,000.00	13,000.00	8,000.00	9,000.00	9,000.00	13,500.00	117,500.00
Miscellaneous purchase	3,300.00	2,900.00	2,800.00	2,400.00	2,300.00	2,300.00	2,600.00	3,350.00	2,400.00	2,300.00	2,300.00	3,400.00	32,350.00
Utilities	205,000.00	165,000.00	155,000.00	115,000.00	105,000.00	105,000.00	135,000.00	205,000.00	115,000.00	135,000.00	135,000.00	210,000.00	1,785,000.00
Marketing	41,000.00	-	-	-	-	40,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	81,000.00
Linen purchase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Land	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Building	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Furniture	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Registation fee	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Insurance	250,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	250,000.00
Training	40,000.00	-	-	-	-	32,000.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	72,000.00
PMS setup fee	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salary	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	268,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	368,265.00	4,319,180.00
Wages	28,875.00	23,992.50	22,942.50	18,743.00	17,692.50	17,692.50	20,842.50	29,400.00	18,742.50	20,842.50	20,842.50	29,925.00	270,533.00
Sales commisions (5%)	37,665.00	36,875.00	30,960.00	26,040.00	18,900.00	16,160.00	16,320.00	22,135.00	40,230.00	21,000.00	24,465.00	25,080.00	315,830.00
EPF (12%)	47,656.80	47,070.90	46,944.90	34,440.96	46,314.90	46,314.90	46,692.90	47,719.80	46,440.90	46,692.90	46,692.90	47,782.80	550,765.56
ETF (03%)	11,914.20	11,767.73	11,736.23	8,610.24	11,578.73	11,578.73	11,673.23	11,929.95	11,610.23	11,673.23	11,673.23	11,945.70	137,691.39
Income tax (12%)	717,343.49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	717,343.49
Settement of Vat Payable	726,374.00	-	-	-	-	-	638,852.50	-	-	-	-	-	1,365,226.50
Input Vat	63,778.00	22,264.00	20,988.00	15,884.00	14,608.00	22,528.00	18,436.00	27,483.50	15,884.00	18,403.00	18,403.00	28,149.00	
Total Expenses	2,581,671.49	712,635.13	692,636.63	516,383.20	610,159.13	687,339.13	1,288,682.13	756,783.25	645,572.63	654,176.63	657,641.63	767,047.50	10,570,728.44
Net cash flow	15,385,888.03	1,136,957.88	861,807.38	691,074.80	347,548.88	214,868.88	- 189,282.63	1,074,272.75	946,833.38	626,707.88	720,645.38	1,206,976.50	23,024,299.08
Cash position	15,385,888.03	16,522,845.91	17,384,653.28	18,075,728.08	18,423,276.96	18,638,145.83	18,448,863.21	19,523,135.96	20,469,969.33	21,096,677.21	21,817,322.58	23,024,299.08	
VAT calculator (11%)													
Output Vat	202,812.50	170,280.00	143,220.00	103,950.00	88,880.00	89,760.00	121,742.50	221,265.00	115,500.00	134,557.50	137,940.00	234,080.00	1,763,987.50
Input Vat	63,778.00	22,264.00	20,988.00	15,884.00	14,608.00	22,528.00	18,436.00	27,483.50	15,884.00	18,403.00	18,403.00	28,149.00	286,808.50
NET VAT	139,034.50	148,016.00	122,232.00	88,066.00	74,272.00	67,232.00	103,306.50	193,781.50	99,616.00	116,154.50	119,537.00	205,931.00	
VAT Payments							638,852.50					838,326.50	

10.5.4. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Profit & Loss account for the years ending 2018, 2019 and 2020

Three Years

PROFIT & LOSS PROJECTION

		LKR		
		2018	2019	2020
REVENUES (SALES)				
	TREND			
Cash Sales		6,771,000.00	8,062,350.00	9,621,750.00
Credit Sales		4,514,000.00	5,374,900.00	6,414,500.00
TOTAL SALES		11,285,000.00	13,437,250.00	16,036,250.00
COST OF SALES				
	TREND			
Food purchase		244,000.00	231,500.00	269,500.00
Chemical purchase		93,750.00	97,750.00	117,500.00
Miscellaneous purchase		56,400.00	29,150.00	32,350.00
TOTAL COST OF SALES		394,150.00	358,400.00	419,350.00
Gross Profit		10,890,850.00	13,078,850.00	15,616,900.00
EXPENSES				
	TREND			
Utilities		1,183,000.00	1,410,000.00	1,785,000.00
Marketing		100,000.00	90,000.00	81,000.00
Registration fee		75,000.00	-	-
Insurance		250,000.00	250,000.00	250,000.00
Training		90,000.00	72,000.00	72,000.00
PMS setup fee		20,000.00	-	-
Salary		3,480,000.00	3,843,000.00	4,319,180.00
Wages		176,550.00	219,187.50	270,533.00
Sales commissions (5%)		191,380.00	265,400.00	315,830.00
EPF (12%)		438,786.00	487,462.50	550,765.56
ETF (03%)		109,696.50	121,865.63	137,691.39
Depreciation		342,072.00	342,072.00	342,072.00
TOTAL EXPENSES		6,456,484.50	7,100,987.63	8,124,071.95
Net Profit Before Tax		4,434,365.50	5,977,862.38	7,492,828.05
	TREND			
Income Tax		532,123.86	717,343.49	899,139.37
Net Profit After Tax		3,902,241.64	5,260,518.89	6,593,688.68

As shown in proposed hotel's Three years Profit & Loss projections, its Gross Profit increased in 2019 by LKR 2188000 compared to 2018 and year 2020 by LKR 2538050 compared to 2019. In line with business Net Profit after Tax, in year 2019 increased by LKR 1358277 compared to 2018 and year 2020 by 1333170 compared to 2019. Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed business is financially sustainable in terms of making profit.

10.5.5. Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel: Balance Sheet ending for the years 2018, 2019 and 2020

Balance Sheet

	FY-2018	FY-2019	FY-2020
Current Assets			
Cash	10,117,181.00	15,903,459.02	23,024,299.08
Accounts receivable	761,904.00	836,163.00	944,832.00
Total	10,879,085.00	16,739,622.02	23,969,131.08
Fixed Assets			
Linen purchase	221,000.00		
Land	9,000,000.00		
Building	9,500,000.00		
Furniture	610,000.00		
Equipment	220,000.00		
Total Fixed Assets		19,208,928.00	18,866,856.00
Less accumulated depreciation (Negative Value)	-342,072.00	-342,072.00	-342,072.00
Total	19,208,928.00	18,866,856.00	18,524,784.00
Total Assets	30,088,013.00	35,606,478.02	42,493,915.08
Current Liabilities			
Income taxes payable	532,123.86	717,343.49	899,139.37
Vat Payable	653,647.50	726,374.00	838,326.50
Total	1,185,771.36	1,443,717.49	1,737,465.87
Other Liabilities			
Total	-	-	-
Owner Equity			
Investment capital	25,000,000.00	28,902,241.64	34,162,760.53
Accumulated retained earnings	3,902,241.64	5,260,518.89	6,593,688.68
Total	28,902,241.64	34,162,760.53	40,756,449.21
Total Liabilities & Stockholder Equity	30,088,013.00	35,606,478.02	42,493,915.08

10.6. Strategies for business sustainability & Ratio analysis

The proposed business will follow the following strategies to maintain its financial sustainability and further ratio analysis will justify the proposed hotel financial strength and as well as its financial sustainability.

10.6.1. Strategies:

- The owner will not take dividend until the business run four years such as till the business financially stable. The researcher will only take his salary as a general manager. This will help to strengthen business finance in its introducing time as business able to build-up healthy cash position.
- Arranging agreement with creditors and charge penalties for late payments; this increase on time payments and financial sustainability.
- Pre-arrange cash and overdrafts facilities for necessity situation.
- Bulk purchasing and importing; this reduce the purchasing cost and transportation cost and directly leads to increase business finance health and sustainability.
- Arranging credit purchasing; it increase business finance sustainability as its provides some time to pay such as by the time, other income flowing to business cash flow and through that cash, business can make payments for its credits.

10.6.2. Ratio analysis:

Ratios	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
GP	96.51%	97.33%	97.38%
NP	34.58%	39.15%	41.12%
ROCE	13.50%	15.40%	16.18%
Current Ratio	8.53: 1	11.02: 1	13.25:1

Table 39. Ratio analysis

Gross profit ratio

“Gross profit ratio refers to the ratio of gross margins made by a firm on its sales.” (Elango, 2015, p. 94) It shows the proportion of profits generated by business that before selling and before deduct its administrative expenses. The proposed hotel’s Gross Profit Margin expected

to be 96.51% in 2018 and then grow by 97.33% and 97.38% respectively in 2019 and in 2020. This figures give a good indication of the proposed business profitability and financial health as it has acceptable gross margins. Further, the researcher has compared his proposed business ratio analysis with Jetwing Lighthouse hotel's ratio analysis in year 2015 and 2014 expecting to get clear vision of his proposed business finance positioning. The Jetwing hotel's GP ratio were 79.90% and 78.29% respectively in 2015 and 2014. Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed hotel will be in a strong position compared to Jetwing hotel as proposed hotel's Gross Profit Margin is much higher. For the Jetwing hotel's income statement see the appendix 12.

Net profit ratio

Net profit margin refers to; net profit to total sales and show how much profit a business makes on each dollar of sales after all expenses and taxes have been paid . (Dunne & Lusch, 2008, p. 40) The expected NPBT of proposed hotel is 34.58% in 2018 and then grows up to 39.15% and 41.12% respectively in 2019 and 2020. The Jetwing hotel's NPBT were 17.68% and 17.95% respectively in year 2015 and 2014 and therefore, it can be justified that the proposed business is in much healthier positioning in terms of its financial health.

ROCE

ROCE indicates; how many dollars in profits each dollar of capital employed generates. This is a long-term profitability ratio as it is measures how effectively assets are performing while considering long-term finance. (Return on Capital Employed, n.d.) In other words, a higher ROCE points out more efficient use of businesses capital. The proposed hotel's ROCE is expected to be 13.50% in 2018 and then grows up to 15.40% and 16.18% respectively in 2019 and 2020. Compared to Jetwing hotel, the proposed hotel will be in a good position as Jetwing hotel's ROCE were 4.96% and 4.81% respectively in 2015 and 2014. For the Jetwing hotel's balance sheet see the appendix 13.

Current ratio

“The current ratio measures the firm’s ability to meet its short terms obligations.” (William, Brian, & Lucey, 2008) The proposed business current ratio in 2018 will be 8.53:1 and then grows up to 11.02:1 and 13.25:1 respectively in 2019 and 2020. Since these figures are higher, it can be concluded that the proposed hotel will have strong financial health and thus, the proposed hotel will held much better position that compared to Jetwing hotel as its current ratios were 1.04:1 in 2015 and 0.74:1 in 2014.

10.7. Growth strategies

Apart from the business marketing strategies that discussed in Chapter 07, the following strategies will implement as business further growth strategies.

- **Increasing distribution channels**

For example, affiliate with new travel agents and liked by more hotel reservation web sites leads to business growth in order to its increase hotel sales.

- **New products for existing customer**

For example, the hotel will be offer an A la carte menu for an extra cost.

- **New products for new customer**

The hotel will target new customer segments like tourists from Middle East.

- **Franchising**

After the successful business launched, the hotel will introduce franchising.

- **Re-investing**

Since the owner does not take a dividend for the first 4 years, the proposed hotel will re-invest its resources on business growth such as expanding the number of rooms.

- **Backward integration**

For example, the hotel will cultivate its required fruits and vegetables and that leads to cost-effective operation and consequently leading to business growth.

10.8. Contingency plan

“Contingency plan suggest the activities that must be done when the risk has crossed the threshold and has become a problem or issue.” (Kasse, 2008, p. 118) Therefore, the contingency plan is very important to any business as it is assisting the businesses to make things go well. Based on identified potential risk factors, the proposed hotel contingency plan is described in table 40. Further, note; following contingency plan has been developed considering risk management strategies that discussed in Chapter 9.

Table 40. Contingency plan

Changes in budget or cash flow shortage	Inability to carry out planned activities, delay or stop the operations.	Pre-arranged LKR 2000000 to pump business cash flow, Obtaining an overdraft facility or short-term loan, Obtaining credit agreements with suppliers.
Employee turnover	Increase of training and human resource cost, Decreasing employee relationship and that results low employee performance.	Creating good working environment, introducing good salary schemes, personal development programs, incentives and welfare. Preparing employee contract with fair policies.
Short sales generating periods or reducing expected sales	Decrease net profits and increase product cost per unit	Price cutting, discounts, introduce promotions, increase distribution channels and targeting new customer segment.
Economy crisis	Reducing sales causing high cost operations and business failures.	Reducing staff and reducing selling price, Using pre-prepared saving: LKR 2000000 to run smooth business in crisis time.

Conclusion

The research findings highlight a growing demand for hotel establishments and this is a significant recommendation for setting up an Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel. The growing demand shows there is a current requirement to reduce the gap between tourist arrivals and available rooms. The proposed hotel's innovative concept of eco lodging facilities for budget price will create a unique competitive advantage because it fills an identified gap in the Sri Lankan eco-hospitality market. Since this is a new concept, the interviewed hoteliers and potential customers have also claimed that the proposed hotel has a higher possibility for success.

Maintain an excellent customer service, standard facilities, positioning, human resource planning, financial planning and a proper implementation plan is essential for the business sustainability and its growth. The hotel location and design also perform as support functions for business growth and sustainability. The identified key operational issues of the hotel including; employee turnover, PEST control, hygiene, quality assurance, legal requirements, waste management, debt management stock control, energy management, supply chains and organisation development. The hotel's risk management strategies and contingency plan will manage, eliminate or transform its identified risks and any unexpected issues. This means that the business will be protected. The proposed hotel business plan will be constantly re-evaluated during the different stages of its operations due to business and market environment changes. The proposed Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel's pay-back period is after three years and eleven months; this indicates that it is a good investment for its stakeholders.

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Appendices

Appendix 01. Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence - 2008 to 2014

Tourist Arrivals by Country of Residence - 2008 to 2014

Country of Residence	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
NORTH AMERICA	24,311	24,948	40,216	49,057	59,236	65,616	72,653
Canada	10,258	10,707	21,123	24,671	29,329	30,926	33,282
U.S.A.	14,053	14,241	19,093	24,386	29,907	34,690	39,371
LATIN AMERICA & THE CARIBBEAN	3,739	617	620	1,036	1,626	3,166	4,124
WESTERN EUROPE	167,187	170,123	256,861	315,210	373,063	421,037	479,007
Austria	2,651	2,409	3,925	6,262	7,991	11,300	12,664
Belgium	2,378	2,617	5,398	10,122	11,323	9,138	9,915
Denmark	1,320	1,362	4,393	6,582	8,323	9,845	11,239
Finland	468	738	1,950	3,649	4,840	2,471	2,903
France	10,594	15,886	31,285	48,695	56,863	64,388	78,883
Germany	30,625	29,654	45,727	55,882	71,642	85,470	102,977
Italy	9,126	7,514	11,423	13,527	15,871	17,982	21,116
Netherlands	13,030	11,291	17,861	23,966	26,754	22,281	24,196
Norway	1,613	1,666	3,955	4,977	7,703	8,573	9,237
Spain	2,282	2,387	4,461	5,886	8,319	8,183	11,914
Sweden	3,711	3,560	7,096	10,937	13,775	12,597	14,259
Switzerland	5,326	6,331	9,427	14,110	20,054	19,141	20,097
U.K.	81,331	81,594	105,496	106,082	114,218	137,416	144,168
Others	2,732	3,114	4,464	4,533	5,387	12,252	15,439
EASTERN EUROPE	29,440	26,310	35,517	49,249	72,401	125,695	154,153
Russia	15,797	11,834	13,278	21,385	28,402	51,235	69,718
Ukraine	952	2,577	5,703	9,967	22,348	38,607	29,882
Others	12,691	11,899	16,536	17,897	21,651	35,853	54,553
MIDDLE EAST	16,776	23,741	37,540	57,501	56,169	80,509	88,991
AFRICA	2,141	1,549	2,308	3,614	5,045	8,081	12,163
South Africa	756	779	1,415	1,962	3,048	3,366	4,155
Others	1,385	770	893	1,652	1,997	4,715	8,008
EAST ASIA	44,944	48,329	68,430	96,194	132,730	183,097	280,511
China (P.R.)	10,349	9,880	11,660	18,507	27,316	54,288	128,166
Indonesia	1,157	1,040	1,343	2,049	2,890	17,295	29,558
Japan	10,075	10,926	14,352	20,586	26,085	31,505	39,136
Korea (South)	4,300	3,695	4,426	5,485	7,838	12,207	13,412
Malaysia	5,188	6,850	13,367	16,094	21,776	19,181	23,178
Philippines	1,693	1,421	1,391	2,047	5,687	14,616	11,160
Singapore	5,802	7,808	11,875	15,953	17,273	15,546	15,762
Thailand	3,583	3,208	3,684	5,880	7,897	9,608	9,260
Taiwan (P.R.)	1,907	2,715	5,277	7,010	12,703	3,931	5,193
Others	890	786	1,055	2,583	3,265	4,920	5,686
SOUTH ASIA	128,098	126,205	175,694	237,647	247,559	326,556	370,299
Bangladesh	1,564	1,294	1,954	4,726	4,646	10,037	10,754
India	85,238	83,634	126,882	171,374	176,340	208,795	242,734
Maldives	31,564	31,916	35,791	44,018	47,572	79,474	86,359
Nepal	860	676	753	826	1,038	2,019	3,319
Pakistan	7,885	7,373	9,148	14,724	16,056	25,336	25,424
Others	987	1,312	1,166	1,979	1,907	895	1,709
AUSTRALASIA	21,839	26,068	37,290	46,467	57,776	60,836	65,252
Australia	19,536	23,239	33,456	41,728	51,614	54,252	57,940
New Zealand	2,240	2,672	3,487	4,212	5,641	6,174	6,880
Others	63	157	347	527	521	410	432
Total	438,475	447,890	654,476	855,975	1,005,605	1,274,593	1,527,153

(Annual Statistical Report , 2014, p. 18)

Appendix 02. World Disposable Income Map

(Bradford, 2015)

Appendix 03. Survey questionnaire

Southern Institute of Technology – New Zealand
“The study of hotels in Kandy – Sri Lanka”

Dear Respondents,

We thank you in advance for your time and collaboration. The purpose of this survey is to analyse people’s ideas about hotels that they may like to use when visiting Kandy - Sri Lanka. Please be assured that all information will be kept confidential and will be used only for this research work. For any additional information or query, please contact:

The researcher: Mr Nilan Samarakoon – PGD in Business Enterprise student at the Southern Institute of Technology – New Zealand

Email: nilansamarakoon@yahoo.co.uk
212577414

Mobile: +64

Please (✓) for the choice you have made.

1. You are:

- International tourist** () *if yes, go to question number 02.*
Domestic tourist () *if yes, go to question number 03.*

2. Write the country you are from:

3. Where are you from:

- | | | | |
|-------------------------------|-----|-------------------------------|-----|
| Central Province | () | Eastern Province | () |
| Northern Province | () | Southern Province | () |
| Western Province | () | North Western Province | () |
| North Central Province | () | Uva Province | () |
| Sabaragamuwa Province | () | | |

4. Will you visit here again:

Definitely won't	Probably won't	Not sure	Probably will	Definitely will

5. What is your reason to travel:

Leisure () Business () Studying () Family visit ()
 Religion () Other (Please write it down)

6. Are you visiting here with:

By yourself () Family () Business Group ()
 Friends () Other (Please write it down)

7. "Eco hotel is an environmentally responsible lodging that follows the practices of green living by doing energy conservation, water conservation, recycling and waste management". Have you ever stayed in an eco-hotel before?

Yes () No ()

8. What is your favorite hotel category:

Eco-hotels () Beach hotels () Upper scale Star hotels ()
 Budget hotels () Guest house () Motels ()
 Cabana () Other (Please write it down)

9. Would you like to take a holiday in an eco-hotel within next five year times?

No () Unlikely () Not sure () Very likely () Definitely ()

10. Imagine you are making a choice to stay at an eco-hotel lodging facility: Rate the followings in terms of importance to your decision: (1=Less important – 5=Most important)

	1	2	3	4	5
As a social responsibility					

	1	2	3	4	5
Natural surrounding					

	1	2	3	4	5
Location – easy access					

	1	2	3	4	5
Price					

	1	2	3	4	5
Because I think the eco-hotels are a main trend of today.					

Hotel design:

	1	2	3	4	5
Build with cement & concrete					
Build with Timber & Mud					

Hotel concept:

	1	2	3	4	5
Cultural exchange					
Organic food					
Responsible tourism					
Ayurvedic					

Services:

	1	2	3	4	5
Room service					
Laundry service					
Transport arrangements					
Ticket bookings					

11. “Budget hotel is the lowest category of hotel that provides the rooms and meals at cheap cost”. Are you familiar with “Budget hotel concept”?

Not at all familiar () Somewhat familiar () Quite familiar ()
 Very familiar () Extremely Familiar ()

12. What do you think about opening a new hotel that combined both eco and budget hotel concepts?

1	2	3	4	5
Very bad idea	Bad idea	Neutral	Good idea	Excellent idea

13. “Kandy is the home of The Temple of the Tooth Relic, one of the most sacred places of worship in the Buddhist world. It was declared a world heritage site by UNESCO in 1988.” Therefore, setting up an Eco-friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy is a idea?

1	2	3	4	5
Very bad idea	Bad idea	Neutral	Good idea	Excellent idea

14. How often do you take holiday per year?

Once () **Twice** () **Three times** ()
Four times () **More than four times** ()

15. When do you prefer to take a holiday?

March – May () **Jun – August** ()
September- October () **December – February** ()

16. How many days would you like to take as your holiday?

Less than 3 days () **3 – 7 days** () **8 – 14 days** ()
More than 14 days ()

17. Generally, would you like to make your reservation as:

Bed and breakfast ()
Half board ()
Full board ()
Only room ()

18. In terms of following three type of services, what type of service you would prefer?

Self-service ()
Personalized service from our staff ()
Self & Personalised services combination ()

19. How much would you like to spend for your lodging facilities:

Lowest as possible () **Somewhat budget** () **Average** ()
Very high () **Extremely high.** ()

20. What type of media are you using to find and update about hotels?

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------|-------------------------------|------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Social media | <input type="checkbox"/> | Newspapers/ Magazines | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Internet sites | <input type="checkbox"/> | TV advertisements | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Radio advertisements | <input type="checkbox"/> | Word of mouth | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Other | <i>(Please write it down)</i> | | |

21. Gender:

- Male** **Female**

22. Age of respondent:

- | | | | |
|---------------------------|--------------------------|----------------------|--------------------------|
| 18 – 25 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | 26 – 35 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 36 – 45 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | 46 – 55 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| More than 55 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | | |

23. Occupation:

- | | | | | | |
|------------------|--------------------------|-------------------|--------------------------|------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Student | <input type="checkbox"/> | Unemployed | <input type="checkbox"/> | Part-time | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Full-time | <input type="checkbox"/> | Retired | <input type="checkbox"/> | Self-employed/ Own business | <input type="checkbox"/> |

24. Educational Background:

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------|--------------------------|----------------------------|-------------------------------|
| Primary | <input type="checkbox"/> | Secondary | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Undergraduate degree | <input type="checkbox"/> | Postgraduate degree | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Doctoral degree | <input type="checkbox"/> | Other | <i>(Please write it down)</i> |

25. Are you single or married / in a relationship?

- Single**
- Married/in relationship**

26. If single rate your income here:

1 Very low	2 Low	3 Average	4 High	5 Very high

27. If married rate your joint income here:

1 Very low	2 Low	3 Average	4 High	5 Very high

28. What is your opinion about opening an Eco-friendly Budget Hotel in Kandy, Sri Lanka:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Appendix 04. Guideline for interviewer: survey questionire

- The questionnaires should be distributed in ‘Kandy’ city center area where the higher number of international tourists can be found.
- The researcher should pick up the second tourist that you will see in every ten minutes in order to maintain random respondents. Thus, estimated sample respondents will be 100 and out of hundred, 75 respondents should be international tourists and other 25 respondents should represent domestic tourists.
- The sample respondents cut off age must be eighteen and no-one under eighteen should be selected.
- The survey process should be conducted since 15th October 2015 till the end of November 2015.
- The survey conductor should properly explain the purpose of this research and the approximate time that will take to complete the survey.
- If the respondents find any difficulty of understanding about the questionnaire, the researcher should explain and help them.
- The researcher should provide a pen and note pad with the questionnaire.
- Patience, attention, values and respect to the respondents should be considered throughout the survey process.
- The filled questionnaires should be posted to the researcher Mr. NilanSamarakoon.

Appendix 05. Interview questionnaire

Southern Institute of Technology – New Zealand “The study of hotels in Kandy – Sri Lanka”

FACE TO FACE INTERVIEW

Dear Respondents,

We thank you in advance for your time and collaboration. The purpose of this interview is to analyse hotels like eco-friendly and budget hotels and to get your expert information about the hotel business. Please be assured that all information will be kept confidential and will be used only for this research work. For any additional information or query, please contact:

The researcher: Mr Nilan Samarakoon – PGD in Business Enterprise student at the Southern Institute of Technology – New Zealand.

Email: nilansamarakoon@yahoo.co.uk

Mobile: +64 212577414

1. Which of the following categories best describes your hotel?

- | | | | | | |
|----------------------|-----|---------------------|-----|--------------------------------|-----|
| Eco-hotels | () | Beach hotels | () | Upper scale Star hotels | () |
| Budget hotels | () | Guest house | () | Motels | () |
| Cabana | () | Other | | | |

2. If it is an eco-hotel, what are the eco practises that your hotel follows? Tick each one that you practice.

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------------|-----|-----------------------------------|-----|
| Organic food | () | Energy Conservation | () |
| Renewable Energy | () | Water Conservation | () |
| Land Conservation | () | Recycling Program | () |
| Waste / Toxicity Reduction | () | Community Programs/Charity | () |
| Other | | | |

3. Rate your target market starting the most important from number 1 to 6.

- Business** (…)
- Leisure** (…)
- Honeymoon couples** (…)
- Backpackers** (…)
- Educators** (…)
- Other.....** (…)

4. What types of facilities / services do you offer to your customers? Tick each one you offer.

- TV** () **Internet** () **Locker** () **Alarm clock** ()
- Gymnasium** () **Laundry** () **Concierge** () **Food & beverage** ()
- Car Parking** () **Disability access** () **Others**

5. Rate the followings in terms of importance to operating a successful hotel business:

	Not important	Somewhat important	neutral	Important	Highly important
Price					
Location					
Higher level of service standards					
Brand					

6. What, according to you, is the key to customer satisfaction?

Probe 1: Can you give me some examples?

Probe 2: Why are these important?

7. What according to you is the best way to promote this business in the hospitality market?

Probe 1: Could you please provide some examples?

Probe 2: What things have you implemented in your business?

8. How would you assess the current hospitality market?

Probe 1: Do you think the current hospitality demand is high?

Probe 2: Could you tell me more about Kandy hospitality market demand and supply?

9. “The current eco friendly trends in hospitality market are leading to responsible tourism” According to you, this statement is

Very untrue	Somewhat untrue	Neutral	Somewhat true	Very true

10. Can you explain the tourism seasonality in Sri Lanka?

Probe 1: According to you is there any busiest period?

11. What type of strategies do you usually use during quiet period to run your business smoothly?

12. Can we have an idea of your hotel average occupancy rate in your last financial year?

13. What is your opinion on the new concept of the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel?

Probe 1: Do you think this busnisness concept has a good opportunity to be successful in the Sri Lanka market?

Probe 2: Why do you think so? or why you don't think so?

14. Rate the level of competition in Kandy eco-hotels market:

1 Very low	2 Low	3 medium	4 High	5 Very high

15. How do you differentiate between yourselves and your competitors ?

Probe 1: Can you give some examples?

16. Rate the skilled labour market availability in terms of following hospitality areas in Sri Lanka:

	1 Very low	2 Low	3 medium	4 High	5 Very High
Housekeeping staff					
Duty managers					
Receptionists					
Guest relations					
Chef de cuisine					
Sous chef					
Concierge					
F&B attendants					
Valet / laundry					
Finance					
Marketing					
HR					

17. Rate the raw materials availability (fruits & vegetable, linen, chemical) in terms of quality and standards:

	1 Very low	2 Low	3 medium	4 high	5 Very high
Fruits and vegetable					
Linen					
Cleaning chemicals					

18. In your opinion, what are the major operational issues?

Probe 1: Can you provide some examples?

Probe 2: What strategies would you follow to overcome these issues?

19. How you have developed your pricing strategy?

20. Are you happy with profitability?

21. Rate 1 to 5 in terms of customers spending: (1= highest, 5 = lowest)

(.....) **Accommodation**

(.....) **Food & beverage**

(.....) **Entertainment**

(.....) **Leisure & Adventure**

(.....) **Other: Please Specify**

22. Any other opinion or comment:

23. Introduce yourself: (Optional)

Age:.....

Occupation :.....

Education background:.....

Industry experience:.....(Years)

Appendix 06. Guideline for interviewer: Face to Face Interview

Step 1

Setting up:

Take a list of Kandy small and medium size hoteliers from Sri Lankan Tourism Board and then put their names on a piece of paper. Put all pieces of paper into a box and draw tickets randomly. After that, make a telephone call to each selected hotel and ask for permission to conduct a face to face interview with the hotelier, or management. If permission is refused, start from the next. Afterwards, pre-schedule an interview date and time in line with their availability. Note: Interviews should be conducted from 1st November to 31st December 2015.

General information:

- The interview should be conducted for 08 -12 minutes.
- Permission should be asked to record the interview process. Giving permission will be optional to hoteliers.
- First, the interviewer should provide questionnaire to the interviewee and then should ask all questions; which allows the interviewee to read the questionnaire while the interviewer is asking questions. Answers should be written on a question sheet while interviewees are answering the questions.
- The interviewer should make sure to reach interview place 30 minutes earlier. One question should be asked once.
- In probe questions: use skills in asking relevant questions.
- Important things such as patience, attention, values and respect to the interviewees should be considered throughout the interview process.

Step 2

Interview process:

- Interview should be set to a place with no distraction such as light and noise in order to make the interviewees feel comfortable.
- The purpose and the process of interview should be clearly explained.
- The interviewees should be informed of all the confidentiality involved in this research process.

- Indicate how long the interview process will take.
- The interviewees should be informed how to get in touch with the interviewer later if they want to.
- The interviewees should be given the opportunity to ask any questions about the arrangement for the interview and the people who involve before starting the interview.

Step 3

After the interview:

- The interviewer should clearly verify the notes written during the interview or whatever have been recorded on tape.
- The interviewer should take note of any observations made during the interview.
- All the written notes and recoeded tape should be posted to the researcher.

Appendix 07. Further secondary research

5.3.1. Forecast Travel and Tourism contribution to the GDP in year 2025

The Sri Lankan travel and tourism sector's direct contribution to GDP was LKR 462.1 billion in 2014 which was 4.8% of total GDP. Thus, it was forecast to increase by 1.3% in 2015 and 6.1% from 2015-2025, which is up to LKR 842.5 billion. Further, this will be a 4.5% of total GDP in 2025. In year 2014, the total contribution of travel and tourism sector to GDP was LKR 1,067.4 billion which was 11.1% of total GDP and it is projected to rise by 2.5% in 2015. Moreover, it is forecast to rise by 6.1% pa to LKR 1,979.2 billion in 2025 which will represent 10.5% of total GDP in Sri Lanka. (figure 59) Furthermore, out of 184 countries, Sri Lanka was ranked at 24th place in terms of long-term growth (2015-2025) to the total contribution of travel and tourism to GDP. (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 1)

Considering all these facts, it can be concluded that the tourism and hospitality sector of the Sri Lankan economy will grow significantly in the future years. This is a good sign for the proposed business as it is in hotel industry.

Figure 59. Total contribution of Travel & Tourism to GDP (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 1)

5.3.2. Sri Lanka Tourist Arrivals Forecast 2016-2020

According to Trading Economics global macro models and analysts' expectations, projected tourist arrivals in 2016 to 2020 Sri Lanka are illustrated in table 41. These figures were last predicted on Monday, February 1, 2016. (Sri Lanka Tourist Arrivals 2016-2020,2016)

Table 41. Tourist Arrivals Forecast 2016-2020

<i>Forecast</i>	<i>Tourist arrivals</i>
<i>Actual were in 2015</i>	1798380
<i>Quarter 1 – 2016</i>	1817843
<i>Quarter 2 – 2016</i>	1882611
<i>Quarter 3 – 2016</i>	1947379
<i>Quarter 4 – 2016</i>	2012147
<i>In year – 2020</i>	2637789

As discussed in the literature review, Sri Lankan Tourism Strategic Plan 2013-2016 expected 2.5 million tourist arrivals in 2016. However, according to the above forecasting it can be concluded that the projected arrivals in 2016 could take longer than experts have forecasted. However, the above forecasting still indicates rapid growth of tourist arrivals and that will be very good for the proposed business.

5.3.3. Forecast travel and tourism contribution to the investment in year 2025

The travel and tourism investment in 2014 was LKR 115.7 billion which represented 4.1% of the total investment in Sri Lanka. However, it is estimated to increase by 8.3% in 2015 and by 5.5% pa over the next 10 years; representing LKR 213.4 billion, that is 3.9% of the total investment. Therefore, it can be concluded that the investment in Sri Lankan tourism sector will keep on increasing, which proves Sri Lankan tourism industry is one of best place to invest.

5.3.4. Forecast travel and tourism contribution to the employment in year 2025

The travel & tourism directly supported jobs were in 2014 is 352,000 which were representing 4.3% of total employment in Sri Lanka. However, this was expected to decrease by 2.6% in 2015 and then increase by 2.5% pa to 438,000 jobs by 2025 which is 5.2% of total

employment in Sri Lanka. “In 2014, the total contribution of Travel & Tourism to employment, including jobs indirectly supported by the industry, was 10.0% of total employment (819,500 jobs). This is expected to fall by 2.4% in 2015 to 800,000 jobs and rise by 1.7% pa to 943,000 jobs in 2025 (11.1% of total).” (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 1) These figures indicate, the tourism industry in Sri Lanka will boom rapidly within next 10 years while increasing employee opportunities and thus, creating positive impact to the proposed business.

5.3.5. Forecast visitor exports in 2025

Sri Lanka generated LKR 453.8 billion in 2014 through the visitor exports and this is expected to decrease by 1.6% in 2015. However, in line with latest statistics, a total tourist arrival in 2015 were 1,798,380. (Monthly Statistical Bulletins 2015, n.d.) Furthermore, a forecast tourist arrival of 3,314,000 is expected in and it predicted to generate LKR 825.5 billion, which is an increase of 6.3% pa. (Figure 60) This shows the sustainability of future hospitality industry in Sri Lanka and consequently this will have a positive effect to the proposed business. (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 5)

Figure 60. Forecast Visitor Exports & Foreign Tourist Arrivals – 2025 (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 5)

5.3.6. Forecast leisure and business travellers spending in 2025

“Leisure travel spending generated 86.8% of direct Travel & Tourism GDP in 2014 (LKR 639.3bn) compared with 13.2% for business travel spending (LKR 97.1bn). Business travel spending is expected to grow by 4.1% in 2015 to LKR 101.0bn, and rise by 6.6% pa to LKR 192.0bn in 2025. Leisure travel spending is expected to grow by 1.1% in 2015 to LKR 646.1bn, and rise by 5.9% pa to LKR 1,145.4bn in 2025.” (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 6) Therefore, it can be concluded that the leisure tourist spending generates majority to GDP and thus its growing rate is also higher compared to business traveller spending. This proves that the proposed business is focusing on right customer group as it is targeting on leisure travellers.

5.3.7. Forecast domestic traveller spending in 2025

Domestic travel spending was 38.4% in 2014 compared to 61.6% of visitor exports. Further, domestic travel spending is projected to increase by 6.4% in 2015, which is up to LKR 300.6 billion and also expected to grow by 5.5% pa to LKR 511.9 billion in 2025. Considering this fact, it can be concluded that the domestic tourism will also grow up parallel to inbound tourism. Since the proposed business is targeting both international tourist and domestic tourist, the proposed business sales will be maximised. (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2015 Sri Lanka, p. 6)

Appendix 08. Business Canvas Model Analysis

Key partners

key partners of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel include government agencies, industry associations, tour operators, suppliers, financial institutes, insurance companies and logistics services to help its daily operation.

Key activities

The key activities are the activities that need to be done to perform well in the industry. The proposed hotel's leading activity is housekeeping operations and other supporting activities including food and beverage operations, marketing, financial and customer relationship management.

Customer value proposition

The core value of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel is an eco-friendly and cultural experience which provides a budgeted price. As discussed in Chapter One, Sri Lankan hospitality market consists of some eco-friendly hotels, but none of them offer their services for a budget price as they follow value driven cost structure. However, because the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel follows cost-driven structure such as keeping its cost to a minimum and offers its services at a budget price, its customer value proposition will be focused more on the budget price and eco-concept.

Being part of the eco-friendly practices of hotels, this creates a feeling of pride and social responsibility among customers. Furthermore, fun and exciting times through cultural events will be another value proposition of the proposed hotel. On the other hand, serving organic food for its customers will increase customer values to their health.

In addition, hotel location and environment will help the customers to experience relaxation moments and have a peaceful mind. Nevertheless, individual focus which is given by personalised services of Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will increase the customer value proposition through customer satisfaction.

Customer relationship

The proposed hotel customer relationship will lead to long term relationship as its expect to create loyal customers. In line with the research findings of survey question 18, the proposed hotel will offer personalized services while offer some self-servicing facilities as its majority of potential customer preferred combined service of personalised and self-service. Further, since the Eco-Friendly Budget Hotel will be a small organization, it will be easy to focus more on its customers and provide personalised service compared to large hotel organisations.

Customer segments

The target customers will be leisured tourists with limited spending capacity who are interested in experiencing nature and local culture. The proposed hotel will be targeting 75% inbound tourists as the current Sri Lankan government is promoting international tourism. Likewise, nearly 25% customers will be represented by local tourists. Further, the research findings have proved that the target customers representation, growth and accessibility are in a highly satisfied level.

Key resources

The proposed hotel key resources include; location, design, financial capacity and its qualified and experienced management.

Distribution channels

The hotel distribution channels will include direct sales through online / at premises and indirect sales through wholesalers by 60% and 40% accordingly.

Cost structure

The proposed hotel's cost structure will consist of fixed and variable costs in line with its room charges. For hospitality business is in the service industry, the proposed hotel's variable cost will be high compared to fixed cost.

Revenue streams

The hotel revenue is generated through room sales and it will consist of two elements such as transaction and recurring revenue. The wholesalers can get the hotel products on credit basis, and the other customers will be able to purchase its products in cash.

Appendix 09. Seasonality of Tourist Traffic 2014

(Annual Statistical Report, 2014)

Appendix 10. Tourist Nights & Occupancy Rates by Month 2014

(Annual Statistical Report, 2014)

Appendix 11. Capital Assets depreciation

Items	Quantity	Price	Scrap value	Expected Life	Yearly depreciation	Total yearly Depreciation
Building	1	9500000	3500000	30	200000	200000
Double bed	10	25000	2000	8	2875	28750
Single beds	10	15000	2000	8	1625	16250
Drawers	10	12500	1500	8	1375	13750
Tables	5	5000	500	7	642.8	3214
Chairs	20	2500	500	7	285.7	5714
Kitchen tables	2	5000	500	7	642.8	1285.6
Computers	1	25000	4000	8	2625	2625
Refrigerators	1	40000	4000	10	3600	3600
Vacuum cleaners	4	7500	1500	7	857.1	3428.4
Microwave ovens	2	12500	1500	7	1571.4	3142.8
Scrub machines	1	15000	1500	7	1928.5	1928.5
Solar power units	1	75000	5000	10	7000	7000
Irons boards	2	5000	400	6	766.6	1533.2
bed sets (double)	25	5000	400	4	1150	28750
Bed sets (single)	20	3000	400	4	650	13000
Bath towels	60	400	40	4	90	5400
Hand towels	60	200	20	4	45	2700
Total						342071.5

Appendix 12. Income Statement of the Jetwing hotel

Income Statement			
<i>Year ended 31st March,</i>			
	Note	2015 Rs.	2014 Rs.
Revenue	3	731,742,995	681,104,565
Cost of Sales		(147,053,316)	(147,821,548)
Gross Profit		584,689,679	533,283,017
Other Income and Gains	16	4,926,568	2,290,972
Marketing and Promotional Expenses		(26,913,000)	(23,089,847)
Administrative Expenses		(413,895,103)	(379,436,414)
Finance Cost	17.1	(8,884,348)	(1,942,540)
Finance Income	17.2	532,424	5,491,639
Profit before Tax	18	140,456,221	136,596,828
Income Tax Expense	19	(11,048,829)	(14,277,435)
Profit for the Year		129,407,392	122,319,393
Earnings Per Share	20	2.81	2.66

(Annual Report - Jetwing Hotels , 2014/15, p. 104)

Appendix 13. Balance sheet of the Jetwing hotel

		2015		2014	
		Note	Rs.		Rs.
Statement of Financial Position					
<i>As at 31st March,</i>					
ASSETS					
Non-Current Assets					
Property, Plant and Equipment	4	2,510,502,910		2,529,136,504	
Prepaid Lease Rent	5	2,393,940		2,424,243	
Intangible Assets	6	1,278,947		851,917	
Other Non-Current Financial Assets	7.1	87,975,788		59,388,785	
		2,602,151,585		2,591,801,449	
Current Assets					
Inventories	8	29,808,973		28,631,147	
Trade and Other Receivables	9	114,904,835		99,110,522	
Cash at Bank and in Hand	21	21,347,489		22,565,455	
		166,061,297		150,307,124	
Total Assets		2,768,212,882		2,742,108,573	
EQUITY AND LIABILITIES					
Capital and Reserves					
Stated Capital	10	460,000,974		460,000,974	
Reserves	11	1,696,305,264		1,696,721,841	
Retained Earnings		310,753,593		273,926,809	
Total Equity		2,467,059,831		2,430,649,624	
Non-Current Liabilities					
Post-employment Benefit Liability	12	24,949,427		22,678,483	
Interest-Bearing Loans and Borrowings	13	116,748,594		87,353,786	
		141,698,021		110,032,269	
Current Liabilities					
Trade and Other Payables	14	114,315,878		146,800,831	
Current portion of Interest-bearing Loans and Borrowings	13	41,995,800		51,425,174	
Income Tax Payable		3,143,352		3,200,675	
		159,455,030		201,426,680	
Total Liabilities		301,153,051		311,458,949	
Total Equity and Liabilities		2,768,212,882		2,742,108,573	
I certify that these Financial Statements are in compliance with the requirements of the Companies Act No. 07 of 2007.					

(Annual Report - Jetwing Hotels , 2014/15, p. 103)